

Mathematically Verifying Metaphysics & Origins of Everything

The theory of everything in Abhidhamma (Verifying the Origin of Everything)

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Abstract: It is about a new type of mathematical discovery about the origin/existence of the universe. I have used modern scientific discoveries (E.g., quantum mechanics) and explanations about fundamental elements (quantum physics) in Buddhism to verify it. I researched from zero (0) to find the universe's origin. If zero is fundamental, then the continuation of zero (0) in infinity (∞) can emerge as dimensions between continued directions making relative dimensions. Meanwhile, it could continue as interactions of dimensions, making an emergence like the first universe. It is about verifying the root of everything using a theory about everything (sub-waves, forces) while making predictions better than String Theory and M-Theory. It is a sort of equation that uses binary moments (momentum!) of dimensions. It helped me find a few mathematical interactions like elementary waves, quantum foam, forces, etc. Using it, I have tried to explain the fundamental nature of the Planck constant, wave functions, symmetry breaking, Black Holes, Dark Matter, force moments, quantum gravity, and many more. That shows that the universe is solving mathematical equations. Let's find out how the universe(s) makes dimensional structures, subtle elementary waves, observers/knowings, and interactions.

Keywords: Mathematical science of the origin, Quantum mechanics explained, Mathematical relationships in Abhidhamma, Astronomical discoveries explained, Quantum gravity explained.

Mass = Matter \times Antimatter. Anyone can try to falsify the following extraordinary correlations:

The Proton's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Matter(59×31) \times 1.005303472855531 eV/c²?

The Down Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.023381212332223 eV/c²?

The Up Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.077816383200958 eV/c²?

The Electron's mass == Matter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.001387338009097 eV/c²?

The Muon's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.01886073187205 eV/c²?

The Tau's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.000302326214752 eV/c²?

The Strange Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.051798216785732 eV/c²?

The Bottom Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times (3 + 4)$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.008503859194067 eV/c²?

The Charm Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 2$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.024565750222095 eV/c²?

The Top Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 2 \times (3 + 4)$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.008426030527669 eV/c²?

mass charge spin	$\approx 2.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ $\frac{2}{3}$ $\frac{1}{2}$ u up	$\approx 4.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ $\frac{1}{3}$ $\frac{1}{2}$ d down	$\approx 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ -1 $\frac{1}{2}$ e electron	$\approx 2.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ $-\frac{2}{3}$ $\frac{1}{2}$ \bar{u} antiup	$\approx 4.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ $\frac{1}{3}$ $\frac{1}{2}$ \bar{d} antidown	$\approx 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ e^+ positron
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Quantum objects depend on binary qualities and activities like 0, 1, and -1 in reality. Scientists would need to know the fundamental units of the unit called Ampere (A) unit. According to this research, Ampere (A) = kg².m⁻⁶.s⁻¹. They can try to understand the necessity of those units to understand quantum objects. The E=mc² equation only shows a state of potential energy. If the Ampere (A) = kg².m⁻⁶.s⁻¹, then the E=mc² equation becomes Energy of actions = kg⁻¹ m⁸ s⁻², becoming consistent with the other units. Some topics in this research are completely new, including some laws of mathematics and calculations. Mathematical processes of nature are more complex than conceptual calculations. Some mathematical laws can be verified through predictions and discoverable or analytical facts. According to Buddhist science, emotions impact our destinies. Mental factors are scientifically verifiable, and can be used to explain the process of the mind to children in schools. Exploring Buddhist science in Abhidhamma is like exploring the universe and life. The science in it is based on the scientific doctrine of necessity.

Dependent origination (pratītyasamutpādā/ paṭiccasamuppāda) is the Buddha's teaching on causality and the process of life. Interdependent co-origination (paṭi(resistance/pressure)-ichcha(like/attachment) sm(co)uppāda(origination)): 1st moment/Khana: i. Avijjā/Avidyā (nescience/asymmetry), ii. Saṅkhāra/Saṃskāra (energy/volitional formations).

2nd moment/Khana: iii. Viññāṇa/Vijñāna (oppositely made knowing), iv. Nāma-Rūpa (emotional-material actions), v. Saḷāyatana/Ṣaḍāyatana (six sense bases/sources), vi. Phassa/Sparśa (contact/touch), vii. Vedanā (feeling/sensation) viii. (the builder of Saṃsāra/re-becoming/rebirth) Taṇhā/Tṛṣṇā (wish/desire-attachment), 2nd or 3rd moment/Khana: ix. Upādāna (clinging/grasping), x. Bhava (become/behave/continue) (the origin of 'that is a part of this/me' nature). 3rd moment/Khana: xi. Jāti (generation/regeneration), xii. Jarāmaraṇa (decay-death/break). E.g., The influences of quantum waves become the nature of knowing/taking due to interaction, and co-create material & emotional actions. That-color making form is a way of interaction with eye-form and Re-knowing at the time of creation of all of them.

Absolute time (Kshana/Khana) and relative time are two different processes. The relative time depends on the speed of decaying. Speed changes the Specific Charge of quantum objects, and the flow of Charge is responsible for the time-delay in clocks. It doesn't mean that speed reduces absolute time. The speed of light depends on the medium it travels. Therefore, it is not a constant in all environments, and a fixed existence of space is required to give it a fixed value. Hidden densities of space would change the speed of light. If the density of space changes with time, then it can change the speed of light as if changing the time of light. Therefore, Einstein's $E=mc^2$ equation is incomplete.

If the speed of light (c) = $2 \times 1.000319386826568 \times \alpha \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 / 2.05411795111383 \text{ m.s}^{-1} = 2 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3) \text{ m.s}^{-1} = 299 \text{ 792 458 m.s}^{-1}$, then $2 \times 1.000319386826568 \times \alpha / 2.05411795111383 = 2 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3)$. Therefore, the fine-structure constant (α) = $2.05411795111383 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.000319386826568) = 6.62607015 / (3 \times 3 \times 100.8900158893226) = 6.62607015 / (17 \times 17 \times 3.141592653589793 \times 1.000098980184429) = 6.62607015 / (1.000098980184429 \times \pi \times 17^2) = 0.0072973525693$. Probably, the speed of light has relationships to fundamental building blocks with **101, 59, 31, 17, 3, 2** units and the Planck constant $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{Hz}^{-1}$.

Dark colors would become bright colors due to continuous higher densities of light waves/nets in the mind-streams. The contact/touch (Passa/Sparsha) quality originates between material zones (Rupa Kalapa) due to new basic/extra quality like a sense (Pasada Rupa) and aligned quality/object. The causality would make lifeless states of knowing (Pure Gnana) with lifeless emotional (Nama) and material (Rupa) actions, lifeless senses, and lifeless contact/touch. Seemingly, the 12 links of dependent origination show similar actions in different names. E.g, 1-Avijja (unlearning) is like an unconscious knowing/upbringing (a bodily knowing/upbringing). 3-Vingnana (Re-knowing) is a conscious (lifely) knowing/upbringing. 9-Upadana (clinging/upbringing) is like an unconscious strong knowing/upbringing (an unconscious belief). Similarly, 2-Sanskara (formation/interacting) is like a set of 4-actions/Namarupa. 4-Namarupa (Name-form) are a set of actions/Namarupa. 11-Jati (generation/rebirth) is like a set of actions/Namarupa. Also, 2-Sanskara (formation/interacting) is like a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara. 4-Namarupa (Name-form) is like a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara. 12-Jara-marana (decay-death) is a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara. Also, 12 main delusions of memory/Mara justify poisons like attachments by thinking that "I can't give that to others yet because I didn't receive/use that yet". Similarly, some big things can make us feel small, like making us think that "this is a big thing that I can't easily get". Likewise, we think that "I know exactly how to control that situation". Delusion/Moha supports anger/Dosa to make justifications like "I/You can forget the feelings of sadness and anger quickly by being attracted to that new action." The recognition of those justifications and bodily reactions is a way to reduce delusion. The duality (Dukkha) of nature is recognizable. The co-arising (Samudaya) truth is the resistance/Pati of liking/ICca that should be removed to be a witness (Sakshat) of no-tensioning (Nirodha). Delusion/Moha supports greed/Lobha to make justifications like "I'll take that to appreciate that", "I would lose that because of my mistake", "That is not mine yet", "Others will take that before me". Those justifications of greed/Lobha depend on 8 main unskillful states of the mind, including 4 minds (mind-states) of greed from the "influences of others/encouragements" (Sasankarika). E.g, 1. Your attraction to that is not bad. 2. Others waste that soon. 3. You can't leave/forget that. 4. You are losing that.

The external demonic/demi influencer called Vasavatti Mara would represent bodily and environmental (external) 'poison-vaccinating memories' (Vasa/poison/Asava/influence/sin Vatti/vaccinating Mara/Namarupa). Lord Buddha started teaching Dhamma after the invitation from Sahampati Brahma-king or a sympathetic memory. Natural states of knowing would differentiate material and emotional actions, even without a support from a conscious knowing. If strong entanglements between material elements in the body naturally reduce after some time, then strong influences (Asava) of attachments of living beings would reduce naturally. Presumably, new attachments of some mental states cause increasing entangled bindings between material elements. If so, the initial/earliest state of the initial/earliest

universe has originated with less material bindings and a state of smooth equilibrium, without extremely condensed material objects. It is a hypothetical potential of the initial/earliest universe with initial/earliest (arising/Uppada) states of the bodiless mind, without bodily pain due to less actions of the mind, an uncountable time ago. But if those blank/neutral/initial (arising/Uppada) minds could wish to be beautiful like wishing to be a creator/separator of awareness (aims) and other extra qualities while ignoring (keeping back) and giving a low state/caste to the directed creator/mother (destined entanglements like destined Kamma/actionings) of the initial mind like insulting the good balance/mother, then as a result the initial mind could lose its initial state(s) while being smarter/brighten/separated and Re-knowing (existing/Thiti) in low/basic state(s) of nature/father. Still, it is an initial mind like a new/secondary state(s) of the mind that doesn't stay with other emotional and material qualities in the highest/king Brahma realm. But the deluded/greedy mind could try to go to a pleasurable (emotional) Brahma realm/husband while distracting the paths/boys of other/Dhamma elements. And also, rejecting the nearest/third balance/son of knowing in the 3rd moment/Khana of the mind, causing it to vanish/die (Bhanga) itself. If so, the future states of the mind/Citta could attract the five aggregates of clinging called matter, feeling, recognition, mental formation (emotions), and another Re-knowing while causing all of them to vanish/die due to being unable to attract the mind/Citta permanently. The aim of the mind and five aggregates of clinging use/aim sound and other experiences of nature. Unlearnings and the makings (Uppāda) of the mind/Citta could cause increasing attachments and ignorance (Avijja/unleaning) of other minds and itself, causing it to be vanished/killed by the forces of the world/enemies. The mind is like Swarnathilaka, the girl who had a golden birthmark on her chest as if she had a shining mind, like an evolutionary birth of the mind.

According to Buddhism, greed (Lobha), anger (Dosa), and delusion (Moha) are three poisons that make suffering. They can make efforts to make tenses while remembering that "I didn't give that yet, and you will have to wait to get that from me". They have a potential to be hidden efforts against a goal, as if tensions expect to delay that benefit. Spontaneous remindings would come from habitual relationships of emotions and materials as if habit is reminding. We can feel the painful results of likes and words to recognize our beliefs like "That is lovely, and I'll not leave that." "My pain aims to believe good feelings I'll get that I didn't get, and I now forget/ignore kindly-giving that to others." A thinking wave of anger is like "I/You will have to take a lot of actions against them as soon as possible or now." Also, anger makes us think like "They didn't do that, and those useless people caused me to do a lot of bad actions." A hate aimed memory is like "You have a lot of good extra things that you can give, but you don't give them to me". A strong lust is like a hate towards the same object like "I liked that favorable thing/action a lot, but I can't get that." We can be kind to attractive things while thinking like "It is innocent", "I don't want to harm it", "Others protect it", "Not a dangerous useless demon/animal," "Not a deep black hole," "That action is not trying to take anything now," "Not like a dirty garbage", "You or others shouldn't use me as they wish for useless actions without my permission", "Not a very old evil witch/ghost, Not staying alone lonely without showing abilities, Not requesting for attention," "Not a tight/solid black cube/shit," "Not a fully dark prison," "Not trapped in the middle of unmovable black rocks," "Not a formless zero & infinity like an extremely small black dot without a shape. Not a singular unit without parts." "The attractive thing/action/beauty is like a belief, and I was thinking that I'll not be disappointed about that belief". A greed aimed care is like "I'm unable to take care of them yet, and I can't help them without pleasurable feelings." A fear aimed delusion is like "Others can steal my things easily, and I don't have enough power to stop that soon." A view/belief resisting dull delusion is like "That view/belief is not good, and I'm disappointed about that view/belief." We can let things happen unintentionally without thinking like "That belief is not bad, and I'll not be disappointed." An ego aimed delusion is like "That is the only solution, and they know that I explained about that better this time." An overconfidence aimed delusion is like "They think that they do it correctly, but I'll have to do a lot of things yet." Also, a delusion is like "They would continue working against us, making me responsible to react with extra effort." An anger aimed blame is like "Others do bad actions because of them, but they don't show that they like to do that." A delusional motivation is like "I have done a lot of things for them, and they are thinking that I protected them." A self aimed delusion is like "I got/won it, and I can keep it now because no one else is here to take it from me now." A painful attraction with an aim to win attractive things hiddenly think like "I look at that because I'm not a loser." A delusional ownership is like "I did it, and I must take the responsibility because those memories belong to me." If a person is emotionally hungry, then looking at others nearby to develop efforts can help that person to share foods. When we give food to others like helpless animals nearby before we start eating foods, the body remembers to give. Urgent needs can make frustrations, and develop overconfidence with beliefs to be quick by depending on memory. A lovely greed is like "You consistently give love to me, and I'm unable to avoid it because you are special to me." The delusion in bravery is "I'm ready to handle any situation because I'm prepared with enough tools to protect me." An attention aimed delusion is like "I have enough body parts like hands and legs, and I can save others from them."

A self-body aimed egoistic belief is like "I know that I understood it myself, and I showed my higher intelligence."
 An anger aimed requirement of delusions is "You are/were hiding valuable things, and you didn't care about others."
 A delusional safety is like "I & some others protect my things always, and I have names, things, fixed feelings, etc."
 An attachment with a wish to stay with our things to protect us is "I'll be powerful enough to hold body-mountains."

Skillful thinking patterns are like "I'm not going to do anything to harm anyone." "This is an effort to understand the truth and skill." "May all the thoughts be good, and be the path to cessation." "The mind and the body are not mine."
 "You can fully stop overreactions that you haven't done yet." "When they make you aggressive, wait to feel good."
 "When you receive a blame, you can smile to be relaxed." "You are not an owner to expect anything, so be relaxed."
 "This body doesn't belong to the mind, and habitual aims of the body would aim to give bodily elements to others."
 Lord Buddha would not radiate bad outgoing carriers (4 Karisa) with Cittaja, Uthuja, Āharaja, and Kammaja forms.
 The believing-mind ignores multiple causes of situations, thinking like "That is the only cause for this to happen."
 A reaction with delusion can think like "Your belief is wrong because it is not like my belief, and my belief is correct."
 A reaction with anger is bad. If we shouldn't be kind to bad actions/beliefs, then we can use selfless thoughts (Sati).
 Some groups use competition to justify bad actions, as if they have a license to become criminals against opposition.
 Violence is a bad solution, and it is an act of helpless and ignorant beings who don't use intelligence/causality well.
 Violence can lead to tensions, causing us to be busy with useless news on some special days and weeks like Vesak.
 We can disown bad memories by thinking like "Some people/trees have done those actions due to some situations."
 "An attraction/Raga is like a burning, and I must reduce burning the mind, as if moving away from devils/Pisacha."
 "The mind, mental factors/thoughts and bodily actions are aims, but the mind doesn't need to be aims." "The mind doesn't need to aim for colors, sounds, smells, tastes, feelings, and knowings." "Nothing like me is here to continue."
 "When some qualities and actions make interactions due to their natures and situations, nothing to be surprised of."
 "We can be kind to good streams of minds regardless of actions of bad streams of minds or attractive observations."
 The mind-senses can be kind to the six senses while thinking like "Not permanently closed caves," "Not colorless,"
 "Not soundless," "Not smell-less," "Not tasteless," "Not feelingless," "Not imaginationless," "Not conscienceless,"
 "Not avoiding relationships," "Not reducing connections," "Not leaving the past, present, and future to forget them."
 "Not staying outside in between hot lights without a move or touch, and bodily senses would not be burned inside."
 "Not expecting anything from outside to keep the pain inside for a long time, and pain of likes in blood hates relief."
 Some high egos would reject some other high egos. Some high egos would pretend like low egos to expect benefits.
 "If you don't have any good solution for that problem, then there is nothing to worry about that problem for now."
 "The problems and solutions are so complex, and I would need to use extremely high efforts to handle all of them."
 Unenlightened people shouldn't try to tell others to stop liking at once to be enlightened. Give the right knowledge.
 Mind-senses make thinking comments/voices by using outputs of five other senses and memories. But mind-senses should not have a direct relationship with the five senses according to the correct theory of momentariness. Dualistic waves of attractive mind-states (greed) and resisting co-arisen-states (pain) in the body should not continue making those unskillful causal connections by using outputs of previous momentary five senses and previous mind-streams.
 "The mind shouldn't continue taking and burning locations, as if killing, stealing, grasping, lying, & misusing them."
 "The mind is not feeling an extremely rotten dead body with pests-infected flesh while decaying into broken bones."
 "When a few others have a lot of extra qualities/shapes, I can be kind to them without a worry to give more of that."
 Fully enlightened hearts would avoid physical contact with each other to avoid insults and give respect to the mind.
 The 6 results of the 6 senses depend on illusory recognition & mental factors. Knowledge can transform recognition.
 When Bikkus give the right knowledge without expecting anything from others, we need knowledge to recognize it.
 We can honestly investigate the knowledge related to causality, to receive the right knowledge without wasting time.
 Others should take the responsibility of their lives to be good whether we will pay back debts we owe to them or not.

The body is unaware about experiences of the mind in a previous life. Therefore, the body is unable to inform the mind about a previous life without a special support from the mind. The mind naturally takes many habitual paths and patterns of nature. But usually, consciousness tries to believe a very few outcomes. Trained observations (Samma Ditthi) are helpful to train the mind to take better paths and better patterns. Beliefs, intentions, delusions (Moha) and other emotions of a person would interact with collective emotional fields of closely related groups of causality due to causal relationships between them. We can try to find verifiable causal relationships of emotions to manage them. A spontaneous laugh is a result of bodily pressure and delusion (Moha). If a laugh interacts with some collective wrong beliefs, then some causal rejections would work against that laugh. Ignitions can happen due to our new actions. Crying would attract bad results because the act of crying depends on anger. The six senses, and other

elements (Dhamma Dathu) cause the mind to think spontaneously without a thinker. The nearest cause of thinking is like a womb that has an ability to generate new thoughts. Therefore, the 'womb-cause remembering/memorising' (Yoniso Manasikara) is helpful to understand the patterns of understanding without words, to reduce believing words of languages. Awareness is not a thinker. The mind can recognize the interactions of the six senses without words of a thinker. The awareness about the six senses, sense-objects, emotions, and knowing help to understand meanings of experiences without words while helping the mind reduce creating a words-thinker, and help the mind and body to make a trained stillness/one-pointedness (Samma Samadhi). Also, an observation of a distant point for a long time without trying to recognize an object would help to develop one-pointedness against attractive streams of awareness. Some patterns of thinking disturb observations of the six senses while adding greed, anger, and delusion with words. Our thinking efforts to avoid attractions reduce due to tiredness. The recognition of limits of efforts helps to let go. Strong needs can cause us to think like "I believe that it will happen, and I'll not be disappointed even if I'm wrong." A strong aim to get a thing would make the body wait with tension to get it first, preventing the mind from getting it. If some beings use greed a lot to get things from others, then an interaction between them would create bad results. We shouldn't expect respect from greed, anger, and delusion. If others disrespect us, then they would expect or get disrespect. Some bodily entanglements with parents would impact us. And any memorization against parents would attract bad reactions. The recognition of signs in nature and actions to read nature and actions is a way to understand reaction/Karma. The word conscious would mean life-thoughts like a son of aims. Good thoughts would be the only way to liberation with the transformed aims like "nothing to touch, nothing to feel, nothing to recognize, and nothing to imagine." Devadatta acted against the Lord Buddha due to hatred. That would indicate a competitive nature of Humans in this era. Languages, religions and nature help to see/imagine supreme Buddha. If Jesus was a Buddhist or a truth seeker, then he could try to teach the truths unless our intrinsic delusions/sins prevent that from happening. We would need to be kind to all the enemies who come to kill us, as if allowing causes to kill us to be enlightened. But we should be prepared to leave all the worlds before imagining murderers/Mara, to be kind as if attracting them. The mind can allow the body & mental factors to reduce the observations of the mind to kill new life, to be nothing. We can stop observing colors, and etc, as if being kind to blackness, silence, odour, bitterness, pain, and unknowing. Knowing & cognition depend on habitual and interdependent opposite knowing, but we can analyse that to be good. Lord Buddha used the word Mogha/empty to scold some bad people. But he had reduced the need to control others.!

Ideas are transformed/voiced feelings. We can give up the need to prove the ownership of ideas to reduce self-belief. When the mind selects unskilful options secretly, we can tell it to select skilful options to be relaxed and kind. We can reduce expecting glory and praise when we try to stop rebirth because causality makes expectations with them. Unbroken connections of emerging formless/unbalanced infinities/unities would continue momentary rebirths of the mind. Trained observations and trained knowledge would fill some emerging unbalanced nothingnesses as a path to liberation. Earned knowledge about the path to enlightenment is like a gift that a person can give as an inheritance to a child. A person is a process that depends on ultimate processes. Taste indicates rising actions, as if increasing that. Smell indicates falling actions, as if decreasing that. Color indicates distant actions, as if using from a distant action. Sound indicates close actions, as if vibrations. Craving/Tanha indicates grasping action, as if binding distant actions.

Long streams of delusional feelings can depend on long wavelengths of waves in the body. The mind can use long streams of feelings to balance them. E.g., 'The mind doesn't have a body. It can't save others. It can give knowledge.' 'The body makes tensions by depending on old habits. But the mind is always new, and it is not responsible for that.' 'Colors and other extra qualities are not pleasurable surprises/miracles/winners, and they/we are like tension takers.' When the mind is burning in the body, we can imagine the body being burned & tortured everyday by enemies of us. The mind would give up life by imagining extreme levels of pain when cutting the body 3 times a day for 100 years. When the mind feels pain in some body parts due to attachments, we can imagine the mind in them to send kindness. We can choose to be unaware about objects that we can aim to joke about because jokes can aim to lie about actions. Structural nets of relationships make the mind name/aim huge bodies, and the bodiless mind tries to use hard bodies. Painful feelings are like tortures in the body. We can stop breathing for a few seconds to recognize more of them. We can recognise thinking patterns that we have used to justify the fears of losing the mind and body, to reduce the fear. When we don't avoid riskful actions and greed while learning anything during a tough time, the result would be bad. Feelings of need, loss, hopelessness, mistake, and death can be transformed into worse imaginations to reduce them. Finally, we can imagine not having freedom to speak & think useless egoistic words in any situation due to causality. The aims of touch/contact like streams of feelings and voiced interpretations can't make a person with fixed feelings. We can reduce bodily and externally influenced feelings of insecurity in us while staying in darkness and silence to

reduce observing extra qualities like colors and sounds with their extra tensions, as if feeling secure without tension. We can watch colors of people with less tension by thinking like “Those colors would represent trees like mothers.” The mind can reduce some hidden attachments by imagining it giving back causes of tensions it got through senses. When body parts make pain due to causes, we can imagine the mind in them to send kindness to nearby blood/flesh. Consciousnesses (life-aims) would mainly continue in blood and flesh with connections like lifetimes of the mind. A beginner can think like “I don't know how to get well soon yet, and I can't recognize multiple causes of feelings yet.” “The mind is everything. What you think, you become,” is commonly attributed to the Buddha, but it isn't scriptural. A life is like a tree with or without wished intentions. ‘Those trees can't corrupt knowledge without multiple causes.’ Aim of the mind would have a tension like a Karma with a large coverage like a finger that holds a body-mountain. The mind can use the heart to guess the breathing process as feelings of memory in the heart, while giving kindness. A lot of delusions depend on unskilful thinking patterns with strong tensions like burning, pushing, and dull tension. The imbalance of the mind bends & uses a lot of parts/aims, but no one is outside or inside the body with fixed parts. The belief of a fixed soul/self can be reduced by ignoring the word 'I' for a while to replace a word like Mara/demon. One person can use 10 main faculties/Indriya/faces as Saddha, Virya, Sati, Samadhi, Prajna and 5 opposite faculties. Virtue/Sila-aim/sign/lakkhana draws lines to save the mind/Sita from bad faculties when knowledge/Pandith is away. When bad faculties force the mind, we can imagine not doing anything as if allowing good faculties to take actions. When the mind is forced to take pleasurable actions, it can take satisfiable actions with an aim to protect virtue/Sila.!

1. Introduction

This new research area is entirely a new type of mathematical discovery about the origin of the first universe, which was developed—as a theory of mathematical symmetries or as symmetric laws in nature—using the most fundamental laws in the earliest possible universe. Surprisingly, scientific discoveries and Buddhism (Abhidhamma) helped me verify and continue the calculations. The earliest moment of nothingness (the universe's origin) could have been infinitely nothing as a relatively infinite moment until the symmetric laws made the dimensions in directions. “I wrote a book about the origin of the universe and Buddhist explanations about the universe, in 2020 *(1)”. I researched it based on mathematical interactions of dimensional symmetries and the most fundamental technical aspects of the universe. This analyzes it with a few extensions while introducing a structure for the fundamental waves to compare and explain the Standard Model of Elementary Sub-waves in quantum physics, etc.

I would easily explain the universe's existence using this fundamental type of mathematics. And the interactions in the calculations explain how they could make Time, length (Planck constants), waves, mass/energy, forces, and elementary sub-waves, including the Higgs Boson, with the possibility of making an atomic structure.

There are almost no motionless places in space as “the space is filled with fluctuations of energy fields/mass called quantum foam *(2)”. “Virtual matter and antimatter appear and disappear in space *(3)”. There are possibilities in the quantum levels that can make the disorder in the universe. And according to the second law of thermodynamics, entropy always increases. The interactions can make irreversible interactions. So, they would make the flow of time irreversible, even if those interactions are related. It seems that Time is an absolute fundamental phenomenon. And space and other energies look like fluctuations of Time between dimensions. Suppose we can understand how all the dimensions are combined mathematically, becoming the fundamental structures and time. In that case, we can easily understand that we don't need any unscientific explanation to explain the interactions of quantum objects/fields, etc.

The calculation shows how dimensional objects (aims/arms) emerged using dimensional gaps between the six main directions. I write an initial/smallest (0) distance/gap like this +0-0 as it shows a direction without using a distance. Knowing-separation is like creating a separation due to time. I developed the calculation using simple mathematical laws with a natural type of (universal) mathematics that I discovered using symmetries, order, probabilities, etc.

The universe is a process. And that process is almost based on mathematical symmetries, probabilities, dimensions (aims), etc. “Scientists could discover a lot of symmetric quantum interactions experimentally. And they helped scientists to predict the existence of more elementary sub-waves (E.g., The Higgs Boson was proposed in 1964 by Peter Higgs. Discovered in 2012) *(4)”. It suggests that quantum sub-waves must follow the rules of symmetric

dimensional entanglements. This mathematical research is about the origin of the universe. And the results of it can help scientists conduct more experiments to find and verify the fundamentals of Quantum Mechanics, knowing, etc.

If the first universe was A THING with minimum nothings (nulls), then the direction of a nothing (0) thing = +0-0. According to this mathematical formula: $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ OR $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + ab + ba + b^2$. Next moment:

$$\begin{array}{l|l}
 (+0-0)^2 = 0^2 - (+1-(-1)) \times 0 \times 0 + 0^2 & (-0+0)^2 = 0^2 + (-1-(+1)) \times 0 \times 0 + 0^2 \text{ --- Initial knowing!} \\
 = (+1-(-1)) \times 0^2 - (+1-(-1)) \times 0 \times 0 & = -(-1-(+1)) \times 0^2 + (-1-(+1)) \times 0 \times 0 \text{ --- A knowing potential.} \\
 = (+1-(-1)) \times 0.0 - (+1-(-1)) \times 0.0 & = -(-1-(+1)) \times 0.0 + (-1-(+1)) \times 0.0 \text{ --- A knowing with action.} \\
 = \{(+1-(-1)) \times (+0.0 - 0.0)\} \text{ --- smallest gap} & = \{(-1-(+1)) \times (-0.0 + 0.0)\} \text{ --- A derived action and quality.} \\
 (+0-0)^6 = (+0-0)^2 \times (+0-0)^2 \times (+0-0)^2 & (-0+0)^6 = (-0+0)^2 \times (-0+0)^2 \times (-0+0)^2 \text{ --- A collection!}
 \end{array}$$

Those initial knowing qualities could necessarily co-originate with anti-knowing qualities/actions/interactions. Also, multiple reflections between co-originations could make knowings/Gnana and anti-knowings/Vingnana.!

$$\frac{(+0-0)^6 = (+1-(-1))^3 \times (+0.0-0.0)^3}{\text{Knowing-quality \& aimed-action must be a necessity for an interaction because two unknown actions can't interact.}} \quad | \quad \frac{(-0+0)^6 = (-1-(+1))^3 \times (-0.0 + 0.0)^3}{\text{Knowing-quality \& aimed-action must be a necessity for an interaction because two unknown actions can't interact.}}$$

Knowing-quality & aimed-action must be a necessity for an interaction because two unknown actions can't interact.

I apply this formula $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ into this $(+0.0-0.0)^3$ to get the subsequent simple outputs first (the first couple interaction (E.g: $(1 \times 1) \times 1$) as a separation of the symmetry) with knowings/qualities & anti-knowings/actions: $(+0.0-0.0)^3 = (+1)-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0)$ OR $(+1)-(-1)) \times (0.00 - 0.00) \times (+0.00-0.00)$, and etc.

$$(+1-(-1))^3 = ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3) \text{ --- The four great Bhūta/actions originate with another derived set of them - Abhidhamma.}$$

A point with a minimum of 6 directions like this $(+0-0)^6$ could depend on 'gapless joints' (Anantarika Prathya). There are a lot of things to explain about that output yet. We can get a fundamental and stable output from this first $(+1-(-1))^3$ result as simple eight results. Seemingly they are like the eight absolute/elementary forms. Buddhism also mentioned eight simple elements called Pure Eight ('Suddhāṭṭhaka' in Pali). There are four fundamental units of forms/ghosts called 'Four Mahā Bhūta' and four more forms/bhūta called Gati/characters. Bhūta is another name for "ghosts" because of their elusive nature. *(5)"). I tried to make the calculations easier for the readers to understand the basic pattern and mathematical rules. I tried to simplify the calculations using extra steps, symbols, shapes, etc.

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2. Mathematical Science And Buddhism - Part 1

There are dimensions in the universe that follow mathematical rules and steps. The steps in this calculation represent the highest possible dimensional interactions based on the natural laws of dimensions (directional moments) and the most possible symmetries. And it is NOT based on a 4 or 5-dimensional (4D or 5D) universe that already exists as spacetime, matter, forces, etc. A result of the calculation generally showed the existence of 4 main dimensions and 1 stable sub-dimension with 1 unstable sub-dimension that tried to split a dimension or rotate as 0.5 or '1/2 Spin'. I could find sets of dimensional numbers in the calculation (like the numbers in elementary sub-waves). And I named those sets of dimensions 'Elementary Magics' (dimensional sets to explain quantum fields/sub-waves, etc.). I would like to call the first 8 combinations of dimensions 'Pure Eight Ghosts' (like the 'Suddhāṭṭhaka' explained in 'Abhidhamma Piṭaka' in the Theravada Buddhist tradition). I found a lot of details about paramount ('Paramārtha') facts in nature from Buddhism. And they are similar to the results in the calculation of dimensional interactions. So those details were surprisingly a kind of verification of the results. E.g.:

i. "The 4 Great/Fundamental units of Forms/Ghosts (Pali: 'Catu Mahā Bhūta') *(5)."

ii. "The Pure Eight ('Suddhāṭṭhaka') *(5)."

iii. "28 Material Forms/Phenomena ('Rūpa') *(6)."

iv. "52 Mental Factors ('Chetasika') *(7)"

v. "The 4 Innumerable Aeons (the 4 'Asaṃkhyeya Kalpas') in The Great Aeon ('Mahā-Kalpa') *(8)."

vi. "The lifetime of a 'Matter Area' ('Rūpa-Kalāpa') is equal to 17 Mind/Heart-mind/Beauty-measurement ('Chitta') moments/conscious-moments ('Cittakkhaṇas'), or 51 short instants ($17 \times 3 = 51$); as there are 3 short instants in a moment of mind/beauty-mind ('Chitta') *(9)"

I continued the calculation as a differential equation, and then I discovered 8 formations of dimensions first. But I didn't care about it much until I heard the word '*Suddhāṭṭhaka*' in Buddhism. The results in the calculation show some similarities to the explanations in Buddhism regarding the process in the universe. So I have mentioned those similarities between the calculation and explanations.

The universe was probably a THING even if it was infinitely nothing (a zero infinity) in the first relatively infinite moment. A thing must be in six directions: up, down, left, right, forward, and back. And, it would continually go to zeros and infinities and come from there like filling the gaps and making things and new dimensions as moments of direction. We can use the properties at the start of a void-based universe to calculate the process in that universe.

This new theory is about the beginning of the dimensions and the universe. The second moment of existence in the first universe was probably a result of separations of infinities. Those dimensional infinities continue in all directions and try to be symmetric between dimensions. As required, I applied 6 directions to remove that infinite nothingness in the first universe. It made 12 dimensions of directional/vector moments (E.g., +6-6 and/or -6+6). I used directions and the virtual gaps in the infinite nothingness to start the calculation to figure out the dimensional symmetry.

E.g.:

The virtual gap in a linear zero ($0^\infty = +0$ or/and -0) direction (E.g.: between left and right) = $(+0-0)$ AND/OR $(-0+0)$

The virtual gaps in the 6 dimensional universal zero (0^∞) that had linear 6 directions = $(+0-0)^6$ AND/OR $(-0+0)^6$

The Dirac equation showed the existence of antimatter in 1928. Also, it showed a matter-antimatter symmetry in the laws of nature. According to theories like that and scientific discoveries about symmetries in nature, we can generally say that there are two opposite symmetries in the universe called Matter and Antimatter. And they could emerge from two opposite symmetries like this:

Initial Matter AND/OR Antimatter: $\{(+0-0)^6$ AND/OR $(-0+0)^6\} \times n$ ---- 'n' is an initial or derived number. $n \geq 1$

= $(+1-(-1))^3$ -- They $((+1-(-1)) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+1-(-1)))$ could cause the 1st compression of mass as a unit/nucleus.

$\times (+0.0-0.0)^3$ -- They $((+0.0-0.0) \times (+0.0-0.0) \times (+0.0-0.0))$ could cause the formation of Charge, Spin, Mass, etc.

AND/OR (Anti)

{

$(-1-(+1))^3$

$\times (-0.0+0.0)^3$

} --- But the $(-0+0)^6$ could continue to many $(-0.0+0.0)^6$ points. (E.g., $n \times (+0.0-0.0)^6$ and $6+x = n$)

If $n=1$ in the 1st $n \times (-0+0)^6$, 2nd $n \geq 6+(4 \times 3)+8$ in $n \times (+0.0-0.0)^6$ as n removes infinities between 2, 3 dimensions.

The next 2 simple steps (the interactions of binary $0(+1-(-1))0$ gaps of the 0.0 points as possible densities of them):

$(+0-0)^6 =$ -- If the initial matter zones influenced new matter zones around it, they could interact with each other.

Before I continue the calculations, I like to compare a few scientific discoveries with a few details in Buddhism.

3. The Pure Eight & Five Orders In Nature And Similar Scientific Discoveries

According to Abhidhamma teachings in Buddhism, there are 8 fundamental elementary ghosts (invisible elements) called Pure Eight (Pali: Suddhāṭṭhaka/ Sinhala: Shuddāshtaka), including 4 great fundamental ‘invisible elements’ (ghosts) and 4 elements with character/‘Gati’ of them. Just like that, we can see 8 elementary sub-waves as two groups of sub-waves in the ‘Standard Model of Elementary Sub-waves’ (UP Quark, Down Quark, Electron, Electron Neutrino, and Gluon, Photon, Z Boson, W Boson) including the 4 force-carrying sub-waves in the atoms. Probably, those 8 elementary sub-waves could emerge from those Pure Eight elements as two different groups of elementary sub-waves.!

According to Buddhism, there are five orders or processes (like laws/norms in nature, or Pali: Niyama) which operate in the physical and mental realms.

- 1.) **Utu** Niyama (order of season/time and non-living matter.)
- 2.) **Bija** Niyama (order of germs and seeds.)
- 3.) **Karma** Niyama (order of act and result.)
- 4.) **Dhamma** Niyama (order of the norm.)
- 5.) **Chitta** Niyama (order of mind or psychic law.)

It is nurture, genes, Karma, Dhamma & Chitta that shape our future. Thus, according to Buddhism, Karma (action) gives many different results based on various reasons.

4. Simplifying Interactions Of Sub-Dimensions To Continue The Calculation - Part 1

I used a few symbols as a type of mathematical symbols for quick identification:

(i.) **Up / Down**

$$(+0.0-0.0) / (-0.0+0.0) = \mathbf{1_{-}/(1/1)} \text{ OR } \mathbf{1_{-}}$$

(ii.) **Down / Up** {When six dimensions entangle from point to point while making the 0 to 0.00000 range, they can interact only within that range until the universe continues to the next point (0.000000), increasing it (decimals).}

$$(+0.000000-0.000000) / (-0.000000+0.000000) = \mathbf{1_{-}.....x(7/7)} \text{ OR } \mathbf{1_{-}.....}$$
 but it was not in the first universe.

$$\mathbf{1_{-}.....x(3/3)} \times \mathbf{1_{-}/(1/1)} = \mathbf{1_{-}.....x(5/5)} \times \mathbf{1_{-}/(0/0)/2} \quad | \text{ dimensional potential} = 2$$

AND

$$\mathbf{1_{-}...../(3/3)} \times \mathbf{1_{-}x(1/1)} = \mathbf{1_{-}/(0/0)/4} \times \mathbf{1_{-}.....x(5/5)} \quad | \text{ dimensional potential} = 4$$

OR

$$1_{\dots} = 1_{\dots} / (..x(1/1)), \text{ AND } 1_{\dots} = 1_{\dots} / (../(1/1))$$

$$1_{\dots}x(3/3) x .. = 1_{\dots}x..x(5/5) / 2 = 1_{\dots}x(5/5) / 2$$

$$1_{\dots}x(5/5) x .. = 1_{\dots}x..x(7/7) / 2 = 1_{\dots}x(7/7) / 2 \text{ is above the limit of 6 decimals gap of the formation.}$$

For that reason, that 2 would not exist there as a **dimensional potential**, $1_{\dots}x(7/7) / 2 = 1_{\dots}x(5/5) x ..$

$$(iii.) (+0.00-0.00) x (+0.00-0.00) = 0.00^2 - (1_{\dots} x 1_{\dots}) x 0.00 x 0.00 + 0.00^2$$

$$(iv.) (0.00000 + 0.00000) = 2_{\dots} x 0.00000 = 1_{\dots} x 1_{\dots} x 0.00000 \text{ \{“.....” = against 6 zeros\}}$$

$$(v.) 1_{\dots} / 1_{\dots}x(5/5) = \text{Neutral}(\dots) / \text{NEUTRAL}(\dots) \text{ OR Null}$$

5. Finding The Fundamental Process In The Mind With Science & Buddhism

According to Abhidhamma, the mind continues (itself is) a paramount moment called the Chitta/mind moment (Cittakkhaṇa). It has three moments called arising, existing, and dissolving moments. Chitta continues processing sensations between 17 moments called Citta Vīthi/series. A Matter Zone (Rūpa-Kalāpa) has 17 Chitta moments too.

Assume there are small matter zones with a small period in the smallest volume called Planck scale and Planck time. Likely, time can continue from moment to moment on energy wave moments in it, just like the continuation of 17 Chitta moments in Rūpa-Kalāpa (Matter Zones). And suppose there are 2 more existing (Thiti) moments in 2 more smallest Matter Zones that exist (Ṭhiti) during the arising (Uppāda) moment and dissolving (Bhanga) moment. While this is the case, those 3 smallest Matter Zones can behave like 3 separate dimensions of existence. In case there are 2 invisible (supersymmetric) moments like that. Arguably, we can guess the existence of Dark Matter as 2 types of Matter that exist during the arising moment and dissolving moment of our matter and/or mind. According to Buddhism, the mind is a virtual (reflection-in-between, imaginary/anti-all) phenomenon that can manifest in virtual realities. Accordingly, it is relatively invisible between realms (levels of existence). “There are clear separations between different types of realms/worlds and sub-realms in Buddhism (31 Loka/worlds). The first 5 worlds are Hell, Animal, Hungry Ghost, Asura, and the Human world. But there is no big difference between humans and animals. So if we say that humans and animals live in only 1 world, there are 4. But if some humans live in the animal world and there is another human world below the heavenly worlds, then there are 5 worlds below the 6 Deva worlds. Above, there are 10 Brahma worlds with Brahma beings who can enjoy bliss. There are 6 more Brahma worlds from the ‘Asaññasatta’ (Satta/beings with no cognitions) world to 4 ‘Immaterial worlds’ (‘Arūpa-Loka’). *(10)” Those groups of worlds (1+4+6+10+6+4) show a balance (4, 6, 10 & 10, 6, 4) like a dimensional balance. Seemingly there are worlds as groups ((10, 10, 10) or (4, 6, 10, 10) or (1, 4, 6, 10, 6, 4)) and subgroups ((1, 4, 6) & (6, 4)) too. But as humans, normally, we can’t see the Deva and Brahma worlds. Perhaps some worlds are visible to other worlds. That visibility could depend on natural reasons. E.g., Suppose most living beings always have/use only 1 moment (Ṭhiti moment) of consciousness in the 3 moments in Chitta/mind moment. In that case, some Matter/Rūpa Zones/Kalāpa would emerge before or later, without aligning with our Chitta moment. And then, those beings wouldn’t see Uppāda (arising) and Bhanga (dissolving) moments consciously, when other Matter Zones appear as a result of the Ṭhiti

(existing) moment in them. As if using an energy moment that starts before or after the start of the living moment of others. However, that level of visibility can change depending on the power of the mind/Chitta. Some great and wise people said they could see invisible beings (E.g., Ram Bahadur Bomjon). So perhaps, some people may have the ability to change the wave pattern in their minds (mind/wave moments) to see the generally invisible moments.!

$(\text{cat, obs}) = (\text{cat} , \text{obs} + \text{cat} , \text{obs})$

The 10 or 11 Sensuous Worlds (kama-loka)

Realms added by Suresh (the many worlds/realms created by the wave)

Hot/Cold Hell realm	Animal realm & Humans	Preta realm	Asura realm	Human realm	6 Heavenly/Deva realms	10 Blissful Brahma realms	10 higher Brahma realms
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The wave function splits into branches representing different measurement outcomes.

Distinct branches will never affect each other in any way.

It's as if they have become part of separate worlds.

Thus, Everettian quantum mechanics is the "Many-Worlds Interpretation."

Credit (video): "Mysteries of Modern Physics by Sean Carroll"

The energy of the wave function of the universe is perfectly conserved in the Many-Worlds interpretation of quantum mechanics. It uses decoherence/environment to explain the measurements and the emergence of a world.

According to Abhidhamma, the Chitta is a fundamental phenomenon (a Paramartha) in the universe. It is a very primitive cyclic process. Chitta is like a unique process in fundamental waves/fields (like a moment of changing flavor/formation or attraction). It would make a process like this: 1. attract dimensions (to be stable), 2. make/absorb dimensions (becoming stable/balanced), 3. select dimensions to react (becoming unstable/unbalanced again). A detectable or undetectable unique quantum process in a few elementary sub-waves could make their causes/effects (creative environment) continue as a process that could probably become a cyclic process similar to the process in Chitta. E.g., quantum entanglement, superposition, tunneling, antimatter reactions, unstable dimensions, etc. According to Buddhism, looking at the process in the Chitta moment to explain it in detail was the hardest thing the Buddha did after the Buddhahood. The Chitta moment continues on dependent origination. And it is a natural process and not a living being. Also, it is the place the mind observes things and dies instantly. But causes continue to live for a moment again. We see something with the rapid continuation of the observations in mind (maybe we observe dimensions in quantum fields). At a glance, the Chitta moment possibly can move through Matter Zones because of the short life in a Chitta moment. Perhaps the existence of 17 Chitta moments in Matter Zones helps to continue the living moment in Chitta, helping to survive after death. Abhidhamma explains a process in Chitta moments that always arises with some Mental Factors/'Chaithasika' (in 52 Chaithasika/Cetasika) becoming a Chitta Plane/'Bhūmi' (in 89 Chitta Bhūmi) of existence. It would seem that 'existence' is an emergence from the quantum fields. According to quantum mechanics, experimentally detecting ripples in quantum fields usually show the existence of those quantum fields. Assume our brains emit many visible or invisible quantum fields (electromagnetic fields) when we think. We can try to use scientific technology or an extraordinary power of the mind to detect those

quantum fields (E.g., “mind reader/influencer: Lior Suchard *(11)”).

6. Mathematical Probabilities Between Dimensions Of Conditioned Zeros - Part 1

The dimensional structures can interact during and/or after the formations. The dimensional superposition of this 0.00000 point probably becomes $(+0.00000)^6$ interrelatedly. And/Or, it becomes this $(+0.00001+0.000000 -+0.000000-+0.00001)^3$. This 0.00000 point in the calculation is likely connected to a new start. But it could share dimensions with 0 to 0.00000 range and above as 4 possible arrangements and 4 probabilities for each arrangement:
 1.) $(+0.000000+0.00001 +0.000000+0.00001)^3$. 2.) $(-+0.000000-+0.00001 +0.00001+0.000000)^3$.
 3.) $(+0.00001-+0.000000 +0.000000-+0.00001)^3$. 4.) $(-+0.00001+0.000000 +0.00001-+0.000000)^3$.

Dimensions and virtual gaps of formations of this $(+0.00001 -+0.00001)$ higher and this $(+0.000000 -+0.000000)$ lower instants could probably make around 64 possible ways of formations of the plus (+) and minus (-) possibilities while continuing to the next moments of the ‘non/no/null directional’ (0.000000) point. Potentially, that point could be a gap within its range. Directional infinities convert the 6 directions into moments of nothingness in the universe. Possibly, it continued towards the outside and inside point (+6-6) like moments becoming 12 dimensions. It could arise/originate like a dimensional symmetry making those virtual gaps at the ‘non/no/null directional’ (0.000000) point. The positions and arrangements of the plus (+) and minus (-) possibilities would make 64 probabilistic formations. It is like a cyclic process in the virtual gaps of dimensions. This is a simple representation of them:
(1. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 2. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-), 3. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 4. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 5. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 6. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-), 7. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+) & (+)(-+), 8. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+) & (-+)(+-), 9. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-), 10. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-), 11. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 12. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 13. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 14. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(-+), 15. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(-+) & (+)(-+), 16. (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+) & (+)(+-) & (-+)(+-) & (+)(-+) & (-+)(+-) x 4 (“the 4 formations of this: (+-)(-+) & (+-)(-+)”) = 64 probabilistic formations

Those 64 possibilities were based on only 1 arrangement of these $(+0.00001 +0.000000 -+0.000000 -+0.00001)^3$ symmetric instants. But with the other 3 arrangements of those instants, there would be 4 different groups of 64 possibilities. The total duration of those 256 possibilities is the duration of that cyclic process. E.g., “According to Buddhism, a great cyclic process in the cosmos make 256 destructions as 64 destructions in 64 sub-periods (between Great Aeons or Intermediate eons /Antahkalpa (20 human growths)) and 3 more periods with 64 destructions (64×4), during the contraction (Sanvattai) and expansion (Vivattai) of the universe as a cyclic process. *(12)*(8)”.

The theory of Cosmic Inflation doesn’t explain the origin of energy. It is a hypothetical theory that ignores the speed of light in a high-density medium. It is like pseudoscience. Buddhism mentioned the expansion and contraction of the universe. As said, a rain of high-energy beams called Sampatthi (energy/Shakthi) Mahamegha filled space during Vivatta Kalpa. Galaxies formed during Vivattai Kalpa. The universe contracts and energy rains destroy planets during Sanvatta Kalpa. It remains contracted (fills) during Sanvattai Kalpa. Mahā-Kalpa ends with Vivatta Kalpa. Vivatta Kalpa is likely an energy crossover.

There are many probabilities of formations on the directly unrelated 3 standard dimensions. Probabilities increase on the number of standard dimensions. And prone to lead a process like cyclic explosions (destructions or probabilistic rotations). They probably make a continuation pattern of those destructions like a continuation of a ratio. E.g., “According to Buddhism, there is a ratio of 64 destructions in the universe: 56:7:1 as $((7+1) \times 7):7:1$ that brings Cosmic Heat, Water (contraction or an energy), and Air (moves apart) $((\text{Heat} \times 7 + \text{Water} \times 1) \times 7) + \text{Heat} \times 7 + \text{Air} \times 1$). Those destructions happen between Great Aeons or during a Great Aeon as mentioned in some texts. *(12)”

The beginnings, according to Buddhism:

*"There comes a time, Vasettha, when, after a long period, this world contracts. At a time of contraction, beings are mostly born in the Abhassara Brahma world. The beings were made of mind, fed on bliss and joy, self-luminous, traveled across the air, and were glorious, and they stayed like that for a very long time. But sooner or later, after a very long period, this world begins to expand again. At a time of expansion, the beings from the Abhassara Brahma world passed away and are mostly reborn in this world. Here they dwell, mind-made, feeding on delight, self-luminous, moving through the air, glorious, and they stay like that for a very long time. At that time, it was pitched darkness all over with no sun or moon, no day or night. -The Lord Buddha. *(13)"*

“There is an explanation in Buddha’s teachings about a cyclic process in the universe. According to that explanation, the great universe undergoes 64 or 256 destructions completing a cyclic process (after 64 or 256 destructions) during or between Mahā-Kalpas. And according to another explanation, at a time, the world (Earth) explodes too (perhaps on a force from outside). And billions of world systems (many Sakwala regions in the megaverse) will be destroyed simultaneously (almost at once). The 64th destruction would always be huge. After many destructions, there would not be many habitable worlds. *(12)” The beings (including most hell-beings) would survive in the Ābhassara Brahma world (a higher realm) as the density of matter in that world is low as mentioned in texts. But a few living beings in hell won't be able to experience good results till their merits arise as if they wanted it to happen like that. E.g., “Those who didn't do enough good actions/Karma and had all the very wrong views (the 10 Niyatha Mithya Drishti (Micchā Diṭṭhi)) firmly (definitively). Including those who rejected the process of the Karma/Vipaka (good and bad actions and results), and rejected the existence of an afterlife, and rejected the existence of heavenly beings, and rejected the existence of wise people.” Consequently, they would be moved to a hell of another Sakwala (E.g., to a distant galaxy/universe) before the start of the next Mahā-Kalpa. As mentioned in texts, the cyclic destructions in the universe don't significantly impact some Brahma realms. The impacts are different depending on the density and nature of materials in the planes of those realms. Buddhism helps to make a theory to explain almost everything.!

We can experience or technically observe Electrons, Up Quarks, Down Quarks, Photons, Gluons, Quantum Fields, Mathematics, Dark Matter, Dark Energy, Momentum, etc. Fundamental elementary sub-waves/fields and their interactions generally show us the process in the universe and life. Discovering the origin of elementary sub-waves is the most important thing. We finally need to explain the existence of almost everything we see and experience.

“Likely, the universe is a process of symmetric mathematical probabilities of dimensions. According to experiments and theories in particle physics, there are quantum superpositions in particles/fields. *(14)” If the 6 main directions made dimensions, then a non-dimensional zero (zero infinity: 0^∞) could be equal to dimensional zeros $((+0)^6)$ while separating from the infinity. And that could make a density in dimensional zeros like a way to reach the state of infinity again. That mathematical requirement could always be based on the 6 main directions to be symmetric.

If the earliest nature of the universe could make mathematical probabilities like a continuation (momentums) of zero from 0 to 0.00000, etc, then that could lead to symmetric cyclic possibilities in the universe. The superpositions and

probabilities of this 0.000000 and this 0.00001 could be symmetric positions of instants like these 0.000000/0.00001 or 0.000000x0.00001 And 0.00001/0.000000 or 0.00001x0.000000. That can change as a rotation. It is a 2-dimensional cycle (these 'x' and '/' or '\' symbols show directions only.). Hence, instead of having the previously mentioned probabilities of instants, there could be super probabilities with superpositions like these:

1st formation: $(-+0.0/+ -1 -+I|+-0.0)x0^5$ and/or $(-+1/+ -0.0 -+0.0|+-I)x0^5$,
 2nd formation: $(-+0.0x+ -1 -+Ix+-0.0)x0^5$ and/or $(-+1x+-0.0 -+0.0x+-I)x0^5$,
 3rd formation: $(+ -1/-+0.0 + -0.0|-+I)x0^5$ and/or $(+ -0.0/-+1 + -I|-+0.0)x0^5$,
 4th formation: $(+ -1x+-0.0 + -0.0x+-I)x0^5$ and/or $(+ -0.0x+-1 + -Ix+-0.0)x0^5$.

The superposition of 0.000000 and 0.00001 would be very close to 0.00000, staying both of them next to it and becoming neutral probabilities. They can change cyclically as probabilistic rotations, filling the collapsed gaps like rotating dimensions. (E.g., from up to the left, up to the right, up to the back, up to the forward, etc. And moving to the next formation in the probabilistic formations of the entangled and conditioned symmetric zeros of the universal zero (0^∞) that has a dimensional shape.

7. Continuing The Calculation To Verify The Origin Of The First Universe - Part 1

$(+1-(-1))^3 = (+1)^3 - ((+1)^3x(-1) - (-1)^2x(+1)^2) + (-1)^2x(+1) - ((+1)^2x(-1) - ((+1)^2x(-1)^2 - (-1)^3x(+1)) + (-1)^3$
 $\{(+0-+0)^6\} \times n = \text{initial MATTER and/or ANTIMATTER} = \{(+0-0)^6 \text{ and } (-0+0)^6\} \times n$ --If 1st $n=1$, 2nd ≥ 26

(According to Abhidhamma, Matter Zones make Rūpa Sarira (Matter Body) that can make Rūpa Santhāna (Atoms).)
 * Likely, two dependent/related formations would appear AND disappear together, or the first formation OR second formation would appear or disappear per moment during the interactions. But both of them would coexist relatively and/or in parallel worlds. Those 2 possibilities are represented in the calculation separately using the AND/OR term. Everything is a linear moment, and the expansion increases them, making the relative time and gaps on emergence.

The first universe could continue from point 0 to 0.00000 range while interacting with originations of dimensions, at least from the point 0.00000 $(+ -1 \dots -+0.000000 + -0.000000 \setminus -+1 \dots)$. But it could be the next significant origin of dimensions even if it had to share its dimensions with the previous sub-waves. Neutrino shows the potential to reach the last (0.000000) point on $(+1/+0.0)x0^5$ superposition. They would share dimensions with previous/next sub-waves, changing neutrinos. Right-handed matter neutrinos and left-handed antimatter neutrinos are missing. The first universe could start from this initial state $(+0-+0)^6$. But the next initial state could be a little bit different. That formation could start from the last point (edge), making the next new start or continuing the previous sub-waves.

E.g.,

$(+ -0.00000 + -0.00000)^6$ OR $(-0.00000 + 0.00000)^6 = \text{the second origin of MATTER and/or ANTIMATTER}$
 $= \{(+0.00000 - 0.00000)^6 \text{ and } (-0.00000 + 0.00000)^6\}$ OR $\{(-0.00000 + 0.00000)^6 \text{ almost without initial antimatter}\}$
 The universe could evolve from 0 to 0.0 and so on, making dimensions $(1 \times n)$ to balance every 0.0 and 0.0×0^n positions, becoming superpositions. Zero (0) could continue making both 0.0 and 1 simultaneously. And it could continue making the radius in the universe from 0 to $\pm 0.00000x0^n$ continuing the expansion. Accepting that as the origin of energy is easier/logical than believing an illogical story. And creating a God from nothing is not scientific.

8. Comparing The Mathematical Structures And Dimensional Sets With The Standard Model Of Elementary Sub-waves

		three generations of matter (elementary fermions)			three generations of antimatter (elementary antifermions)			interactions / force carriers (elementary bosons)	
		I	II	III	I	II	III		
mass		$\approx 2.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 1.28 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 173.1 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 2.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 1.28 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 173.1 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	0	$\approx 124.97 \text{ GeV}/c^2$
charge		$\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$-\frac{2}{3}$	0	0
spin		$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	0
		u up	c charm	t top	\bar{u} antiup	\bar{c} anticharm	\bar{t} antitop	g gluon	H higgs
	QUARKS	d down	s strange	b bottom	\bar{d} antidown	\bar{s} antistrange	\bar{b} antibottom	γ photon	
		$\approx 4.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 96 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 4.18 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 4.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 96 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 4.18 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	0	
		$-\frac{1}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	
		$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	
		e electron	μ muon	τ tau	e^+ positron	$\bar{\mu}$ antimuon	$\bar{\tau}$ antitau	Z Z ⁰ boson	
	LEPTONS	$\approx 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 105.66 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 1.7768 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 105.66 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 1.7768 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 91.19 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	
		-1	-1	-1	1	1	1	0	
		$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	
		ν_e electron neutrino	ν_μ muon neutrino	ν_τ tau neutrino	$\bar{\nu}_e$ electron antineutrino	$\bar{\nu}_\mu$ muon antineutrino	$\bar{\nu}_\tau$ tau antineutrino	W^+ W ⁺ boson	W^- W ⁻ boson
		$< 2.2 \text{ eV}/c^2$	$< 0.17 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$< 18.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$< 2.2 \text{ eV}/c^2$	$< 0.17 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$< 18.2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$	$\approx 80.39 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	$\approx 80.39 \text{ GeV}/c^2$
		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1
		$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	1

According to the mathematical structures, elementary forms/sub-waves and forces are generally 1D, 2D, and 3D (standard 3 dimensions: up-down, left-right, forward-back) dimensional sets. So we can simplify the standard model of elementary sub-waves by removing the 2-dimensional (2D) and 3-dimensional (3D) elementary sub-waves (E.g., 2-dimensional Charm Quark, 3-dimensional Top Quark, etc.). The right-handed, left-handed, and antimatter sub-waves would be mentioned separately. But those elementary forms/sub-waves would appear in the dimensional structures as plus and minus charges or as a potential emergence due to interactions. Right-handed: the direction of spin is the same as the direction of motion. Left-handed: the directions of spin and motion are opposite.

As an assumption, likely some elementary sub-waves get mass depending on dimensional interactions of the Charge and/or Spin. E.g., Up Quark has a $\frac{2}{3}$ Spin. Therefore $\frac{2}{3} - \frac{3}{3}$ is equal to $-\frac{1}{3}$. If so, only 1 dimension gets mass. Down Quark has a $-\frac{1}{3}$ Spin like $\frac{3}{3} - \frac{1}{3}$ equals $\frac{2}{3}$. Likely, it has 2 dimensions to get mass. The Down quark is nearly 2 times more massive than the Up Quark. But electrons (minimum $-\frac{3}{3}$ or -1) and neutrinos (maximum $\frac{0}{3}$ or 0) don't have an extra or minor charge. Electrons would get mass using the Spin dimensions ($\frac{1}{2}$). Neutrinos are asymmetric (E.g., only left-handed, Neutrino Oscillation). And they don't interact with the Higgs field to get mass.

The fabric of space cannot bend without quantum impacts as space itself is a lot of actions and sub-waves. Even if spacetime geometry shows geometric gravity, quantum gravity can emerge on interactions of sub-waves that depend on entropy. Hence, the early stages of our universe in the standard model of cosmology shouldn't be based entirely on geometric gravity. And using General Relativity to say that our universe started from a tiny scale when the time was around Planck time is logically wrong. Presumably, some beliefs have made the scientific community biased.

The Most Possible Structure: Area 2 from 2 in Zone 1

(1.4			-(1.5				
(1.4.1	- (1.4.2		+ (1.4.3				
$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <th style="text-align: center;">(1.4.2.1</th> <th style="text-align: center;">- (1.4.2.2</th> </tr> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> $\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$ </td> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> $\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$ </td> </tr> </table>		(1.4.2.1	- (1.4.2.2	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$
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$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$						
+0.5+3	+0.5+4	-0.5+2	+0.5+1	-0.5+1	+0.5+1		
+0.5+3	-0.5+4	+0.5+2	+0.5+1	-0.5+1	+0.5+1		
+0.5+3	-0.5+2	-0.5+0	+0.5+1	-0.5+1	+0.5+1		
-1+4	-1+3	-1+1	-1 OR +0.5/-1+0.5	-1 OR +0.5/-1+0.5	-1 OR +0.5/-1+0.5		

1.5.1			1.5.2
(1.5.1.1	- (1.5.1.2	- (1.5.1.3	(1.5.2
$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} & (+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 2/3 \\ & - ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3) \\ & + ((+0.5 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 2/3) / (\dots) \\ & - ((-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1)) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1/3 / (\dots) \\ & - (-1/2) \times 2 \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 0.00000/3 \end{aligned}$
+0.5+3	-0.5+2	-0.5+0	+0.5-1
+0.5+1	-0.5+0	-0.5-2	-0.5-3
-0.5+1	-0.5+0	-0.5-2	-0.5-3
-1+2	-1+1	-1-1	-1-2
-1+2	-1+1	-1-1	-1-2

As an example, an electron looks like this:

$$+0.5 \dots \times (+1) \times ((+1) \times (+1) \times (+1)) \times (-1) \times 1 \times 2/3$$

$$- (+0.5 \dots \times (+1) \times ((+1) \times (+1) \times (+1)) \times (-1) \times 1 \times ((2)/3))$$

And it is almost equal to this too:

$$+0.5 \times 6/3$$

$$- (+0.5 \times 6/3)$$

Dimensional Interactions of electrons, quarks, forces, Higgs Boson, etc.

Most likely, the 0.5 Spin and the 6 dimensions in **E**lectrons (approximately, **E**: $+0.5 \times 6/3 - (+0.5 \times 6/3)$) would make an unstable dimension (1) on the interaction of unstable Spin (0.5) or on the Spin itself. And suppose the **M** dimensional set (elementary particle, **M**: $-1 \times 5/3$) in the dimensional structure is with -1 dimension (-1 as Spin or like a force moment) and +5 dimensions that remove and fill it with -1 as a replacement of the dimension. In that case, that elementary particle can attract or receive 1 dimension from electrons on entanglements between sub-waves, making a cyclic process through dimensions in space like the Magnetic **M**onopoles. That symmetric process could keep that elementary particle (**M**) as a relatively satisfied cyclic force. Also, **P**hotons (**P**: $-1 \times 6/3$) could give dimensions to fill **M** against electrons as an interaction between them (like electromagnetism). **P** is in group 1 (but there are more types/sets, too), and **E** is in group 2 in the dimensional structure.

Protons (the 3 quarks as +1 Charge in the nucleus with Gluons) can accelerate when a particle accelerator (E.g., LHC) accelerates Protons in electromagnetic fields. And during that process, Protons can absorb electromagnetic fields increasing the Kinetic energy. The dimensional sets of electrons are filled with $-(+6)$ dimensions between 3 unstable dimensions as $-(+6)/3$ in the dimensional set, which is called the -1 Charge, or $-3/3$ Charge in electrons (negative charge) in quantum physics. It seems electrons are stable enough to stay alone, but they interact with other sub-waves on Charge and Spin. According to the calculation, the Spins of sub-waves don't seem stable (E.g.: $-0.5 \times 6/3 - 0.5 \times 4/3$ can become $-1 \times 5/3$ for a moment, and vice versa), as the Spins can change from 1 to 1/2, or 1/2 to 1. And they can interact as stable sub-waves and virtual sub-waves. The 3 quarks in Protons have two types of dimensional sets called Up Quark (**U**: $0.5 \times 5/3$ and/or $-(0.5 \times 5/3)$) and Down Quark (**D**: $0.5 \times 4/3$ and/or $-(0.5 \times 4/3)$). The 2 Up Quarks have approximately $(0.5 \times 5/3) + (0.5 \times 5/3)$ dimensions. The Down Quark has approximately $-(0.5 \times 4/3)$ dimensions that could interact, making the $+6/3$ Charge in Protons. It is the +1 Charge (as a total charge) in a Proton (positive charge) in quantum physics. The plus (+) and minus (-) sides/directions of the quarks possibly can change just like the change called color/flavor change (as mentioned in quantum mechanics) in quarks and Gluons (**G**: $-(-1+1)/3 - (-1+1)/3$) in the nucleus. Or, they represent the Spin direction of sub-waves (right-handed and left-handed sub-waves) or matter and antimatter sub-waves. They don't show only the matter sub-waves and the antimatter sub-waves as plus (+) and minus (-) results. As scientists see, there are right-handed quarks and right-handed electrons. Still, scientists couldn't find right-handed neutrinos as an anomaly (reasonably due to symmetry breaking/separating). So perhaps some interactions produce alternative particles/dimensional sets (E.g., antimatter neutrinos, left-handed neutrinos, etc.) instead of right-handed neutrinos. There are two types of neutrinos (**N**, **N**) in area 1 of the most possible dimensional structure. Most likely, including the Sterile neutrino, which is almost recognizable as a different type of neutrino (In May 2018, MiniBooNE experiment: a possible signal indicating the existence of Sterile neutrinos.). Gluons (**G**) easily change the direction of traveling on interactions. Gluons have equally canceling dimensions as if they are dimensionless. Gluons don't have a 0.5 dimension. They don't have an asymmetry between plus and minus dimensions to make a strong long-distance entanglement between many dimensions. Instead, they have only 2 main dimensions $(-1+1)$ as a minus dimension and a plus dimension that

could try to annihilate each other, making a 'force moment' (trying to cancel energy dimensions). For that reason, possibly Gluons are traveling while changing the direction of travel. It is a privilege to travel to many nearby locations again and again within a short/least period. They don't need to travel long distances to rotate the direction of travel to repeatedly reach many nearby locations. Gluons travel without taking the least distance, such as the distance that elementary sub-waves usually take to rotate the direction of traveling by a force. As if Gluon is traveling faster than light, in terms of reaching the same location again and again quickly. But as a massless particle, surely Gluon is traveling at the speed of light (c) from one location to the nearest location.

There are more than 6 typical dimensions in a dimensional set of the Higgs boson (**H**: $(+1 \times 6 \times 0.5)/3$ and/or $-(-1 \times 6 \times 0.5)/3$) becoming unstable with the extra dimensions. These $(+1 \times 6 \times 0.5)/3$ dimensions made the Higgs boson (smallest/earliest Higgs boson) highly unstable. As seemingly, two unstable extra dimensions in it produce an unusual Spin. Perhaps, It is like a scalar field that can be in any direction, making a volume and causing sub-waves to have mass. According to Abhidhamma, there is an effective (vital) material form (Rupā) called the Life Faculty (Jīvitindriya) in the group of concretely produced (Nippahna) materials. And they stay with a group of matter called abstract (Anippahna) material forms (like quantum foam) in the 28 types of material forms. Also, the Space Element called Ākāsa Dhātu is undoubtedly located in a dimensional structure. $*(6)^n$). However, there are 8 dimensions, or 8 dimensions with 3 unstable dimensions that can behave like 11 dimensions in a dimensional set, including a dimension like 0.5. But if the 0.5 dimension is a combination/joint of 2 opposite dimensions $(+1-1)$, then perhaps those 12 dimensions made the Higgs boson as if reaching the maximum of balanced dimensions in the symmetric dimensional set, including the 6 unstable dimensions. But likely, there are 11 dimensions (interactions) in the smallest Higgs Boson (in the 1st generation). However, the 8 or 9 dimensions $(1 \times 6 \times (0.5 \text{ or } 1-1))$ try to be stable within 3 unstable dimensions $(/3)$ while emerging as 6 dimensions $(1 \times 3 \times (1-1))$ or 5 dimensions $(4+0.5)$. They can make the main 3-space and 1-time dimensions with the matter/antimatter dimensional sets using the 0.5 dimensions. If the high densities of matter waves are based on vacuum space, then their mass would depend on space-densities.

Weak interaction

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^- + W^+ &\rightarrow \nu_\mu \\ d &\rightarrow u + W^- \quad \times \quad \begin{matrix} \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{Z} & \implies & \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{W} \\ -(+0.5+4)/3 & -(-1+4)/3 & -(+0.5+5)/3 & -(-1+3)/3 \end{matrix} \\ W^- &\rightarrow e^- + \bar{\nu}_e \quad \times \\ W^+ &\rightarrow e^+ + \nu_e \quad \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{Z}^{0.5} &\implies \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{N} = e^- + \bar{\nu}_e \\ -(-1+3)/3 & -(+0.5+3)/3 & -(+0.5+6)/3 & -(-1)/3 \text{ OR} \\ & & +0.5/-1 + (-0.5)/3 & \end{aligned} \quad \text{Suresh}$$

Z⁰ boson

According to the experiments about the Z bosons decay, in 10% of the Z-decays, charged lepton-antilepton pairs (Eg: 'electron'-'positron') are produced. The Z boson decays in 20% of the cases into a neutrino-antineutrino pair (Eg: 'Electron neutrino'-'Electron antineutrino'. The neutrino decay gives another 3 possibilities.). In 70% of Z decays, a quark-antiquark pair (Eg: 'down quark' - 'antidown quark') is produced. Adding up the 6 quark types (up, down, charm, strange, top, bottom) each with 3 colors results in 18 decay possibilities. This gives a total of 24 decay possibilities, but only 21 are visible.

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{Z}(-1 +4)/3 + \mathbf{Z}^{0.5} (+0.5+3)/3 \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 + \mathbf{W}(-1+3)/3 \text{ AND/OR} \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 + \{+1+1\}/3 \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 + \{(\mathbf{N}(+1-0)/3)+1\} \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 + \{(\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5-0)/3)+0.5+0.5\} \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3 +4/3) + \{(\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - \{(\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3) +0.5/3\}\} \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3) +1 -0.5/3 + (\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - \{(\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3)\} \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3) +0.5/3 + (\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - (\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3) \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3) + \mathbf{E}(+0.5+6/3) -6 + (\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - (\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3) \\ \implies &\mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3) + \mathbf{E}(+0.5+6/3) + \mathbf{E}(-0.5-6/3) +0.5/3 + (\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - (\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{Z}(-1 +4)/3 + \mathbf{Z}^{0.5} (+0.5+3)/3 \implies \mathbf{D}(+0.5+4)/3 - (\mathbf{D}(-0.5-4)/3) + \mathbf{E}(+0.5+6/3) + \mathbf{E}(-0.5-6/3) + 0.5/3 + (\mathbf{N}(+0.5+0.5)/3) - (\mathbf{N}(-0.5-0.5)/3)$$

According to the most possible dimensional interactions, that is the explanation for the transformation of the Z boson. - Suresh

9. Using The Dimensional Structures To Compare And Predict

- 9.1.) According to the dimensional structures, most likely, there is a fundamental separation between large objects and small objects (E.g., between Black Holes and planets/gas) since the mathematics of the universe could make more than 1 main dimensional structure (more than 1 model of elementary sub-waves). And with a cyclic process, those dimensional structures would continue, evolve, and shrink, as they are the only kind of dimensional structures that could exist before and after a Big Bounce.
- 9.2.) There are dimensional Spins (0.5 and 1) and unstable 3 dimensions ($/3$) in the dimensional structure. The positive, negative, and neutral charges of elementary sub-waves are based on dimensions (E.g., $4/3$, $5/3$, $6/3$) and lower charges (E.g., $1/3$, $2/3$). Both Up Quarks ($-(1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 2/3)$ and/or $(1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 2/3)$) and Down Quarks ($(1 \times 1 \times 2/3)$ and/or $-(1 \times 1 \times 2/3)$) have extra charges. The mass/energy would depend on the symmetric capacity of entanglements. Presumably, some dimensions become infinite/future (less entangled gaps reach relatively distant points) or end as a force moment/repeatedly, and don't curve/bend. Suppose a dimension is like an arrow that points in a direction. If so, the 0.5 dimension is probably like a joint of two arrows trying to take a moment in both directions (or an arrow moment that goes towards both directions!).
- 9.3.) Scientists (including Dr. Peter Higgs) could predict the existence of the 'Higgs Boson'. As we now know, it has a mass of around 125 GeV. But some scientists expected a higher mass for the Higgs boson. I tried to compare the mathematical structures with the properties of elementary sub-waves in the Standard Model (of particle physics) using ratios, patterns, etc. I compared a mathematical ratio in the dimensional groups with the standard mass of sub-waves. I could guess that there is probably ANOTHER Higgs Boson that can emerge as a 2-dimensional (2D) Higgs Boson. But it would decay quickly like the 1st Higgs Boson due to its unstable structure or Charge. Also, it would make a relatively very massive unstable structure, making it very difficult to discover experimentally. Perhaps, the energy required to make the 3rd Higgs Boson (like a solid Higgs Boson) or higher energy/pressure would make a tiny high-density structure like a tiny Black Hole. E.g., Likely, the core of a massive dying star makes a tiny Black Hole that can grow.
- 9.4.) **Hypothetically describing what happens in the double-slit experiment.**

It was difficult for theorists to explain the amazing results of the double-slit experiment theoretically. Because the double-slit experiment shows that the elementary sub-waves/fields behave like both waves and sub-waves. How can we solve that mystery? Quantum objects passed the double-slit behaving like waves making a wave pattern on the screen. Still, when the things were MEASURED NEAR THE SCREEN, they behaved as if they went back in time and returned to hit the screen behaving like particles, without making an interference pattern on the screen. As if our interaction with quantum objects changed the history of quantum objects.! Yet, if all the dimensions are time-based lines (lines of moments without a solid string and size), then the sub-wave can relatively change without a time illusively, using the detector and screen when the sub-waves travel through the double-slit to hit the screen. We can assume the time dimensions that can entangle between sub-waves and observers. So, when we observe/see or measure a time dimension (when we interact with a dimension of a quantum object), their entanglements probably change the time dimensions in both sub-waves and observers at once. So the double-slit experiment is showing us something like a magic trick. The double-slit experiment showed us that the previous state in the quantum objects changed once we measured it. But during the double-slit experiment, the observer observes sub-waves of Electrons, and when Electrons hit the screen, the screen becomes another observer.

Then, both the screen and the first observer (the detector) would detect sub-waves of Electrons on instant entanglements between those two observers. If we look at it like that, we can guess that the quantum objects look like particles when observers are not close or unentangled. And they act like waves when there is only one observer or because of their angular momentum (Will splitting the screen would unentangle it?).

Arguably, the dimensional sets and wave functions show the possibility of explaining that process. Presume electric and magnetic fields in Electrons cancel/separate when the detector observes it. Then it would travel with a need to be filled until it can find a magnetic field on the screen or vice versa. And then a field in the screen would instantly fill the gap between the Electron and detector using quantum entanglements, making the observer absorb the Electron completely. But when we don't use a detector/observer first, the screen becomes the only observer that detects its position after its angular momentum that made the wave on it. The observation is likely an interaction or interference that damages the structure of Electrons, observers, etc. We observe the output of that damage (at the detector) with the final exchange between observers (with the screen). There is a similarity between that process and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics. But according to theories in quantum mechanics (wave function), quantum uncertainty is an unpredictable nature in elementary sub-waves that happens whether we observe the quantum objects or not.

- 9.5.) According to Buddhism, there are four paramount natures in the universe called 'Paramārtha Dharma.' Those four (4) ultimate realities are known as Rupa (4 great material forms + 24 material forms, or 28 in number), Chaitasika (52), Chitta, and Nibbana (timeless state). There are 8 fundamental formations called Pure Eight, including the 4 great fundamental forms (ghosts/Bhūta). According to the dimensional calculation, visibly, there are 4 fundamental dimensional sets (elements) and 48 more dimensional sets (8×6) as 24 pairs (8×3) on the same dimensional structure in every 2 sets in Area 1 of the structure. It appears that those sets have the fundamental/initial electric and magnetic charge moments. But possibly a polarization (extremes in a wave function) could break that symmetry while emerging as matter and force sub-waves. In that sense, surprisingly, there are 28 material formations in the dimensional structures too.
- 9.6.) Assume the existence of an empty section (a separation) at the center of the dimensional structure (in the 3rd section). That section could disconnect the dimensional connection between the matter area and the opposite area. The matter area could have mass, massless force carriers, and possibly a causal potential to impact our emotions. The opposite area could have massless fields, just like more fields of fundamental emotions that don't have physical properties. There are 96 sets of dimensions as 48 pairs in the structures, depending on the first four formations. Consequently, those first and last formations could emerge as 52 formations that behave almost like massless/subjective fields. Perhaps those dimensional sets are like 52 fields of fundamental emotions like the 52 'Cetasika' which are immaterial 'mental factors' (Arūpa/Nāma) that interact with the mind (Citta). More details are mentioned in Abhidhamma Piṭaka (the 'Basket of Higher Doctrine' (Higher Dhamma) of Theravada Buddhism). So It is difficult to say that we are just material phenomena. If observations are like instant cancellations of opposite dimensions that make force moments, then they can make a non-existence or a balance between dimensions (+1-1=0). Or, they can make a timeless entanglement between them (as fixed +1-1=0). Perhaps, that (0) can cause the observation (in mind), and change/bend or interact with other actions. Maybe, that happens on a partial force in waves.
- 9.7.) [Analyzing the strange behavior of neutrinos to explain gravity, force, etc.](#)

The strange behavior of neutrinos (**N**) is most likely a result of a dimensional interaction in them (**N**: $-(-1)/3$ OR $(+0.5/-1)+(-0.5)/3$ as filling gaps to be symmetric'). Strangely, the dimensional set in the structure, which most reasonably represents an 'electron neutrino,' has only 1 dimension within the 3 unstable dimensions ($/3$) as $1/3$. Yet, this $1/3$ dimensional set made the Spin (0.5) and Charge (0) on a transformation or interactions of dimensions. Arguably, It is like a type of symmetry breaking as $(0.5+0.5)/3$. It is located between the range of dimensional sets that represent force-carrying sub-waves. So the 3 dimensions ($/3$) or anything else tried to divide that 1 dimension. Or, if there is a process that could change that single ($1/3$) dimension, then it could become/borrow these $0.5+0.5$ broken/shared dimensions. In contrast, the 0.5 dimensions ($1/2$) could try to be symmetric alike $0.5+0.5$ or $0.5+1-0.5$ or $(+0.5-0.5)/-1$ shared sets of dimensions on related interactions. It would use dimensions from an external source to be symmetric, without becoming asymmetric dimensions such as 0.3 , $0.3+$ complex/hypothetical dimensions.

However, a neutrino could have strange behaviors even with only 1 dimension because of its rotation. It behaves just like a divided (0.5) dimension. Also, neutrinos could have a repulsive Spin or a repulsive Mass and things like that. Because they can change dimensions easily between $1/3$ to $0.0/3$ as a 0.5 Spin. There are 3 directions in a qubit, just like the 3 unstable ($/3$) dimensions. It requires 3 numbers to describe a qubit. And then 15 numbers ($(3 \times 3) + (2 \times 3)$ possibilities) for the next qubit. They are related to the eV (electron Volt) energy. Likely, the dimensions in 'electron neutrinos' don't help them enough to make a big mass. But we can try to find the initial mass of an electron neutrino using the nature of qubits. E.g., "qubits between $0.0/15$ to $1/15$ would show a mass between 0.00 to 0.066 eV." If the Spin of a neutrino is equal to 0.5 or $1/2$, its dimension is unstable or connected to an unstable dimension. Or, it $-(-1)/3$ can freely rotate in any direction. Thus, the dimensions in neutrinos could get the 0.5 Spin on a joint of it (1) as symmetry making with the unstable dimensions in Higgs Bosons, etc. As we know, neutrinos are almost asymmetric/irregular. When a neutrino travels, it makes 3 types of neutrinos (1D,2D,3D neutrinos: Electron N, Muon N, Tau N). If it Spins like a 0.5 dimension instead of $-(-1)$, then it or another dimension needs to be stable, making dimensions like $1-0.5$ (as if making a muon neutrino on a mathematical symmetry). And after that, again, it becomes unstable while it obtains another unstable (-0.5) dimension. Thereupon, it needs to be stable again, making dimensions like $-1+0.5$ (as if making a tau neutrino). But the -1 dimension would be canceled on the previous $+1$ dimension making a force moment while changing the flavor/type of the neutrino again.

Seemingly, General Relativity ignores the existence of Gravitons and the speed/flow of them/gravity when objects move fast. But likely, neutrinos attract dimensions (1 or 0.5) and change themselves and cancel or try to cancel some dimensions attracting more dimensions, making a small force like that. Suppose a

dimensional asymmetry prevents a complete annihilation and leaves a few dimensions that can behave like an ‘emerging force’ (counter-attraction). In that case, it can act like a tiny Dark Energy that would slightly move galaxies. Indeed, some reasons could increase dimensions in space, and in contrast, some reasons cancel or connect them. They absorb/cancel as an observation of dimensions that could remove or balance them, making a dimensionless void or a mass death between the 1, 2, or 3 standard dimensions, becoming the cause of a force, like making the gravitational force, electromagnetic force, and strong force.

If some sub-waves didn’t have a 0.5 (or 1/rotation) unstable dimension, then likely those 1-dimensional (1D), 2-dimensional (2D), and 3-dimensional (3D) sub-waves in the 3 standard dimensions could be stable (without changing the dimensional (D) generation (flavor)). But if a particle had a 0.5 Spin, it could be unstable while trying to use more than 1 dimension (1D) to make a move (moment). Likewise, if the 0.5 Spin makes dimensions unstable, sub-waves with the 1 Spin could be stable in 3 dimensions (3D). So it sounds like there are 3 layers (3D) in some force-carrying sub-waves, including 2 hidden layers as similar layers of quantum fields. But potentially, they can decay into 2 and 1-dimensional forces on interactions or influences of the other/unstable sub-waves. The first flavor in the Standard Model (Up Quark, Down Quark, Electron, Electron Neutrino) is generally/mainly based on only 1 standard dimension (1D). Generally, there is 1 more dimensional (1D) set in the second flavor (1D+1D). And same as that, there are 2 more dimensional sets in the third flavor (1D+2D). The masses and forces (force moments) could have an interrelated balance, becoming almost balanced and fixed ratios in the structures. And that mathematical balance could relatively look like fine-tuning in some dimensional structures, atoms, galaxy formation, etc.

9.8.) There are ways to confirm whether neutrinos make the gravitational force (gravity) or not.
 E.g. (i.) Around 2 hours before the supernova 1987a star explosion (when that dying star turned into a Black Hole), the dying star started to release energy as neutrinos. It continued releasing for around 2 hours before releasing light. But that light was only about 1% of the total energy that the star released. Approximately 99% of energy was released as neutrinos before making a Black Hole. That showed those neutrinos could come out from there during that very high gravitational pressure. As if the higher amount of neutrinos were the source of that extreme gravity that could give the star enough pressure to be a small Black Hole (or a neutron star) to be stable. Like coming out while eating from it until the formation of that stable object. It could stop releasing extra neutrinos allowing it to release light as a supernova explosion (“NASA X-ray Telescopes Find Black Hole May Be a Neutrino Factory” - Nasa (13-11-2014, R: 14-169)).

E.g. (ii.) There are no gigantic planets around the sun with a big hot core inside it (E.g., the sun is 109 times wider than Earth). We can imagine gigantic planets near the sun with graviton sub-waves or partial forces in neutrinos could make gravity. In that case, they can interact (E.g., bend the path, change the flavor) while passing the hot core in those planets (neutrinos change flavor/mass inside stars/planets). It can increase the gravitational force between the planets and the sun (E.g., Jupiter is getting closer to the sun each day.). As a result, those planets could move toward the sun sooner than the other planets. On the other hand, it points out that it could be the main reason why most small planets near the sun are fine-tuned with gravity without moving towards the sun faster. Usually, planets get moons on co-formation, capture, collision, etc. Assume a planet had a very low heat in the core (a dead core) that didn’t produce a lot of neutrinos to make a strong gravity. In that case, we wouldn’t see it keeping a relatively large moon in a stable orbit. Some reasons cause planets/moons to orbit for a long time, such as the right distance between them unless the heat in the core doesn't impact. Relatively to the mass ratio between the moon and Earth, Mars has very small moons. The relatively very cool core of Mars required its moons to be like that, or the moons it got stayed with it

with the mass they have. Yet, if some neutrinos are invisible, then it is difficult to calculate their quantum impact. Some scientists say that quantum mechanics requires an elementary particle (a graviton) to produce a quantum gravitational force. Likely, quantum gravity is related to one or more elementary sub-waves produced by the interactions like beta decay and nuclear reactions, without depending directly on the inertial mass. If the gravitational mass is not equal to inertial mass, then the equivalence principle is wrong. Earth: Mars: Moon = Volumes 10: 1.51: 0.2, Masses 10: 1.07: 0.123. Why did Mass drop on Volume? (on density only?) "Qualitatively, results suggest a violation of the Einstein Equivalence Principle. *(16)" Presume the gravitational interactions can indicate a low mass in an object less than the inertial mass by depending on the number of gravitons (waves/neutrinos that made gravity). They would show an incorrect low mass of that object. It is difficult to measure the inertial mass in huge material objects (E.g., inertial mass in planets, stars, interstellar gas, and gas surrounding galaxies). There is a mismatch between the ratio of the measured mass of baryonic matter (protons/neutrons) in the observable universe and the amount of baryonic matter detected shortly after the Big Bang and at later times. Baryonic matter accounts for 4.85% of the energy contents. So, the 'missing baryonic matter problem' is also likely related to a problem with the gravitational mass. If cooled gas clouds don't make enough gravity, their gravitational mass can't equal the inertial mass. Also, the speed of an object can impact gravity. E.g., If 'Planet 9' doesn't exist (is small) or leaves orbit, likely the sun's speed gradually made an impact on the orbits of Trans-Neptunian Objects.

Prof. Albert Einstein was right about the curvature of space that gravitational fields made in space, which could interact and make gravitational waves in space. Presume that curvature results from a quantum force that could increase space density, making the curvature and gravity. In that case, that gravitational wave is a space wave that originated from quantum gravity. But that curvature is not a quantum force that makes gravity. Suppose two objects with strong gravitational forces (like Neutron Stars or Black Holes) reach each other without coming directly, and they don't collide directly using gravity. In that case, those objects can accelerate each other simultaneously on their gravitational forces. And it can cause them to pass each other quickly in an unstable orbit, making it difficult to collide until they move around each other very closely.

9.9.) According to the universe's dimensional laws, every cyclic dimensional formation can interrelatedly increase and decrease the mass and force moments in most elementary sub-waves. Dimensional interactions and structures could give and get mass and force moments following a set of symmetric ratios. Just as fixed ratios between those masses and force moments derived from the universe's formation's probabilistic/cyclic type. Likely, the 3D forces (E.g., deepest force fields in gluons) can become 2D forces and 1D forces on interactions. When it happens with many unstable (0.5) 3-dimensional (3D) sub-waves becoming 2-dimensional and 1-dimensional sub-waves as a dimensional entanglement in the dimensional structure, it could also separate some 3D forces into 2D and 1D forces. And then, those 3 types of forces could make layers of forces as levels of forces. The 3-dimensional (3D) force (the 3 or more force moments) must be the strongest. It is just like the deepest level of gluon force that can keep the elementary sub-waves like Up Quarks and Down Quarks closer to each other, making Protons and Neutrons. The Charge of Quarks and the different layers of gluon forces probably could make the atomic nucleus and the electron's energy levels as they continue the mathematical balance between dimensional sets.

There are two Up Quarks with a $+5/3$ dimensional Charge and one Down Quark with a $-4/3$ dimensional Charge in a Proton. So, there are two large positive Charges ($5/3 + 5/3$) in a Proton with a requirement of two negative Charges from Electrons ($-6/3$) to balance the two Charges. But there is a Quark with a negative ($-4/3$) Charge. And it reduces that requirement while balancing the Charge ($+5/3 + 5/3 - 4/3$) with only one Electron ($-6/3$) as a process of exchanging the Charge between the Quarks in Proton becoming an unstable Charge. That Charge can move the Electron around the Proton, giving space for another Electron of another Proton with an unbalanced Charge and an Electron to balance the Charges in Protons. They can share Electrons at the same level of both Electrons. E.g., “The Proton in the hydrogen atoms is sharing electrons making the hydrogen gas.” Also, they can make the stable first energy level (the first Electron shell) of the atom with only 2 Electrons. E.g., “The two Protons in the helium atom are staying with 2 stable electrons.” Those 2 Electrons fulfill the requirement in Protons that need negative Charges around them to balance their two positive Charges, near the first layer of the 3D gluon force. When there are more than two Protons in the atomic nucleus, the Electrons can arrange against the positions of the first two Electrons in the first layer. Meanwhile, they would cause changing the positions of Electrons in the second layer, like changing the position of Charge between all the directions. The atom would adjust itself to balance the Charges in Protons with the positions of Electrons. They make fluctuations of Charges until the two Electrons in the first layer can be symmetric with the other Electrons to be stable. Likely, the layers of gluons can impact the distance between them. Possibly, atoms require a minimum of 8 Electrons to make the second energy level as 2 symmetric groups of Electrons with 4 Electrons in each group to be symmetric and stable. Similarly, when there are more Protons in the nucleus, the next layer of gluon forces could be strong enough to hold Electrons, making the third energy level. The energy levels show symmetries. E.g., “The filled third energy level in atoms has 18 Electrons like 4 symmetric groups with 4 Electrons in each group and 2 symmetric electrons above them. Likely, the asymmetric last 3 electrons in Scandium made it transitional: $2+8+8+3$. As we know about the Iron-56 (Protons: 26, Neutrons: 30) atom, it has the most binding energy per nucleon, making it the most stable nucleus. So, It is possible that when there are 26 Protons with 30 Neutrons in the atomic nucleus, the most stable combination of layers of gluons and the symmetries of electrons (like this $2+(4+4)+(4\times 4)$) could make the high binding energy. Just like there is an edge created by the best end of all the layers of gluons and electrons. Likely, the strength of force flows as if gluons have 3 stable symmetries of their layers, with the symmetries of electrons.” The most stable and unstable balances of electrons in atoms show that some properties of atoms are almost based on their symmetries of electrons. E.g., The first 2 Electrons in Oxygen $2+(2+2+2)$ overlap with the last 2 Electrons.

The last 7 Electrons in Fluorine $2+7$ are not stable. Oxygen and Fluorine are gasses. The Electrons in Sulfur are stable: $(1+1)+(4+4)+(6)$ makes a metal. The electrons in Chlorine are unstable: $2+(4+4)+7$ makes a gas.

- 9.10.) If a force can combine or collect all the dimensional structures, that would collapse space or end the universe. E.g., “Assume supermassive Black Holes can absorb all the Dark Matter and Matter. They would collapse the symmetry of space and/or matter. In that case, a force would try to annihilate or shrink some areas in space. Maybe the vacuum energy in space would evaporate too.” Or, if the expansion of the edge of the universe produces more space than matter by flattening the curvature of the expanding edge, eventually, the dimensions of space would not support the balance of symmetry in the universe. Maybe the existing space would be a medium (entanglement) to virtually bring the expansion area (gap) to starting points. Like exchanging space with the edge of the universe during the next Big Bang to instantly fill the expanded edge with the existing space! That space can start to behave like Dark Energy that would come back and move galaxies away from each other while coming to the areas of matter and galaxies! But space would go back to new spacetime areas at the expanded and bounced areas between universes and/or at the edge of the entire universe! Perhaps the edge of the entire universe makes a probabilistic rotation making destructive waves while continuing a faster-than-light expansion! But, if new directional moments there (a range) make extra space in space, making all the matter/density, they would cause Big Bangs to fill its gaps.

There are 3 possible separations of this $(+0.0-0.0)^3$ start. Even if it becomes this $(+(1)-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0)$, it could be this $(+0.0-0.0) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+(1)-(-1))$ and this $(+0.0-0.0) \times (+(1)-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000)$ as a cyclic process. Like three types of formations. According to Buddhism, “the universe undergoes 64 destructions on Air/Expand, Water/Contract, & Heat (smallest) elements with a destruction ratio 56: 7: 1. $*(12)$ ” Perhaps basic elements (E.g, interactions of **P**: **W**: **Z**: **G**) would change the fundamental structure in the universe, or some elements would flow/move or collapse, changing entangled dimensions/spacetime, or burning matter. If there is a constant as a ratio, which can remove some units (E.g., time) from constants and make a ratio with a distance to measure something (E.g., tiny polarizations). It may help to find large cosmic interactions beyond the observable universe. E.g., “Presume that there is a ‘relatively stable distance’ in some parts of the universe or the megaverse (on a cyclic process). If so, likely, a constant similar to the ‘speed of light /Planck length’ can help measure quantum impacts in large areas of the visible universe. The density of space (medium) can change the speed of light. E.g., “A low density at the edge of a spherical universe would stretch the space (causing energy to be dense again!)” But we can try to find an initial constant, which we can use to connect the ratios of the universe with the standard constants. E.g., A universal ratio in dimensional structures (fine-structure constant) and a Planck Constant.

- 9.11.) As we know, Gluons are traveling with the freedom to change their direction. There are only two main dimensions representing Gluons (**G**: $-(1+1)/3$) of the structure. Those two opposite dimensions make force moments by canceling them. Likely, mass refills it and doesn’t make a lot of entanglements. The Gluons would absorb mass from nearby elementary sub-waves (E.g., from Up Quarks and Down Quarks) again and again quickly, even if those sub-waves could travel near the speed of light. Consequently, Gluons could make a strong nucleus that eventually could make the Charged Hadrons called protons, which attract opposite Charges called electrons symmetrically forming atoms. Photons (**P**: $-(1+1+5)/3$) usually travel straightly/linearly with the influence of dimensional entanglements. They have a -1 moment that can join to be a force moment without changing the direction it travels because of the entanglements unless an external force changes the direction. Likely, the speed of light is a straight continuation of the Planck time or an energy wave (E.g., 3 or 51 smallest moments), and mass and force are moments. Assume that matter in the

universe increases repeatedly. Credibly, the moments required to complete that cyclic process can increase.

The defined duration of a second depends on an atom (cesium-133). Assume that photons travel using the smallest moments without taking many moments to travel and don't jump to travel ahead. And if there are 51 moments (17 energy wave moments) in a Planck length, then there are '51 × speed of light / Planck length' universal moments in a second. But if photons take 51 moments (E.g., Planck time/length) to travel the smallest moment, that is '51 × 51 × speed of light / Planck length' universal moments in a second. Presumably, the smallest matter zone has 51 moments. And it sounds similar to the Planck length/time. We can try to use the speed of light with a small dimensional structure to make an equation to calculate the duration of the cyclic process of this universe or periods in the process. And shape, size, direction, and rotation of the universe/megaverse, etc.! If Black Holes in the previous universe were antimatter, then the virtual sub-waves in space could come from an annihilation of asymmetry between them and matter. But, it could happen when matter emerges from the initial/Preon states gradually, or while dense material objects emerge between the matter in the previous universe.! But seemingly, the dimensions of both of them are supersymmetric and co-exist as one matter per moment. The Planck scale could be the smallest Preon scale.

- 9.12.) The Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation coming from the early/distant universe showed us large areas with only space without elementary sub-waves, even though the universe was extremely hot and dense after the Big Bang. The calculation shows/made a polarized wave function that the dimensional interactions could make, that could increase/expand, contract/decrease the results of interactions themselves like a cyclic/wave process. E.g., "Cyclic beginnings and continuations of interactions would increase and/or decrease mass/energy moments increasing and/or decreasing force moments as waves with growth on polarization." And expanding the theory in the calculation to increase results can ultimately connect the

calculation to the current universe. But suppose time didn't impact the first origin. If so, infinite directions could make a lot of interactions that would make a large number of structures within the first start of the universe. Keeping it with many sets of dimensions as a maximally dense energy packet (large mass and extremely high pressure that arises on asymmetry) in the smallest universe (inside Planck scale). But on the contrary, the time it takes to complete a cyclic process in that universe could be very small on a strong connection and high density between dimensions. In other words, a dimensional relationship could solve the asymmetry quickly, causing it to be symmetric again soon and restart again. But the next beginning would increase unrelated dimensions and time duration in that universe while connecting it back to its maximum/innumerable again. Perhaps new starts make an equal amount of new dimensions or make a little more each time. And make a cyclic process while staying with the previous dimensions as a co-existence.

Discovering the CMB Radiation helped scientists understand that EXISTING subatomic sub-waves made hydrogen atoms while cooling down the universe. But making a scientific argument/theory about the origin of the universe must be based on the total energy of subatomic sub-waves. If not, that theory should explain the origin of energy to explain the nature of singularity and the Big Bang. Scientists don't know the area of the Big Bang or the size of the entire universe. So they don't know about the total energy in the Big Bang to decide the size of the singularity. The energy packet (minimum size) that made the Big Bang could be very extensive or a cyclic process. E.g., "A probabilistic expansion with a compressing process that fills missing dimensions making cosmic waves/inflation." The energy in the first singularity could increase later on Big Bounces like waves. CMB radiation is polarized. So that's not a clue of a singularity. "Perhaps the universe was almost dark for around 370-380 thousand years or a few years as the extremely hot Hadrons/protons couldn't combine with electrons to emit photons/light till then. **(13)*" Scientists didn't discover the start of Time to explain whether there was a perfect singularity before the Big Bang without using time or not. CMB radiation showed large areas of space too. So it seems that perhaps it was not a perfect singularity. Even if quantum fluctuations could make large areas of space, It is difficult to prove that they did. Time is a change in anything. So if something changed in that singularity, then there was a time in it too. Energy is a process of change. So if there was energy in it, there was a time in it related to the energy fields in itself. Time is a related thing. Maybe the universe must continue trying to be symmetric, even if the universe fails to be symmetric again and again, making Big Bounces. According to the dimensional interactions, the first moment in the first universe started while trying to be symmetric between dimensions after separating from the infinity of zero. If the singularity was only one moment between a Big Crunch and a Big Bang, we can't say that the time didn't pass. Different types of Big Bounces could make different types of universes.

There are virtual matter and antimatter in space that interact as if they try to share something while appearing and disappearing. Certainly, that shows that the matter arose with the help of antimatter dimensions. But a minimal change in dimensions could make more matter than antimatter. Space increases in the observable universe with the interaction of Dark Energy that moves the galaxies away from each other. So perhaps there were large areas of space before the Big Bang, or more space is emerging with/on antimatter reactions. And they relatively increase space in the observable universe. Anti-dimensions give the reason for the existence of matter. And a tiny mathematical asymmetry between matter and antimatter dimensions makes matter. That possibility would depend on wave functions and/or a probabilistic process in the universe. Perhaps we have to explain the nature of the entire universe (or a kind of multiverse) as a single something, as that (1 unit) is the most natural thing that could happen in a natural universe. Only one thing (a unit of energy) could emerge as matter and antimatter dimensions from an infinitely nothing thing. It was shaping/forms that relatively made scale that couldn't be reduced. Different forms/shapes could make

a megaverse or a weak multiverse with island universes that can strongly interact with each other. E.g., “universes that almost have the same structure or same cyclic periods.” So I don't think there are two or more different types of island universes in a multiverse or a megaverse. But the main thing that the entire universe must naturally care about is the symmetry in the entire universe. The entire symmetry and separated symmetries would work together utmostly using waves, structures, groups, constants, etc. Even thinking well about the possible asymmetry/gap between matter and antimatter helps us understand that perhaps that asymmetry could make ‘something that can evolve’ with a cyclic process. If gravity depends on a few sub-waves (E.g., neutrinos) and their amount (entropy/decay), it (GR) doesn't explain their origin.

10. My Philosophy About The Scientific Method, Predictions & Imaginations

The absolute truth about this universe might not make people happy about this universe. Some people don't try to find the absolute truth. And some people try to find the absolute truth in the wrong place.! Some people are limited in the knowledge they can access. Thus, some people don't even know the different types of discoveries and teachings about the absolute truth, so they miss the chance to decide whether that knowledge is important or not.!

Science should be based on reliable scientific arguments. Putting logically inconceivable (impossible) arguments between gaps in science is not real science. Some were based on misunderstandings or weaknesses in scientific methods, theories, and technologies (E.g., (1.) If quantum space decides the speed of light and photons are massless, isn't $E=mc^2 >$ quantum? What is mass? (2.) The Fine-structure constant (α) = $1/137$ or 0.007297351 . But, the reduced Planck constant (\hbar)= $h/2\pi$. $h/\hbar = 6.283185311$. Does 2π convert α into $0.007297351 \times 6.283185311 = 1/22?$ Is it a structure? Or $1:22:1=24?$). Some unscientific arguments move to gaps in science by cutting themselves. Hidden dimensions could make relatively invisible realms and life forms. The invisible Dark Matter shows us that the universe is not only about us (Matter). Assume the earth was not a scientific possibility. But interactions could make heavenly or hell worlds with different masses and forces. The visible matter is not the only set of matter that we can measure. So it's difficult to say that we are special or we need a simple/unpolarized universe to call it natural/stable. Matter/space balance is logically natural. The complexity of the universe is not a good reason to make unimaginable explanations, especially depending on an idea of a person. Or by believing someone who couldn't explain any deep scientific/quantum thing or process that usually can only be explained in detail with a very high level of technology.

Comparing a minimal imbalance between two related things with an unrelated big result to show a huge balance is an act of ignorance or a way to show a huge fake balance. “Cosmological constant is associated with Dark Energy (inconsistent/unknown energy: around 67.4 ± 0.5 (Hubble Tension) to 73.5 ± 1.4 (or 67 to 75) km/s/Mpc). It expands space by acting against gravity between galaxies as a small imbalance between densities inside and outside the visible universe. But showing it as a huge balance instead of as a minimal imbalance is irrelevant/fake.” The way of thinking and analytical ways help find the truth. E.g., It is difficult to use some technologies to prove scientifically that smoking (cigarettes) causes cancer directly, as it takes various periods to appear in the body. And there are many more reasons that can cause cancer instead of smoking cigarettes. But there are analytical ways to prove the impact of smoking cigarettes based on medical reports, analysis, probabilities, ratios, predictions, personal experiences, etc. E.g., There are around 8 analytical ways that can be used vastly (repeatedly) to prove the rebirth:

- 1.) Why do some children talk about past lives? Why do they talk about accidents?
- 2.) Near-Death Experiences (There are thousands of academic publications on experiences that were based on mind-body dualism, including seeing with no activity in the brain.)

- 3.) The existence of mental states, the subconscious mind (E.g., Hypnosis), brainless animals, etc
- 4.) Unusually receiving unusual powers to some people which they could use to perform supernatural or paranormal activities. (E.g., Lior Suchard)
- 5.) Ghostly beings, activities of ghosts, paranormal experiences, spirit possessions, etc.
- 6.) Some people who had supernatural abilities said that they attained ‘Samādhi/Jhāna’ in meditation to see past lives, see heavenly beings, etc. (E.g., Ram Bahadur Bomjon)
- 7.) Some animals and children have unique talents and intelligence by birth.
- 8.) There is no significant difference between sub-waves in atoms and quantum foam in space. So the mind possibly can travel through the quantum foam if the mind behaves like quantum fields, quantum entanglements, waves, etc.

11. Using Meditation To Train The Mind To Understand The Nature Of Reality

*According to my understanding of Buddhism, there is an illusion in the mind that impacts living beings and makes them think as PERMANENT living beings (permanent souls) unconsciously. Considering that possibility based on logical explanations in Abhidhamma and other analyses on the conservation of consciousness, I decided to identify that illusion to remove or reduce it. And stop me from becoming a conditioned living being again and again without my intention if rebirth would be badly conditioned on impermanence “in a cyclic and endless universe. *(17)”*

Most people know that we can train the mind. But sometimes we don’t have enough time to do that. So, we have to find solutions to give us some time to train our minds. Experimentally, I tried to listen to the nature of the mind and body using a recorded Vipassana (special/super seeing) Meditation with a short version of the Loving-Kindness Meditation. I thought about those things myself to see what happens or feel the change in me. It was great. I could use Breathing Meditation (with or without a Mantra) or Walking Meditation to relax the mind and body.

Understanding the nature of the mind is an individual responsibility. E.g., “Removing the ‘I am the body/soul view’ (‘Sakkāya Diṭṭhi’).” Nevertheless, It is good to convince people about the importance of thinking about our real nature while using the most practical ways to develop ourselves in the best path.! According to Abhidhamma, life is a stream of fundamental moments called Citta-khaṇa. In that case, rebirth is a SIMPLE process that depends on the state of mind (including the last moment of mind). So we should be aware of the risk of that simple quantum process to prevent or reduce unfavorable possibilities. And I prefer to make people think about the nature of the mind as an essential personal research/investigation. Also, I like to share a way that we can use to guide the mind quickly.!

Focusing attention on something again and again for a long time is the best way to see that thing as it is. And It is like being mindful of something very deeply. The Pali word ‘Satipaṭṭhāna’ (Sati/mindfulness or Smruthi/reminding Paṭṭhāna/attendance) is sometimes translated as ‘the establishment of mindfulness.’ Satipatthana Sutta (scripture) shows a way to focus attention on the body (Kāyagatā), feelings (Vedanā), mind (Chitta), and phenomena (Dhammā). And there is a process in those things that we should see called Arising, Vanishing/Ceasing, Both Arising and Vanishing/Ceasing. According to Buddhism, there are three characteristics of all existence and beings. Namely, ‘disappearing or unliking or uncontrollable’, ‘non-existing/self or meaninglessness or unbeneficial’, and ‘dependently-existing/depressing or unsatisfactory or sufferable’. I tried to bring the essence of those teachings into a single meditation. If some meditations are helpful, then learning and using a practical meditation is logically intelligent research or investigation. And a person can do it to learn more about it and experience the change in life.

E.g. (to understand and experience):

i.) Breathing is not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking (Aniccā). Depressing and prone to suffering (Duhkha). Meaningless and there is nothing as a self (Anattā). May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

ii.) Postures are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

iii.) Behaviors are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

iv.) Obnoxiousness in the body: 32 dirty body parts are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

v.) Primary Elements (Dhātu): Earth/Solid (Patavi), Water/Contract (Āpo), Fire (Thejo), Air/Expand (Vāyo), Space (Ākāsa). Primary Elements are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

vi.) A dead body in a charnel ground that undergoes the decaying process while eaten by animals is not someone. It's not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

vii.) Sensations are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

viii.) Intentions are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

ix.) Five Hindrances (nīvaraṇa): Sensual wishes/desires (Kamachanda), Anger/ill will (Vyapada), Sloth & torpor / Depression (Thinamidda), Restlessness & Worry (Uddhaccha Kukkuccha), Doubt/suspicion (Vicikiccha). Five Hindrances are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

x.) The Five Aggregates Of Clinging (upādāna-skandha): Materiality or Form (Rūpa), Sensations or Feelings (Vedanā), Perceptions and/or cognitions (Sañña), Volitions or Mental Formations (Saṅkhāra), Consciousness (Viññāna/consciousness is the middle/anti-knowing like a Re-knowing in the Citta/mind-moment/3Khana). The Five Aggregates Of Clinging are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

xi.) Combinational results that arise by meeting Eye, Ear, Nose, Tongue, Body, and Mind with Form, Sound, Smell, Taste, Touch and Thoughts are not me, not mine, nor my soul. Discontinuing and uncertain/unliking. Depressing and prone to suffering. Meaningless and there is nothing as a self. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

xii.) Seven Factors of Enlightenment (Satta Bojjhaṅgā): Mindfulness (Sati), Investigation of the nature of reality

(Dhamma Vicaya), Energy/determination (Viriya), Joy or rapture (Prīti), Relaxation or tranquility (Passaddhi), Concentration/ Clear awareness (Samādhi), Equanimity (Upekkhā). Mindfully stay and see the arising, ceasing, and both arising and ceasing Seven Factors of Enlightenment. May all beings or Cittas be at ease, healthy, and well.

12. Assumptions And Approximations With Questions And Suggestions

12.1.) Scientists say that “Standard gluon sub-waves are massless. But there are gluons in vacuum space with a mass, and travel slower than the speed of light. *(18)” In the dimensional structure, there is a set of candidates for the standard elementary sub-waves and sub-waves in vacuum space. The calculation shows two sets/gluons with $(+1-1)/3$ dimensions like the standard gluons. And another with $(+0.5+0)/3$ dimensions like gluons in vacuum space. Because elementary sub-waves most probably could get mass on the unstable Charge and Spin (unstable Spin: $1/2$). W and Z bosons don't have an unstable Spin ($1/2$), but they have dimensions like the dimensions/Charges in Fermions ($x/3$ without 0.5) to get mass from the Higgs fields. So they are massive too. The Standard Model has 9 unique and fundamental sub-waves (Higgs particle, 4 Fermions, 4 Bosons). But “experiments show 19 extra parameters that need to be applied for the theory by hand (E.g., adding masses, charges, etc.) *(19)”. Perhaps, there are around 19 hidden actions with the sub-waves. E.g, $9+19=28$. Buddhism mentioned 28 or $24(+4)$ material actions.

12.2.) If 1 is not converting to $0.5+0.5$ dimensions itself somehow, then Spin $1/2$ is emerging from an anti-reaction onto a dimension. Or, It is the superposition of the final 1 and 0.0 pair $(+1/-+0.0)$ as an interaction of 1 with 0.0 that would try to cancel/stabilize it by making two separate sets of dimensions $((1/2+1/2) \times \text{sets})$ as an interaction between them, like switching. Perhaps, like turning all the matter sub-waves into antimatter at once and returning.!

12.3.) According to the dimensional symmetries, the first wave function $(+1)-(-1))$ would make 4 probabilistic dimensional structures (1×4). And then, same like that the next wave function $((1 \times (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3))$ OR $(+1-(-1))$) would make 16 probabilistic dimensional structures (4×4). But the polarized wave function $((+1 /-+0.0 +0.0 \ -+1)x0^5)$ would make only 32 probabilistic dimensional structures (16×2) on the separation of the symmetry (polarization) during the first asymmetric interaction. The highest structure (last zone) or the lowest (first zone) could be highly polarized, connecting them to narrow points/destinations. And it could be a less habitable zone for any kind of living being. In that case, probably there are around 31 structures of dimensions that emerged on the wave functions as many worlds/planes (just like the 31 worlds/planes mentioned in Buddhism).

12.4.) If the Higgs particle doesn't behave like it has $1/2$ Spin, then perhaps that Spin $1/2$ cancels out by something else. Seemingly, the Higgs particle decays quickly without allowing its motion to show its Spin. According to the dimensional sets, the Higgs Boson is a fermion (like electrons), and it is not a Gauge Boson. Therefore, it can make the 2nd and 3rd generations of it like fermions.

12.5.) CMB radiation shows a lot of properties in the early universe (heat, density, matter distribution, etc.) in a very short period between 13.8-13.7 billion years. “But it doesn't show CMB properties beyond that period until the light comes from beyond that range. *(20)” It is difficult to know the density, polarization, and some other properties in the regions beyond the observable universe to make theories based on them. If the Big Bang continued to distant regions, perhaps those CMBs may show a universal polarization. The universe could be many sets of energies like many Planck energies ($n \times 1.22 \times 10^{19} \text{GeV}$). General Relativity and entropy can't explain its size. The dipole anisotropy of the CMB and anomalies and the Great Attractor lead us to think about island universes, etc.

12.6.) The early interactions made a few compressed structures with different strengths of the compressions, capable of making many compact objects like a chain of many compressions. And there are 4 higher compression ratios (1-mid:2, 1:2-last, 1-last:2, 0:3-all) like matter compression in Stars, White Dwarfs, Neutron Stars, and Black Holes.

12.7.) Mass (m) becomes Energy (E) as $E = mc^2$. But if the speed of light depends on the Density of Vacuum Space (DVS), it would impact the speed like this: 'the speed of photons' / 'the density of space' = ' c^2 ' / '(DVS)²'. The mass density of space is most likely equal to this: 'Mass of space in a Planck volume' / Planck volume. We can apply the mass density of space ((Mass in Planck space)/ ℓp^3) into the $E = mc^2$ equation to show the connection between the speed of light and the density of space. If we write the mass in a Planck volume like this $Mps/\ell p^3$, we can find the energy like this: $E = m(c^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2)$. There are $kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2}$ units in that energy equation. The kg unit in energy turned into kg^{-1} . Momentum is related to Mass, but the momentum (p) in the $E=pc$ equation doesn't represent Mass. So perhaps, the Energy per Kilogram (kg^{-1}) unit with $m^8 s^{-2}$ units represents the fundamental (quantum) units in energy better than $kg m^2 s^{-2}$ units. $c = 299792458 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, $\ell p^3 = 4.2217 \times 10^{-105} \text{ m}^3$

$$E = m(c^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2) \text{ OR } ((p+mv)/v)(c^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2)$$

$$E = m ((c^2 / (Mps / 4.2217 \times 10^{-105})^2) == mc^2$$

$$(1 \times 4.2217 \times 10^{-105})^2 / Mps^2 == 1$$

$$Mps^2 = (4.2217 \times 10^{-105})^2$$

The current mass of vacuum space in a Planck volume: $Mps = \pm 4.2217 \times 10^{-105} \text{ kg}$

But, based on the accelerating expansion of the universe, the calculated mass density of the vacuum is about $6.5 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg/m}^3$. In that case, the vacuum mass/energy of space in a Planck volume == $(6.5 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-27}) / (4.2217 \times 10^{-105}) = 1.54 \pm 1 \times 10^{-132} \text{ kg}$. It is not equal to the above Mps value of $4.2217 \times 10^{-105} \text{ kg}$. Perhaps, calculating the mass density of the vacuum space based on the accelerating expansion of the universe doesn't show its real value. Based on that energy equation, the minimum Planck mass in spacetime is the mass density in Planck space.

The Planck energy in space: $Eps = m ((c^2 / (Mps / 4.2217 \times 10^{-105})^2)$

$$Eps = 4.2217 \times 10^{-105} \times ((89875517873681760 / (4.2217 \times 10^{-105} / 4.2217 \times 10^{-105})^2)$$

$$Eps = 4.2217 \times 10^{-105} \times 89875517873681760 = \mathbf{3.794274738 \times 10^{-88} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^8 \text{ s}^{-2}}$$

Mass is like wave dimensions. There are 11 dimensions ($kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2}$: $1+8+2=11$) in that quantum unit of energy. The energy/mass in elementary sub-waves/waves is related to their frequency. Perhaps, the mass represents a complex quantum process in frequency. The wave function in the Schrödinger equation is a complex (unexplained) function. And quantum field theory uses complex/imaginary numbers (E.g., $\sqrt{-1}$) to get real solutions. So possibly, the most fundamental (super quantum) nature of frequency/energy is based on sets of linear dimensions (linear kg, m, s units).

If $m=0$, and $E = ((p+mv)/v)c^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2$, then $E = (p/v)c^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2$. If $v=c$, then $E = pc/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2$.

If momentum is nearly equal to zero ($p=0$), then $E = mc^2/(Mps/\ell p^3)^2$. But $Mps/\ell p^3 = \pm 1 \text{ kg/m}^3$, so $E == mc^2$.

If Energy (E) = $kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2}$, then it must be consistent with the other units. There are extra dimensions in that energy. Also, there are extra dimensions in Volt as $kg.m^2.s^{-3}.A^{-1}$. The Ampere (A) is the base unit of electric current. $V = J.A^{-1}.s^{-1}$. The Joule (J = $kg.m^2.s^{-2}$) is a derived unit of energy. Hence, if the Volt (V) = $kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2}$, then $kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2} = J.A^{-1}.s^{-1} = kg.m^2.s^{-2}.A^{-1}.s^{-1}$.

$$kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2} = kg.m^2.s^{-2}.A^{-1}.s^{-1}$$

$$A = kg.m^2.s^{-3} \times kg.m^{-8}.s^2 = \mathbf{kg^2.m^{-6}.s^{-1}}$$

If the Ampere (A) = $kg^2.m^{-6}.s^{-1}$, then $kg^{-1} m^8 s^{-2}$ units for Energy become consistent with the other units.

12.8.) Assume there is more space beyond our island universe. If so, the galaxies should move to balance the density between island universes. The entire universe can expand its edge equally or faster than light without reversing (0 to

∞). But the beginnings at the edge of the whole universe can make density/matter in some areas and a time delay in them, making them big. Likely, space is a stable form of mass, and mass continues in space as matter and a process. Gravity changes the density of space in matter areas and beyond them. If Gravitons come back, matter can contract.

12.9.) Comparing the 28 material forms/actions mentioned in Abhidhamma with the elementary sub-waves in physics:

Concretely Produced (Nippahanna) Rūpa (Ruppana/Rūppatiti Rūpan: Oppression/Irritation is a form/Rupa)

Great Elements (Mahā Bhūta):

Pathavi (extension/hardness), Apo (cohesion/fluidity), Tejo (heat/hotness), Vāyo (motion/pushing & supporting).

Those 4 great/primary (Mahā) elements stay with the following 24 observer-derived (Upādā) material forms/actions:

Internal (Pasāda/Brightening/Polished-base) Rupa (material actions with potential qualities):

1. Cakkhu (eye-brightening form) ===== smallest Photon? (a potentially emerged (Forced/Kammaja) form (Rūpa)?)
2. Sota (ear-brightening form) ===== smallest Z Boson or W Boson? (potentially emerged?)
3. Ghāna (nose-brightening form) ===== smallest W Boson (1)? (potentially emerged?)
4. Jivhā (tongue-brightening form) ===== smallest W Boson (2) or Z Boson? (potentially emerged?)
5. Kāya (body-brightening form) ===== smallest Gluon? (potentially emerged?)

Gocara (Objective) Rupa:

6. Vaṇṇa (That-color gap form) ===== smallest Electron (dimensional entanglements/gaps would make forces/actions)
7. Sadda (Here-sound vibrating form) ===== smallest Down Quark (2)? (vibrating due to a set of $--+\backslash(\mathbf{u1})^2 (\mathbf{d1})^2$)
8. Gandha (Flowing-smell down-falling form) ===== smallest -Down Quark (1)? (an action $--\backslash(\mathbf{d1})^2 (\mathbf{u1})^2$) : **Down**
9. Rasa (Rising-taste up-rising form) ===== smallest Up Quark? (an action $--+\backslash((\mathbf{u1})^2 (\mathbf{d1})) \gg (\mathbf{u1})$) : **Up**

Bhava (Behave/State) Rupa:

10. Itthi Bhava (Feminine behavior form) ===== smallest AXion (A)? (potentially emerged?)
11. Purisa Bhava (Masculine behavior form) ===== smallest AXion (X)? (potentially emerged?)

Hadaya (Mind Base):

12. Hadaya Vatthu (Seating of the heart/mind) ===== smallest Monopole or Z-1/2 or Z Boson? (potentially emerged?)

Life:

13. Jīvitindriya (Life/Regeneration facilitating/driving form) ===== smallest Higgs Boson? (potentially emerged?)

Nutritional:

14. Oja (Nutritioning form) ===== smallest Z (1/2) or Z Boson or Magnetic Monopole? (potentially emerged?)

Abstract (Anipphanna) Rūpa

Limiting Phenomenon:

15. Ākāsa dhātu (Spacing form relic) ===== $-(+0.5+1)/3 + (+0.5+1)/3$ dimensional set?

Communicating (Viññatti) Rupa:

16. Kāya Viññatti (Body intimation) ===== smallest Neutrino (1)? (newly created/Cittaja emerged symmetry breaking?)
17. Vaci Viññatti (Vocal intimation) ===== smallest Neutrino (2)? (newly created/Cittaja emerged symmetry breaking?)

Mutable (Vikāra) Rupa:

18. Lahutā (Lightening form) ===== $(+0.5+5)/3 - (+0.5+5)/3$? (the dimensions fill the gaps of entanglements?)
19. Mudutā (Softening/Moderating/Releasing/Freeing form) ===== $(+0.5+4)/3 - (+0.5+4)/3$? (fill the gaps?)
20. Kammanñātā (Compromising/Balancing form) ===== $(+0.5+3)/3 - (+0.5+3)/3$? (fill the gaps?)

Material Qualities (Lakkhana Rupa):

21. Upacaya (Producing form) ===== $(+0.5+2)/3 - (+0.5+2)/3$?
22. Santati (Continuing form) ===== $-(+0.5+2)/3 + (+0.5+2)/3$?
23. Jaratā (Decaying form) ===== $(+0.5+0)/3 - (+0.5+0)/3$? (a gapless infinity called Anantara Pratya/dependent?)
24. Aniccatā (Dissolving/Discontinuing form) ===== $(+0.5-1)/3 - (+0.5-1)/3$?

According to Abhidhamma, the Material Forms exist in a Matter Zone called Rūpa-Kalāpa. And Matter Zones make Matter Body (Rūpa Sarira/elementary sub-waves), and then they become Matter Groups (Rūpa Santhāna like Atoms). Suddhāṭṭhaka (Pure-Eight) zones make the material objects. But there are 21 material zones with 8 to 13 qualities.

12.10.) The radiation of the CMB or General Relativity didn't show the start of space and time or a quick expansion of a Big Bang. The first point in the first universe could make 6 more points around it first because 6 infinitely small points that symmetrically emerged around an infinitely small point could cover that middle point. Each point could share a dimension with the nearest next point. If there are two or more points at the same place/point, they can increase the density (mass) of the point. Those 6 points that exist around a point and share a dimension with the first point should have potential gaps (geometric 90° gaps) between them, and make more (20) points around the first point in the next moment while the 6 points continue to the next point. But likely, the new (20) points couldn't fill the 90° gaps around the first point between the 6 points symmetrically, covering the first point almost completely. Probably, the points that emerged with the smallest moments could make matter dimensions, and the points that emerged into the earlier points to be symmetric (neutralize the time duration) made antimatter dimensions.

12.11.) Most likely, a lot of matter and antimatter annihilation could/must make a lot of virtual matter and antimatter in space while conserving their charges using neutral/virtual energy, and making photons with their total energy. Probably, the photons that emerged with those annihilations could become matter and antimatter again, causing them to continue that process as a cyclic process while increasing the virtual sub-waves and/or density in space/vacuum.

12.12.) Probably, there are earliest or standard (almost fixed) points in space that could become higher densities (massive) while increasing the density of space. Perhaps, some interactions made extra points in points that could move/bend between the standard/fixed fabric of space. Likely, the quantum gravitational force (graviton) can interact with the dimensions of the extra points, and make a chain reaction, causing matter to feel the gravitational force and move with the extra points in space. Time is real, and it could continue from moment to moment. Time could create the entire universe and continue making the edge (making dimensions) of the entire universe while continuing from nothingness to more nothingnesses (increasing nothingness) with the directions of time relatively.

12.13.) Most likely, the electromagnetic waves/fields in photons can travel faster than the speed of light in its wave. Probably, electromagnetic fields can move around a point, behaving like particles. Perhaps, the missing right-handed matter neutrinos like hypothetical right-handed neutrinos of Dark Matter or observers/detectors like measuring sub-waves that could have a potential to cause DNA to be right-handed like them and become the process of the mind and/or some Dark Matter photons would travel faster than light because of their highly symmetrical relative dimensions. Presumably, what we mostly observe/feel is the force of sub-waves, and we measure the force using the movement of mass. Likely, the Earth's magnetic field is not a force because an electric field can cause moving the

magnet in the compass if it contains an electric field. Electrons repel each other. If some invisible fields travel faster than the standard speed of light, then an observer in that frame of reference would see our light sub-waves with a mass-repulsion or as light in a high-density medium while seeing their light sub-waves without a mass-repulsion. If so, the amount of mass-repulsion and penetrating energy/mass/force relationship in elementary sub-waves could depend on their speed and the related frame of the observer.

12.14.) According to the laws of electricity and magnetism, a density ($\nabla \equiv (\partial/\partial x, \partial/\partial y, \partial/\partial z)$) of electric charge (ρ) is the source of the electric field of force (E); and an electric current density (J) is the source of a magnetic field of force (B). Gauss's Laws: Electric Field, $\nabla \cdot E = \rho/\epsilon_0$ (ϵ_0 is vacuum permittivity), Magnetic Fields, $\nabla \cdot B = 0$.

The Faraday-Maxwell Law: $\nabla \times E = -(\partial B/\partial t)$.

The Ampere-Maxwell Law: $\nabla \times B = \mu_0 (J + \epsilon_0(\partial E/\partial t))$, (μ_0 is vacuum permeability).

Those laws should match with fundamental reality to make correct interpretations of their fundamental process. But according to my analysis of those processes, electrons can't make an electric field force with their filled dimensions. It is not electrons that reject electrons and move away, making the field force; and that outside force is the magnetic field force that causes the potential force called electric charge. Therefore, Gauss's Laws for Electric Field should be $\nabla \cdot B = \rho/\epsilon_0$, and the Magnetic Fields should be $\nabla \cdot E = 0$. Also, the Faraday-Maxwell Law should be $\nabla \times B = -(\partial E/\partial t)$. And the Ampere-Maxwell Law should be $\nabla \times E = \mu_0 (J + \epsilon_0(\partial B/\partial t))$.

12.15.) If the density of Black Holes doesn't decrease when their size increases, can the surface gravity decrease? If adding more mass to a Black Hole lowers its density, then there is a maximum limit that a Black Hole can grow. But astronomers discovered Black Holes larger than that maximum limit. If the larger Black Holes make less density, then the largest Black should become stars/planets or collapse and become smaller Black Holes. I think the current concept of the density of Black Holes is mostly based on assumptions to support/prove General Relativity. Scientists don't know the precise physics of supernova explosions that make a Black Hole. A normal gravitational pressure would not give enough pressure/force to make a Black Hole. So likely, the 99% energy that stars emit as neutrinos during the supernova explosions makes extra gravity, making that very high pressure. I guess metals emit undetectable gravitons while absorbing heat from outside. And then, they may cool down by releasing undetectable neutrinos. Perhaps, that is why metals are cooler than other things even if metals become cooler due to moving their heat faster as well. Scientists say that there are metals inside some asteroids and inside the moon that can produce gravity. And presumably, rocks don't make much gravity. Quantum fields would show activities in hidden worlds.

12.16.) If the Charge of an electron must relate to the mass of an electron to maintain the mass ratio of an electron, then calculating the mass of an electron using that mass-ratio would relate to the type of calculation/measurement of the Charge of an electron. And if the measured Charge of an electron depended on the Charge of a proton, then it would not relate to the real mass of an electron. So perhaps, magnetic fields and the Charge (potential force) of a proton cause electric fields to make an opposite Charge to be balanced with protons, becoming an electron. I think electrons have a positive/appearing effect/output because electrons are filled with enough dimensions/gaps that don't require an attraction/input. Also, positrons should be filled with opposite dimensions or lacking dimensions related to its points, making their appearance positive with a negative nature of the Charge. So the matter and antimatter nature likely depend on the appearance and disappearance of dimensions/time (relatively opposite dimensions) of those sub-waves. I think the difference between matter and antimatter is not related to their defined Charge because the fundamental form/nature of electrons has a positive Charge, and the stream of Charge (potential force) is only an output of material energy/dimensions. Electrons wouldn't make the stream of Charge directly because likely the first formation of protons made a stream of the Charge itself while making a stream of positive Charge called electrons. And likely, the first formation of anti-protons made a stream of anti-charge itself while making a stream of negative

Charge called positrons. Protons are attracting dimensions of electrons, staying at the center of atoms. But antimatter protons would provide dimensions, using the anti-dimensions of its quarks, and behave somewhat like electrons. Positrons would take dimensions from anti-protons, and behave somewhat like protons. If two or more anti-protons can't stay together because of their positive electron nature (Pauli Exclusion Principle), then it creates an asymmetry between matter atoms and antimatter atoms. And anti-protons would not support making antimatter atoms larger than hydrogen atoms. The unfilled nature called charge (flow) between quarks could make protons and antiprotons.

12.17.) Most probably, the nothingness in the universe increases infinitely without reversing, making the relative existence. Material and immaterial forms would exist using the empty points of many nothingnesses, using them as the substance that only exists momentarily. Elementary sub-waves wouldn't feel the distance in the structure of their relative fields between the gaps of space. Also, the entangled sub-waves wouldn't feel the distance between them co-originatingly, showing that they communicate faster than light, even after traveling a very long relative distance.

12.18.) Presumably, the matter zones emerge, becoming larger within 24 moments, and then they become smaller and disappear within the next 25 moments. Perhaps, it makes matter within the first 24 moments, and it makes antimatter (increases negative charge) within the next 24 moments. If so, Antimatter is like a disappearing state of matter that uses the disappearing moments of the matter zones. And if matter zones make both matter and antimatter, then matter and antimatter would exist together like an illusion of material energy relative to the observer who uses matter or antimatter. And a covered point of existence that would contain -6 dimensions relative to matter means that it potentially contains +6 dimensions relative to antimatter, but those antimatter points are reflections of dimensions received from other points. The +1 and -1 dimensions are relative to their direction of appearance because it depends on the point of reference, and the point itself is the detector or observer. If 6 matter points make a virtual antimatter point between them relatively, then that virtual antimatter point would become a matter point at the next moment, continuing the causality. Likely, a matter zone starts to appear from point to point, and then, it starts to disappear from point to point using a minimum of 5 (6,8, or 12) points towards the 6 direction. If we start to count it from the middle, then there are 4 (5 or 7 or 11) points toward each direction and 1 point or 6 points at the center. And it makes a minimum of 25 (31, 43, or 67) planes of existence or 30 (36, 48, or 72) existence using points of matter zones. The relations between momentary existence would make points of matter and points of antimatter relatively. But only the points that originate dimensions (matter points) are real, and the points that virtually emerge between the dimensions of the originated points (antimatter points) are only reflections of matter points. So the interactions between the originated points and virtual points could make a relative process, and behave like energy. Those points of emptiness between their nothingness and infinite nothingness would relate to the 6 main directions of existence momentarily.

12.19.) It is important to use meaningful mathematical tools to find meaningful solutions. As an example, the radius of a circle can be relative to its center, making plus and minus radiuses. Also, the circumference of a circle is relative to its radius (r). But calculating it using the irrational ratio called 'Pi' (π) is somewhat meaningless. So deriving a solution to calculate the circumference of a circle without using an unexplained ratio would be meaningful.

If, $2\pi r/4 = \pi r/2 = a$, then: $((2r)^2 - \pi r^2) / 4 = r^2 - ((2r + a)/4)^2 = r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/16$.

$\pi = 3.141592653589793238..$ And also, $Z \times (2r + a)/2 = r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/16$.

$$Z = (2r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/8) / (2r + a)$$

So if, $r=1$, and $a = \pi r/2$, then: $Z = 0.4061766990685089/3.570796326794897 = \underline{0.1137496126621952} = z$.

If, $r=2$, then: $Z = 1.624706796274037/7.141592653589793 = 0.22749922532439 = \underline{0.1137496126621952} \times 2 = zr$.

Therefore, $Z = zr = \underline{0.1137496126621952r} = (2r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/8) / (2r + a)$. It doesn't need π to get solutions.

If, $Z = zr = \underline{0.1137496126621952r} = r/8.791238726849318 = r/(4 \times 2.19780968171233) = r/(4 \times Y)$, then:

$(4Y)/r = (2r + a) / r(2r - ((2r + a)^2)/8r)$. And if $2r = d$, then:

$$Y = (d + a) / (4d - ((d + a)^2)/d) = (3.570796326794897)/(8 - 6.375293203725964) = \underline{2.19780968171233..}$$

$$4Y = 2(d + a) / (2d - ((d + a)^2)/2d) = (4 + 3.141592653589794)/(4 - 3.187646601862982) = 8.791238726849318..$$

$$4Y = (d + a)/2 / (d/2 - ((d + a)^2)/8d) = (1 + 0.785398163397448)/(1 - 0.796911650465745) = 8.791238726849318..$$

$$4Y = (r + a/2) / (r - ((r + a/2)^2)/4r) = (1 + \pi/4) / (1 - ((1 + \pi/4)^2)/4) = 8.791238726849318..$$

$$Y = (r + a/2) / (4r - ((r + a/2)^2)/r) = (1 + \pi/4) / (4 - ((1 + \pi/4)^2)) = \underline{2.19780968171233..}$$
, So, $(a/2)/r$ is related to $\pi/4$.

Therefore, the smallest standard circle would have 8 points around the center, and looks like an octagon with 8 pads.

If the length of the Z is different (larger) like this: $Z \times (2r + a)/4 = r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/16$, then:

$$Z = (4r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/4) / (2r + a) = \underline{0.812353398137018} / 3.570796326794897 = \underline{0.1137496126621952} \times 2 = 2z.$$

Therefore, $Z = znr = \underline{n(2r^2 - ((2r + a)^2)/8) / (2r + a) = 0.1137496126621952nr} = nr/(4Y)$. So n could be a wave.

If, $i = \sqrt{((-1/\sqrt{2})x(1/\sqrt{2})) + ((-1/\sqrt{2})x(1/\sqrt{2}))} = \sqrt{(-0.5 + (-0.5))} = \sqrt{-1}$, then the 'i' represents an area related to real numbers and positions. Therefore, sometimes imaginary numbers like this $\sqrt{-1}$ can be relatively real.

The Higgs field has a geometry like a Mexican hat that likely represents a polarization of the area of the circle it contains. Likely, the wave function and some other quantum processes are related to symmetries and asymmetries between polarized areas of virtual quantum circles. Also, the relative symmetries (relative existence) of quantum processes are likely related to asymmetries between them that continue their existence for another moment like making an angular momentum. And the angular momentum of dimensions would make a relative appearance, existence, and disappearance between dimensional structures.

Testing #1:

If, $a = \sqrt{2} = 1.414213562373095$, and $r=1$, then: $Z = (2 - ((2 + \sqrt{2})^2)/8) / (2 + \sqrt{2}) = 0.1590097423302679..$

Testing #2:

If, $Z = \underline{0.1137496126621952}$, and $r = \sqrt{2} = 1.414213562373095$, then:

$$\underline{0.1137496126621952} = (2 \times 2 - ((2\sqrt{2} + a)^2)/8) / (2\sqrt{2} + a)$$

$$-21.426140080935 + 6.566851150789942a + a^2 = 0, \text{ then: } a = \underline{2.391697647064}.. \text{ — (A)}$$

If, $Z = \underline{0.1137496126621952}$, and $r = \sqrt{1/2} = 0.7071067811865475$, then:

$$\underline{0.1137496126621952} = (2 \times (1/2) - ((2\sqrt{1/2} + a)^2)/8) / (2\sqrt{1/2} + a) = (1 - ((\sqrt{2} + a)^2)/8) / (\sqrt{2} + a)$$

$$-4.713070040467498 + 3.738424026043752a + a^2 = 0, \text{ then: } a = \underline{0.99557830916451}.. \text{ — (B)}$$

If there is a potential balance between $r = \sqrt{2}$ and $r = \sqrt{1/2}$ radiuses that anyhow can be somewhat symmetrical, then their polarized circumferences would relate to a fixed ratio like this:

$$\text{Polarized Related Circumferences, PRC (A)/(B) = } \underline{2.391697647064} / \underline{0.99557830916451} = \underline{2.402319963229}..$$

If the waves in quantum fields require symmetric mathematical ratios to be stable, then they would have stable wave symmetries related to unique symmetric ratios between wavelengths and wave amplitudes. If the Electron's g-factor (-2.00231930436256) or Tau's g-factor is a ratio related to radiuses of stable orbits or any orbital ratio, then it would have a relationship to an orbital ratio related to radiuses and circumferences of symmetrical and related circles.

Perhaps, the hypothetical Tau's g-factor would relate to the Electron's g-factor and the Muon's g-factor like this: Approximately, Tau's g-factor, $Tgf = Mgf + (Mgf - Egf) = 2.002331841 + 2.002331841 - 2.002319304 = \mathbf{2.002344378}$..

Testing #3:

If, $Z=Zr = r/(4 \times 2.19780968171233)$, and $Y = 2.19780968171233$, then perhaps, the hypothetical Tau's g-factor would relate to it like this: Tau's g-factor $\times Y = 2.002344378 \times 2.1978096817 = 4.400771860065964$. And $Y/\text{Tau's g-factor} = 2.1978096817/2.002344378 = 1.097618224840642$.. $4.400771860065964/1.09761822484064 = 4.0093830081082$.. Then, $4.0093830081082/4 = 1.002345752$.. Therefore, $2.002344378 - 1.002345752 = 0.999998626 = \mathbf{1.00000}$..?

12.20.) The interpretation of the growth of space called 'increasing vacuum energy' is simply misleading because it can be some extra space that comes faster into the observable universe uniformly. Likely, there was a lot of extra space outside the observable universe. Energy is not something that exists, and energy is an output. So the name vacuum energy is an irrelevant answer because it only mentions the output, ignoring the growth of space (virtual sub-waves). The space (virtual sub-waves) inside galaxies shows that space doesn't make extra space from anything. Probably, the earliest state of the emerging universe and near the edge of the expanding universe made states of point source energy fields that could collide later becoming matter and antimatter. Perhaps, high-speed beams of energy must collide with each other to make matter and antimatter, including the virtual sub-waves in space/vacuum. Probably, the virtual sub-waves would conserve their charge without positive energy. The hypothetical Cosmic Inflation assumption/idea is most likely not scientific because a lot of creationists try to use it to spread creationism (Creationism is unscientific and Georges Lemaître was a Catholic priest and father of the Big Bang theory. The independent researcher Russel E. Gmirkin's book (Plato and the Creation of the Hebrew Bible) claims that the Pentateuch (the Torah) utilized the works of Plato's dialogues. Also, the other early oral religious teachings could develop later using new teachings and concepts to make them better and tell that they are old and original direct teachings from a supreme person.). And observations show that a lot of energies require a lot of space, to begin with scientifically, and the massless energy beams use space to exist and collide with each other. The wavelength of high-energy sub-waves is relatively small, but it doesn't make the density of their waves small. So comparing the capacity of energy in high-energy sub-waves relative to its wavelength with the wavelength of energy in the early universe to tell that the early universe emerged from a very tiny high-energy (singularity) that didn't use a lot of space because it had an almost infinitely small wavelength is not a good analogy. Also, the space inside galaxies usually doesn't grow or expand with Dark Energy. So Dark Energy is not likely a product of existing space. Virtual gravitons (probably, the force that oscillates neutrinos) would increase the space density inside galaxies, attracting virtual sub-waves in space while traveling through them. The low difference between the density of space inside matter areas and space areas could reduce the expansion rate of the universe, and it was lower (67.4 ± 0.5 km/s/Mpc) in the observable earliest universe. The high matter densities like the earliest stars and Black Holes could cause extra space to come and fill the low densities in space, increasing the wavelength of light while increasing the expansion rate between them, and causing the Dark ages in the early universe. According to Abhidhamma, "a rain of energized water (like water sticks, water robs, etc) fills the world (island universe) gradually and stays stably filled for a long time until cosmic air (virtual sub-waves) comes into the filled world (island universe), causing to start the expansion. Then, the world (island universe) stays stably expanded until the contraction." Virtual sub-waves in space (like air) can come into low-density areas of space (between galaxies) from outside of the island universe until those virtual sub-waves can go there with a maximum speed (up to the speed of light) to distribute virtual sub-waves uniformly between galaxies. The Big Bounce model is the best explanation for the conservation of energy in both matter and space inside an eternally growing universe. So the entropy can sometimes decrease or increase inside some areas of the universe if the number of gravitons increases while increasing the entropy. Also, the particle accelerators make high-energy sub-waves using low-energy sub-waves, showing that entropy is sometimes a byproduct of acceleration

(force). So cyclic expansion and contraction of gravitons can increase and reduce entropy in the observable universe.

12.21.) If the fine-structure constant depends on the process and structure of the initial (Planck length size) matter zone, then there must be variables and fixed values related to them. If the matter zone shows 17 moments of existence within its lifetime, then possibly, the number 17 could be a fixed value in the constant. If the matter zones disappear and appear 4 times within 4 lifetimes showing a complete rotation virtually, making a complete rotation of existence, then possibly, the number 4 could be a fixed value in the fine-structure-constant. If there is a fundamental value for the dimensionless moment called g-factor that is related to the angular momentum of elementary sub-waves in the observable universe, then a variable or a fixed value closer to the electron's g-factor $-2.00231930436256(35)$ (g(e) in " $\mu(S) = g(e) S \mu(B)/\hbar$ ") would have a relationship with the fine-structure constant. So perhaps, the fine-structure constant would be equal to a collection of variables and fixed values like this: $\alpha = 1/(17 \times 4 \times 2.015235714020221) = 0.007297351$. But if it is true, the value of the g-factor must be a square root of its number if the g-factor in the fine-structure constant must always be a plus (+) value. According to the fundamental behavior of the dimensional sets in my theory, the electric field doesn't make a force, and it would make an angular momentum (electric moment) like the so-called magnetic moment ($\mu(L)$ in " $\mu(L) = -g(L) L \mu(B)/\hbar$ ") in Maxwell's equations. Likely, the electrons are angular momentums because the electric moment (called the magnetic moment according to Maxwell's equations) makes the angular momentum like the orbital angular momentum of an electron. The real field in the electric field in Maxwell's equations is likely a magnetic field in reality. And the real field in the magnetic field in Maxwell's equations is likely an electric field in reality. It was an interpretation that made errors in science.

12.22.) Arguably, the wavelength and wave amplitude (height) of electric and magnetic waves represent the strength of their capacity of asymmetry (potential energy). And their asymmetry and speed would relate to their wavelength and wave amplitude. If speed is relative to the conservation of symmetry of waves, then either wave amplitude or speed should change with a change in its wavelength. So quantum jumps or fast interactions should increase their speed if their wavelength and wave amplitude are relatively small. The wave amplitude of electrons is likely very high even if their wavelength is very small, and that is why they are powerful. And generally, their amplitude would cause their waves to move slowly between other waves. The density of a wave would relate to its duration between its wavelength like this: **Density** = (Average Height[m] × Average Width[m] × Average Length[m])/Time[s].

The work (output effect) of a potential energy would relate to a two-dimensional frame (area: X × Y) that moves Quantitatively (**h** or **lp³** volumes) with Time (Planck time (**tp**) to Z direction): **Frame** = X range[m] × Y range[m].

The volume of a sphere ($V = 4/3 \pi r^3$) would relate to its diameter (2r) and a related ratio (R) like this:

Related ratio: $R = ((4/3) \pi r^3) / (((\pi/4)^3)(2r)^3) = \underline{1.080759292184936}$. So, the volume: $V = R(\pi^3)((2r)^3)/64$

Therefore, the output energy (**E**) would relate to the potential energy in a wave like this: E.g.,

$E = (\text{Frame}[m^2]/\text{Quantity}[kg^{-1}]) \times ((R(\pi^3)/64) \times \text{Height}[m] \times \text{Width}[m] \times \text{Length}[m] \times \text{Density}[m^3.s^{-1}]) / \text{Time}[s]$.

In short: $E = (F/Q)((R(\pi^3)/64)HWLD)/T$ $kg^{-1}.m^8.s^{-2}$. Therefore, if we try to apply the speed of light (**c**) and

the Planck constants (**h** or **h**) to it, then approximately, $E = ((lp^3)/(htp))L(cHW)^2$ while $h = J.s = kg.m^2.s^{-1}$,

or $E = HWL((lp^3)/h)c^2$ while $h = kg$, or $E = (F/h)((R(\pi^3)/64)HWLD)/T$ while $h = kg$, or $E =$

$(Ftp/h)((R(\pi^3)/64)HWLD)/T$ while $h = kg.s^{-1}$.

E.g., i.) If the Electron's mass = $2886.999695480226 \times 59 \times 3 = 510998.9461$ eV/c², and the Muon's mass = $10117.62668773341 \times 59 \times 59 \times 3 = 105658375.5$ eV/c², then Muon mass / Electron mass = $3.504547196029557 \times 59..$ Approximately, the Tau's mass = $510445.2743464522 \times 59 \times 59 = 2883.871606477131 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 3 = 1776860000$ eV/c². Then Muon mass / Tau mass = $3.508348521830645/59..$ Electron mass / Tau mass = $1.001084683865977 / 59^2..$ Seemingly, there is a wave symmetry between Electron, Muon, and Tau. And likely, those numbers are

related to a ratio between wave amplitude (height), wave width, wavelength, and wave density like this:

Wave symmetry ratio of the Electron: **2886.99969548 : 1 : 59 : 3**. The Electron's structure has high and low values.

Wave symmetry ratio of the Muon: **10117.6266877 : 59 : 59 : 3**. Muon's wave height can cause it to decay faster.

Wave symmetry ratio of the Tau: **59×2883.8716 : 59 : 59 : 3**. Tau's high wave amplitude can make it unstable.

ii.) Velocity = $v = L/T$. Momentum = $p = mv$. If, **Kg work** = $m^3 = \ell p \times \ell p \times \ell p$, and potential energy = pc , and $E = (p/h) \times ch$, then $E = (mv/h)ch = (\ell p^3 \times L/T \times c \times h)/h$. But if $h = HWD$, then energy $E = (\ell p^3 \times L \times c \times HWD)/(hT)$.
 $E = ((\ell p^3)/h)cLHWD/T$ or $E = HWD((\ell p^3)/h)c^2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^8 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ while $h = J \cdot s = \text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, or:
 $E = ((\ell p)/h)cLHWD/T$ or $E = HWD((\ell p)/h)c^2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^8 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ while $h = \text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. So If, $D/h = 1$, and mass = $m = HW\ell p$, then: $E = mc^2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^8 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ (m is not in Kg. m = the volume of the mass = $1 \times HWL/\text{mass } m^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$).
 Force (F) = the amount of volume relative to the mass \times acceleration = $n \times (HWL/1\text{kg}) \times a$. So, $E = n(HWL/1\text{kg})c^2$.
 The $E = mc^2$ equation is wrong if energy is an accelerated expansion of a volume. A force/F is a linear acceleration.

Interactions of waves would reduce or increase the density of their potential energy, causing them to change their properties according to the wave symmetry related to their formation. But the wave symmetry would depend on its fundamental quantity related to the Planck constants (h or \hbar). Therefore, different Planck constants could make different waves of quantum fields. Also, a high-quantity Planck constant could make a tight symmetry that doesn't allow traveling at the speed of light. And a low-quantity Planck constant could make a loose symmetry that allows traveling faster than the speed of light. If the observers are related to their wave symmetry, then different Planck constants could make parallel worlds relative to each other.

Photons have a potential to make energy, but energy is not a mass or anything else in reality. Photons make energy when they change their volume like breaking high-energy photons into many low-energy photons or when they change their wavelengths. Photons can change something, but photons just change their volume. And if something absorbs photons, then that process of absorption is a negative energy. If photons can burn something, then that process of burning is a positive energy. The expansion of a volume of mass is positive energy. The contraction of a volume of mass is negative energy. Mass doesn't become energy like this mc^2 with these units $\text{Kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ because energy depends on mass like this $(\text{volume}^2)c^2/m$ with these units $\text{m}^8 \cdot \text{s}^{-2} \cdot \text{Kg}^{-1}$. Therefore, the $E = hf$ equation must have those units like this $\text{Kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times \text{m}^6 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{Kg}^{-2}$. And the $E = hc/\lambda$ equation must be changed into this $E = hc/\lambda \times (\text{volume})^2 / (\text{mass})^2$. Also, the $E = hf \times (\text{volume})^2 / (\text{mass})^2$.

12.23.) According to Abhidhamma, a moment of observation in the mind/Citta has a minimum of 7 qualities/activities called 'fair for all the minds' (Sabba Citta Sadharana), the mental activities/factors (Cetasika). It is a big process that happens during a single observation of the mind. Those 7 simultaneous activities are as follows: 1. Touch, Collision (Passa), 2. Feeling, Intensity (Vedana), 3. Signal, Reminder (Sangna), 4. Intention, Action (Chethana), 5. One-pointedness, Concentration (Ekaggatha), 6. Vitality, Life Faculty/Density (Jivitindriya), 7. Mental Advertence, Remembering (Manasikara). Also, there are 52 mental factors/activities that join with the mind/Citta in many different combinations while making a mind/Citta moment. Likely, the mind/Citta doesn't require an extra moment to remind the previous activity of the consciousness/Citta. As mentioned in Buddhist texts, a moment of consciousness/Citta is filled with a lot of simultaneous functions that can behave like a stream of souls (living moments) conditionally. The mind/Citta is not the only absolute reality mentioned in those earliest texts. The smallest material/Rupa unit lives for 51 smallest moments repeatedly. Also, the mind/Citta usually continues a series of mind/Citta activities (Citta Vithi) like a thought process within 51 smallest moments. So likely, the mind moment depends on the lifetime of the material units. The Buddha didn't reject the existence of the material world outside of the mind. Those Buddhist teachings about mind and matter are not interpretations, and they are original teachings

that are mentioned in early Buddhist texts. Probably, the mind/Citta receives, calculates, and outputs information like a calculator, and processes information like making judgments. The mind (Citta) collects and makes information instantly, and makes the resultants called Karma Vipaka. It says, seeing/contact makes a special knowledge (Gnana) element (Vinnana Dhatu) using the eye and light. It is like heat changing the nature of an ice cube, making different outputs. The process of the mind is a measurement/Mano of beauty (Cittan Mano = Citta/Mind). According to the teachings on Paramartha Dhamma (Ultimate Realities), the mind/Citta observes purposes during all the mind/Citta moments. And the Nibbana Dhatu (the element that ceases/disappears or blows out) is an ultimate reality/moment that causes stopping the mind/Citta. Most likely, the Nibbana Dhatu is similar to the 17th mind moment related to the smallest material zones that disappear after the 16th mind moment of its existence because the 17th mind moment is likely a gap between the death and rebirth of the material zone. According to early Buddhist commentaries, a material zone disappears before the end of its cyclic lifetime. So the 17th mind moments in it would have a somewhat disappeared mind moment. According to Buddhism, the fully enlightened (Arhat) lay people die within 7 days. So likely, they don't have a purpose to live unless they become Buddhist monks to teach Buddhism. Therefore, a purposeless and unattached mind would go through that Nibbana mindless moment letting it stop the continuation of the mind. The noble eightfold path is related to 8 good emotional qualities (Mental Factors) that should be applied to the mind moment simultaneously to attain enlightenment.

Enlightened/Arhat Theros/monks don't have unwholesome biases, and they preserved those teachings from the beginning. And relatively, we can trust enlightened beings more than most unenlightened scholars and their new interpretations because educational qualifications alone don't remove all the unwholesome biases. The enlightened/Arhat Ananda Thero had a strong memory, and it helped him to preserve 82000 Buddhist teachings. And 42000 teachings from the 84000 Theravada Buddhist teachings are Abhidhamma teachings. It says, Abhidhamma is a single discourse, and the Buddha taught it to his mother and other beings in Trāyastriṃśa heaven for three months while going to the upper (Uttar) continent called Uttarakuru to receive meals from humans to partake meals. Uttarakuru continent is closer to heaven, but according to the texts "When it is midday in Aparagodānīya, the sun is setting in Jambudvīpa and rising in Uttarakuru, while it is midnight in Pūrvavideha." If some modern humans who live in Jambūddhīpa (the lowest continent) are capable and intelligent enough to understand those teachings, then I think that they should know the existence of those teachings whether they like to study them or not. Those teachings are not like usual Dhamma Talks, and they are highly technical. But it is not good to think that humans don't want to study those teachings to have a deep understanding of Dhamma/Reality. Theravada Abhidhamma is the well-preserved original science of Buddhism. And Theravada Suttas are sometimes like prescriptions/menus (directions) to understand the science (Abhidhamma) in Buddhism. And it is difficult to understand the science of Buddhism using Suttas only. Abhidhamma helps us understand the teachings in Suttas deeply. Surprisingly, this mathematical research proves the existence of the ultimate realities mentioned in Abhidhamma. The Buddha's explanation is also scientific because he used a different observable analogy to represent those fundamental elements, and he named them with names of material and mental qualities that anyone can think to exist in reality or anyone can feel their existence. So both mathematical and observable ways are scientific. Each step in the calculation is highly derivable. Also, the result of the calculation is compatible with modern science and better than some modern scientific explanations.

12.24.) Special relativity wouldn't change absolute time. The so-called relative time is likely an illusion created by relative interactions. The concept of relative time is most likely a wrong interpretation that doesn't represent the fundamental interactions because the fundamental moment would pass relative to the last moment. And the fundamental time is not relative to speed. It is not only a theoretical illusion that is related to special relativity but also the high-energy muon sub-waves that travel faster than their usual speed showed that they can travel long

distances without decaying quickly. Some observations like that probably show an illusion. The higher speeds would reduce the decaying process of fundamental waves (elementary sub-waves) because of high-energy quantum jumps or something like that, but it doesn't mean that they didn't experience time. The wavelength of light (photon) waves increases while traveling long distances, and therefore their energy reduces while traveling. The reason to increase their wavelength is not the important thing. The fact is their structural change clearly shows that they experienced time. Perhaps, the real problem is not relative to special relativity. Stable wave symmetries of wave particles would reduce the speed of their decaying process. The low-energy muon waves would have a large wave amplitude with a large wavelength that can make the muon wave symmetry unstable, causing it to decay faster. But if the high-energy muon waves have a smaller wavelength with a smaller wave amplitude relative to the low-energy muon, their wave symmetry would be stable, causing them to decay slowly. Electron waves would stay stable because they relatively have very low energy levels and are likely related to protons. The speed of light is not the same for all the observers because only the decaying process in the observers reduces when they travel faster. And when an observer travels at the speed of light, the speed of light that travels with the observer should be equal to zero to the observer relatively. The absolute time and speed don't depend on wrong interpretations and errors in theories and observations.

The gravitational time dilation likely depends on the density (disturbance) in the medium because the pressure in the medium can reduce the speed of the traveler. Therefore, it is related to speed-dilation in higher density. Presumably, the real reason for some people to reject the existence of absolute time is related to the influence of their religious background. It is difficult to wake up the people who want to show that they are sleeping. And, it would be like playing the violin for deaf elephants if they can't hear it because of their religious and geo-political influences. Sometimes, scientists don't use the scientific method well. And the western scientific community is using inflationary Big Bang theories in the standard model of cosmology without discovering the origin of energy and cosmic inflation theoretically using a verifiable theory of everything. Compacted Energy waves should have a high density larger than the matter density in space, and that is why they collide with each other. Energy waves wouldn't easily move in a high-density medium that contains a lot of energy waves even if they repel each other, so they wouldn't travel faster than the speed of light. Virtual sub-waves in space contain energy that converts into massive and massless energy even if they annihilate each other. The energy waves wouldn't make the universe larger within its region, making virtual sub-waves and other massive sub-waves because masslessness is only a mathematical interpretation of the state of some material energy. And it doesn't mean that massless energy waves become larger matter and virtual sub-waves without using external space and sub-waves. The Higgs field would slow down some elementary sub-waves, changing their light-speed mass into a slow-speed mass without making mass. The Cosmic Inflation theory doesn't explain the nature of energy. The observable very huge early universe could be a result of the conservation of energy laws in the previously existing universe. Therefore, the faster-than-light cosmic expansion hypotheses mentioned in the standard model of cosmology don't represent real science. And it blocks other models.

Science is a belief when it is wrong and doesn't predict both the past and the future. It requires reliable scientific calculations to confirm scientific explanations. If some observed facts help to theorize and predict that the universe was a tiny singularity with an infinite density, then to call it a good scientific prediction, it should also predict its previous state with its ingredients. And the observed facts that can be used to make predictions should closely relate to the reference frame of the prediction. But there are no such observed facts supporting it like that. Hypothesis like the so-called Planck epoch (10^{-43} seconds universe), Grand unification epoch (10^{-43} s to 10^{-36} s), Inflationary epoch with a rapid expansion of space (emerging a 10.6 light-years universe within 10^{-32} seconds), and Quark epoch (10^{-12} s to 10^{-5} s after the Big Bang) are misleading interpretations of the theories and experiments. Some interpretations change the theory itself (E.g., they turn General Relativity upside down to predict a tiny singularity with an infinite density), and the collisions between the high-energy particles in the particle accelerators are not like

the so-called Big Bang. They try to say that the 27.574 billion light-years large (CMBR distance \times 2) early universe or a larger part of the universe emerged and expanded before a second. Likely, some people want to reject the requirement of a larger time that needs to explain the origin of the very huge early universe scientifically. And some people try to popularize those hypothetical epochs as if they are verified real science. We should use theories and observations correctly. Humans, animals, and trees become larger little by little after their birth, but it doesn't mean that they were very tiny a few moments before their birth. The observable universe's beginning can't necessarily be a new beginning, and its observable growth doesn't necessarily indicate that it had a new beginning. But it doesn't mean that there was not a beginning from zero at some point. Christianity avoided the concept and symbol of zero, and the Catholic Church refused to accept zero until some major developments in mathematics. But it is difficult for theorists to reject Big Bounce models without using nothingness (zero) in the first place to make their theories. *Prof. Albert Einstein said, 'Two things are infinite: the universe and human stupidity; and I'm not sure about the universe.'* According to Buddhism, the world systems (Sakwalas) formed during the period (eon) of expansion called Vivatta (expanding) Kalpa. And then, the expansion stabilizes during the Vivattasthai Kalpa. And then, it starts to contract during Sanvatta Kalpa. And finally, the contraction stabilizes within a similar duration called Sanvattasthai Kalpa. CMB radiation didn't show redshifts. The Big Bang singularity is only an assumption. Early universe was more than 27 billion light years wide. Galaxies don't expand faster than light. Black Holes could come closer to each other and convert into beams of high energy due to the low density of hidden matter in space in the early universe. Beams of energy could collide with each other, making the CMB radiation. Nothing required early space to expand faster than the speed of light. The speed of expansion is similar in the visible universe, and expansion depends on Black Holes.

12.25.) If the lifetime of a dimensional structure is equal to the lifetime of a Material Zone called Rūpa-Kalāpa, then we can compare their similarities. According to Abhidhamma, 17 from 51 smallest moments (Khaṇas) within two or more contacted Rūpa-Kalāpas reflect/host out re-knowing to continue 17 mind/Citta moments (51 Khaṇas) like this:

- 1.) Atīta/Past Bhavanga/Becoming-part (**AB**) comes after/from Photon? (**P**)
 - 2.) Bhavanga Calana/Vibrating (**BC**) comes after/from Magnetic Monopole? (**M**)
 - 3.) Bhavanga Upaccheda/Sub-breaking/Arrest (**BU**) comes after/from W Boson 1? (**W1**)
 - 4.) Pancadvaravajjana/ Advert-the-five-sense-doors (**PD**) comes after/from Neutrino 1? (**N1**)
 - 5.) The sense of a lot/well-knowing like a Cakku/Eye Vinnana/Anti-knowing (**CV**) comes after/from Z Boson? (**Z**)
 - 6.) Sampaticchana/ Receiving/ Accepting (**Sam**) comes after/from W Boson 2? (**W2**)
 - 7.) Santīrana/ Investigating/ Inquiring (**San**) comes after/from Gluon? (**G**)
 - 8.) Vottapana/ Determining or Manodvaravajjana/ Advert-the-mind-door (**V**) comes after/from Neutrino 2? (**N2**)
 - 9-15) Javana/ Energy making/reacting (Karma making) (**J**) is an energy created by antimatter and matter? (**E1-7**)
 - 16.) Tadarammana/ tight-conform-aim/ Registering (**T**) is a tight-energy while ending the Zone's lifetime? (**RE1**)
 - 17.) Tadarammana/ tight-conform-aim/ Registering (jump?) (**T**) is a tight-energy while disappearing? (**RE2**)
- E.g., A mind/Citta series: (**AB**),(**BC**),(**BU**),(**PD**),(**CV**),(**Sam**),(**San**),(**V**),(**J1**),(**J2**),(**J3**),(**J4**),(**J5**),(**J6**),(**J7**),(**T1**),(**T2**).
A smallest material series: (**P**),(**M**),(**W1**),(**N1**),(**Z**),(**W2**),(**G**),(**N2**),(**E1**),(**E2**),(**E3**),(**E4**),(**E5**),(**E6**),(**E7**),(**RE1**),(**RE2**).

12.26.) The space between galaxies is somehow expanding. But it doesn't mean that space is growing. High-density space could come from somewhere into low-density space if quantum gravity supported it. Space and material elements could exist before the Big Bang/Bounce. Also, time must exist before space, and that is why space starts and continues. The edge of the entire universe could continue growing the universe because of the relatedness between each new point at the edge. And that relatedness could make some constants relatively. General Relativity doesn't explain how mass makes gravity. Gravity could originate from an effect of some quantum sub-waves that travel from high-density to low-density space. Some quantum forces could increase the density of space around a massive object. It means that space doesn't bend in reality, and only its density increases due to gravity. Elementary

sub-waves can't decide the actual time because quantum fields are more fundamental than them, and quantum fields obey the actual time flow. If quantum fields travel like waves, then they should travel faster than light to travel at the speed of light. Prof. Albert Einstein introduced energy in Kilograms. But in reality, energy doesn't have a mass, and only a mass produces energy. Light contains a type of mass because momentum contains mass. According to my theory, Prof. Albert Einstein is wrong about time. But a lot of scientists believe his principles. Experiments proved the co-existence of matter and antimatter sub-waves called virtual particles or quantum foam/fluctuations in vacuum space. Massive objects reduce the speed of particles around them because gravity could increase the density of space near those objects. It is not a bending. Theorists shouldn't ignore quantum nature to prove General Relativity. Black Holes would absorb ordinary matter and hidden/Dark matter to grow continually till their limits. If the existence of Dark Matter is causing the expansion of material energy called Dark Energy, then the expansion can stop after reducing the amount of Dark Matter. According to Stephen Hawking, Black Holes will evaporate due to virtual matter and antimatter in space. But new observations proved that large Black Holes grow even without absorbing ordinary matter. And, a new scientific paper suggested that larger Black Holes would eat Dark Matter too. Maybe, Black Holes would absorb low-energy photons after the annihilation of low-energy matter and antimatter in space.

Scientists should know what Energy is. They can't say that the expansion of the observable universe is made by the energy that makes space. The materials in space are not massless energy, and forces can change their location, and make high and low densities. General Relativity is only a geometric interpretation. The contraction of the observable universe could easily start soon after the moving materials in space reduce the speed of the expansion. Balloons expand somewhat uniformly even if air comes inside from only one side of them. Probably, space air comes between galaxies from everywhere, causing a similar expansion. The standard model of cosmology ignores that possibility while using an unbelievably infinite energy density without matter, blocking the Big Bounce model. Energy is a work like a finished action that doesn't have a mass. Real energy is a relatively high-speed (accelerated) expansion of a volume relative to the amount of mass of an object and space (density of the medium). Light slows down when it travels in a high-density medium, indicating that it needs free space to be. Probably, a mass changes its symmetry relative to the speed of its continuation, but it doesn't convert mass into energy. All the field waves have some type of mass, and that change doesn't make them energy. Prof. Albert Einstein introduced energy using mass (Kilograms), and his definition of energy only represents potential energy in mass, and it is different from real energy. All the quantum elements including space are potential energy because they contain moving or rest mass. And a packet of mass should have a maximum density if it doesn't overlap with other packets of mass. But usually, the defined mass represents overlapped field waves. Likely, the wave function of quantum elements collapses due to increasing the density of their mass during the observation. The wavelength of light changes while the light is traveling because light experiences time. Prof. Einstein didn't care about what light experiences. Wave symmetry changes relative to their speeds, and it doesn't change the absolute time they experience. Relative time doesn't exist in reality. If the light has a mind, then it can know that it changes with time due to quantum fluctuations. Interpretations don't change the reality of time, and light itself is moving in time. Changes in both matter and space make time. If some theorists believe in Einstein's space bending, then it means they don't care about the quantum nature of space. Some theorists tried to show the origin of matter inside a tiny singularity by turning General Relativity upside down, using an unbelievable interpretation. Likely, they didn't know that only matter can produce energy, or didn't care about it!

12.27.) The absolute flow of time could make the relative reality relatively from point to point, and it could be the reality of the relative reality. A completely nothing universe is a thing even if it is infinitely nothing, and that nothingness could increase with time from point to point continuously because nothingness is not a constant with a permanent location. Also, the flow of absolute time is something fundamental that could continue and make relative points of nothingness (negative and positive emptiness). Therefore, relative time could emerge from relative

interactions between points of absolute time. If the smallest unit of matter is a zone like the smallest matter zone mentioned in Buddhism, then it would contain another smallest time smaller than the Planck time. And if the Planck volume appears and disappears repeatedly, then it somewhat prevents or reduces its further divisibility. And binary physics of reality is more fundamental than relatively emerged physics. The Planck constant is likely a fundamental constant. But this binary physics theory shows that there are probably 32 different/parallel Planck constants. Most probably, Dark Matter contains a lot of hidden layers of reality. And likely, there is high-density space and dark/hidden matter (parallel matter) around massive objects. Also, the Buddha explained about habitable 31 planes of existence. So around 32 or 31 Planck constants could make those parallel worlds/planes.! There are 20 Brahma realms, and they are based on low-density matter (Uthuja) like the hypothetical dark matter. The 6 heavenly realms have matter with 'nutritious' (Āharaja) molecules. The visible Human world contains high-density matter. The earth would have 2 hidden spiral arms called the Maha Meru (Large-Emerged) mountain, holding some material realms. But the highest realms don't need the Maha Meru mountain to hold them. The visible earth is also a part of the Maha Meru mountain. Therefore, it covers the sun at night according to Buddhist texts. The first 4 realms are hell realms called Hell, Animal, Pretha, and Asura realms. The 5th realm is the Human realm. But according to Buddhist cosmology, Jambudvipa is the lowest continent of Humans. Therefore, some Humans would live in the animal realm in Jambudvipa. Therefore, we can say that some Humans evolved from Animals. Maha Meru mountain would look like two spiral arms around the earth because it has a part of the mountain on the earth and another part below the earth. Also, the positions of the four continents of the four types of Humans are located around the earth one after another even if they are located in four different planes of existence. Totally, the Human world contains four continents and four different oceans with four different colors of water in four planes. Jambudvipa is the lowest continent, and the other continents would exist on the other parts of the Maha meru mountain around the earth.

Nothingness could grow with the unstoppable time while becoming positive and negative emptinesses of time relative to each other. Time is a moment of spacetime. A moment is a point of existence. A point of time is relative to the 6 directions and dimensions, and they exist relatively. Each point with time is like a baby universe. And they could make the relative existence relative to the directions and dimensions. Time could grow the universe, making and continuing the points of unstoppable time. The meaning of time is a continuation. Prof. Einstein can't change it using his principles. Everything experiences time, but sometimes it is not very obvious. Time could be the creator of everything, and time can move everything. It is extremely logical. Time is not a clock. The entire universe is completely new at each moment if time is the fundamental limit at each point. And those new points of time could make and maintain the limits of constants because the points of time are always new and relational to each other. Time could exist before space, and that is why anything starts and continues. Infinity is infinite if it is not relative. Infinite nothingness could be the infinite negative time in the completely nothing universe. And that moment of nothingness could be both infinitely large and infinitely small because it could not be relative to anything. And then, time could continue to the positive time from point to point because a small point of nothingness doesn't have a permanent location if time continues. Therefore, it could increase with time from point to point. Completely nothingness is also a thing even if nothing existed in the nothingness in the earliest universe. And time is the thing that must flow in the universe. The universe was a thing even if it was completely nothing because it was the only thing that could experience time. It is a simple logic. Time continues inside the Planck volume. And time is a fundamental reality even if it is completely new at each moment. Quantum entanglement is a connection between two entangled quantum objects, and those quantum objects don't feel the distance between them due to the nothingness of the quantum objects between them. The directions of continuation of time (plus and minus dimensions) of each point of nothingness would make geometrical relationships between points of nothingness from moment to moment while the points of nothingness continue to exist. Time could become the smallest moments of existence due to relationships between points of nothingness and continuation of time. Points of nothingness could

make dimensional relationships and structures while they continue to exist. The worlds/locations (Loka) of existence would become symmetrically zero (Suñña/Śūnya) because they must become zero/nothing in reality.

The entire universe had a start. But it doesn't mean that it had an infinite density and it started to expand like a balloon. It could start from a point, and it could expand from point to point. Therefore, the edge of the entire universe would expand forever. The eternal growth of the universe could start an uncountable time ago. Most probably, we only observe some parts of cyclic continuations in the observable universe. Real mathematics starts from zero, but some theorists tried to say that the universe started with strange mathematics that instantly jumps from nothingness to a point with an infinitely huge density. And they don't explain any reason for the growth of space after the formation of the infinite density. There is no reason to think that Black Holes make space (Dark Energy) while becoming more massive. Most likely, some Black Holes accelerate the flow of space materials between galaxies because they would absorb space materials to become more massive. A balloon expands somewhat uniformly when air comes into it, and space comes in while it is expanding. But it doesn't make extra material space. The illusory Dark Energy is a density balancing process/energy that mainly depends on absorptions of Black Holes. If supermassive Black Holes explode due to lowest allowed density, then a lot of solar systems would be damaged. The earliest growth of the universe and some interactions could make both space and matter. The observable universe is not the entire universe as the nearest galaxy is not the only galaxy. And some theories only relate to the frame of reference. High-density space materials could come from all around the universe into low-density regions of space, causing an expansion if quantum gravity supported it. Space materials would travel faster or slower or at the speed of light depending on their interactions with forces and because the speed of light and other elements depends on the density of space (medium) and their wave symmetry (mass distribution). Presumably, light (photons) and similar high-speed waves represent highly symmetric cancellations of opposite dimensions while becoming. So then, electrons would represent an amount of widely effective uncanceled dimensions on its asymmetric structure. Thus, gluons likely contain overly cancelable dimensional structures that cancel dimensions in other materials too. Quantum fields can change mass and speed. Kinetic energy can't make mass, and it only represents high-speed mass.

According to experiments, antimatter-protons could well behave with helium atoms like electrons in helium atoms. If antimatter protons strongly repel each other like electrons, then they would not become anti-helium atoms. Likely, electron's have a positive nature of charge against a positive charge, and the Pauli Exclusion Principle can represent it too. Real negative charges would not repel each other much. Therefore, the negative nature of protons could make atoms larger than hydrogen atoms. Also, the strong force could easily support it too. We know that two electrons repel each other. But two protons don't repel each other like electrons. Anti-protons can't make an anti-helium atom because they are somewhat like electrons. A positron is an anti-electron, but its structure doesn't allow it to behave like a proton even if it has a charge of a proton. The charge of protons and antiprotons is the main factor that impacts their interactions. Just imagine why electrons have a negative charge. Do electrons lack something? No. Electrons have a positive nature of charge in reality. Protons have a negative nature of charge in reality. Anti-protons have a positive nature of charge, and it gives its charge outside like electrons. Therefore, anti-protons repel each other like electrons. And the strong force would not be strong enough to make anti-helium atoms. Electrons have densities, and they behave like waves too. But observing their position can change their structure. Protons need electrons because likely protons lack positive charge. Anti-hydrogen atoms would not be very stable because anti-protons don't need positrons (anti-electrons) much. Charge likely depends on its structure, and it can overlap with each other. Massless photon hypothesis in QED doesn't prove that photons are massless, and it is a wrong interpretation because a photon is not just a force. Also, Proton's high mass doesn't come from its quarks. The gluon field in protons is responsible for the main mass in protons. Einstein's energy equation ($E=mc^2$) is not applicable to photons (light) if photons are massless. Also, the speed of light depends on the density of the medium, but Einstein didn't mention it in

his equation. If we fix that problem in his energy equation, then it shows that energy doesn't become mass because energy depends on mass.

12.28.) Time-dilation is an illusion of quantum wave symmetries. High-energy muons are not normal muons, and they don't decay faster. But it doesn't show a time-dilation. They are just behaving differently due to their different masses at different speeds. Quantum waves would have symmetries that can make the illusion of time-dilation. Slowing down the decaying process of a muon due to their high-energy mass doesn't show a time-dilation. It only shows a different wave symmetry in a different type of muon. It is obvious that high-energy photons, muons, and protons can't behave like a low-energy photon, muon, and proton. Therefore, they have different lifetimes. High-energy protons are not the original protons because they have an extra mass. Also, high-energy muons are not the original muons because they also have an extra mass with their higher speed. Therefore, time-dilation is an illusion created by the stable symmetry of the extra mass and its speed. It is common sense, and we can use our brain to understand it if we don't want to be brainwashed. Low-energy muons and high-energy muons are two different muons. The time of clocks slows down due to higher density of medium (space). Also, the time of clocks slows down due to the speed of clocks. Those two reasons change the clocks in higher orbits. But clocks depend on the nature of quantum objects and their medium. Therefore, clocks change depending on their location and speed. Scientists can use their brain to understand it. But sometimes, they would ignore it even if they know that it is a fact.

The mass of quantum elements changes when they travel faster with an acceleration due to an external impact, causing them to change their Specific Charge (e/m). The decaying process and the speed of clocks can depend on the Specific Charge. Therefore, the mass and movements of clocks can change with their traveling speeds without changing the absolute time flow in their quantum fields. The illusion of gravitational time-dilation is like slowing down the speed of light in water. Water doesn't change the time that light experiences. Disturbances in water cause the light to move slowly. General Relativity doesn't mention the density of space (medium). The time-dilation concept is an opinion that is being used to explain the slow speed or slow decaying process in clocks while ignoring the changes in wavelength and structure of material elements. Scientists have observed that the early universe was running slower. It indicates that the early universe couldn't expand faster than light even before that time due to its high density. Also, a clock can slow down in a high-density medium if the clock is completely open to the medium.

12.29.) Probably, most masses of quantum objects (standard elementary sub-waves) have a relationship to each other because their masses have a strong relationship to a very few similar numbers. E.g., 59, 31, 3.

The Electron's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.001387338009097 \equiv 510998.9461 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Muon's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 1.01886073187205 \equiv 105658375.5 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Tau's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.000302326214752 \equiv 1776860000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Up Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times (4 \text{ or } (2 \times 2)) \times 1.077816383200958 \equiv 2200000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Charm Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times (2 \times 2) \times 1.024565750222095 \equiv 1275000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$ or $(1264501098 \times 1.008302801805871) \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Top Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times (2 \times 2) \times (3 + 4) \times 1.008426030527669 \equiv 172760000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Down Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 3 \text{ or } (8 + 1)) \times 1.023381212332223 \equiv 4700000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Strange Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.051798216785732 \equiv 95000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Bottom Quark's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times (3 + 4) \times 1.008503859194067 \equiv 4180000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Electron Neutrino's mass $\equiv 31 \times 0.0709677419354839 \equiv 2.2 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Muon Neutrino's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 0.9994297371499791 \equiv 170000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Tau Neutrino's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.150513675909527 \equiv 18200000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The W Boson's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times (3 + 2) \times (3 + 2) \times 1.000094376386809 \equiv 80377000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Z Boson's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times (3 + 1) \times (3 + 4) \times 1.013040843642746 \equiv 91187600000 \text{ eV}/c^2$. OR

The Z Boson's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 2 \times 3 \times 7 \times 11 \times 1.000033128649901 \equiv 91187600000 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Neutron's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.00668920257026 \equiv 939565420.52 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The Proton's mass $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.005303472855531 \equiv 938272088.16 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

The mass of gluons without the fluctuations like quarks $= 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1 = 933322239 \text{ eV}/c^2$?

Photons have many different masses, including very low-energy masses. The mass of a photon $\equiv 31 \times a/b \text{ eV}/c^2$?

The Higgs Boson's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times (3 + 2) \times (3 + 14) \times 1.000404952049279 \equiv 125100000000$

eV/c^2 . OR the Higgs Boson's mass $\equiv 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 15 \times 17 \times 1.000404952049279 \equiv 125100000000$

eV/c^2 or $59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times (3 + 1) \times (3 + 7) \equiv 58846758120 \text{ eV}/c^2$ (The hypothetical mass of a matter or

antimatter Higgs super-fermion that has an undetectable $-1 \times$ Charge or $+1 \times$ Charge while $x > 0$) or three Bosons of

this: $59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 17 \times 1.000404952049279 \equiv 41700000000 \text{ eV}/c^2$. Perhaps, the Higgs Boson

contains three bosons, or it decays into matter and antimatter Higgs super-fermions and a photon before it decays

into fermions. Presumably, more groups of elementary sub-waves exist with relatively undetectable charges.

Likely, there is a fundamental building block with 31 points of existence. Perhaps, they emerged from 32 or 33 fundamental structures like 31 points of existence with a lost point or lost points of existence due to a delayed breaking point (like Bhavanga Upaccheda) and interactions. Most likely, a structure with connected 31 or 32 points of existence can connect with another similar structure by sharing their points of existence with each other like this: $((32 \text{ or } 31) + (-32 \text{ or } -31)) \equiv 29 + ((1-1) + (1-1) + (1-1))$ or $(1-1) + (1-1) - 29 \equiv 29 + (x+y+z \text{ or } y+z) - 29$. If $x+y+z=3a$ or $y+z=2a$, and $a=0$, then $29 + (3a \text{ or } 2a) - 29 \equiv 29 + (3 \times 0 \text{ or } 2 \times 0) - 29 \equiv 59$ points of existence with 3 or 2 potential gaps $\equiv 59 \times (\text{built-in } 3-3 \text{ or } 2-2 \text{ symbolic gap}) \equiv 59(3/3 \text{ or } 2/2 \text{ potentiality})$.

Arguably, 31 planes of existence could emerge if they depend on 31 types of possible connections between two connected fundamental streams of existence. If the three neutral gaps $((1-1) + (1-1) + (1-1))$ between the connected two streams of existence became a reason to originate a plane of existence like the third plane of existence, then two neutral gaps between two connected streams of existence $(61(\text{built-in } 2-2 \text{ symbolic gap}))$ could create the second plane of existence. Similarly, four neutral gaps between two connected streams of existence $(57(\text{built-in } 4-4 \text{ symbolic gap}))$ could create the fourth plane of existence, and so on.

The standard period of a second depends on the frequency of the caesium 133 atom, and it is not a universal constant. Therefore, the standard value of the Planck constant is not a universal constant, and its value depends on the measurement of time. If there is a smallest frequency related to the visible universe (visible plane) like a universal constant, then we have to change the value of the Planck constant to make it a universal constant in order to use it better. E.g. A smallest structure like this $59 \times 59 \times 59$ would have the smallest frequency with a universal Planck constant like this $0.5396595277 \times 10^{-15} \text{ eV} \cdot \text{Hz}^{-1}$?

Hypothetical extraordinary correlation #1:

The particular mass of Down Quark and Up Quark could emerge while the structure of the Gluon field becomes geometrically symmetric when it decays into a Proton, making the strongly stable Proton.

Hypothetical Structure Of The Proton

Proton's hypothetical structure $\equiv 3481 \times 31^2 \times 31 \times 9 \times 1.005303472855531 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

Down Quark's hypothetical structure $\equiv 59 \times 31^2 \times 9 \times 9 \times 1.023381212332223 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

Hypothetical extraordinary correlation #2:

The mass of the Helium nucleus $\equiv 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 4 \times 1.005996337712896 \equiv 3755675017.36 \text{ eV}/c^2$

The asymmetry in the Helium nucleus $= 1.005996337712896 - 1 \equiv 0.0059963377128957$

The mass of the final atomic symmetry $\equiv 1/0.0059963377128957 \equiv 166.7684589961309 \equiv$ Nearly, 167 amu.

Atom-65 Terbium's mass $\equiv 158.9254$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1629$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 3396$ K

Atom-66 Dysprosium's mass $\equiv 162.50$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1680$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 2840$ K

Atom-67 Holmium's mass $\equiv 164.9304$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1734$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 2873$ K

Atom-68 Erbium's mass $\equiv 167.26$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1802$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 3141$ K (It is stable at 167 amu)

Atom-69 Thulium's mass $\equiv 168.9342$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1818$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 2223$ K

Atom-70 Ytterbium's mass $\equiv 173.04$ amu, Melting point $\equiv 1097$ K, Boiling point $\equiv 1469$ K

12.30.) According to my analysis of Buddhist sources, a Citta/mind arises (Uppada) during the arising (Uppada) moment of a matter unit or existing (Titi) moment of a matter unit while producing Cittaja Rupa (mind-born matter) or converting the existing (Titi) state of matter into Cittaja Rupa, depending on the formations of material units. And then, the dissolving (Bhanga) moment of a matter unit would host the existing (Titi) moment of the Citta/mind moment. Also, it shows that the existing (Titi) moment of the mind is not material, and it belongs to the Nama/Name category. Finally, the Citta/mind dissolves/vanishes during the next arising moment (Uppada) of the matter unit. The next arising (Uppada) moment of the Citta/mind can happen during the existing (Titi) moment on the same matter unit until the Citta/mind arises (Uppada) on another matter unit during its first existing (Titi) moment. Also, the previous Citta/mind moment could dissolve (Bhanga) during the arising (Uppada) moment of the new matter unit. Smallest material zones originate due to four types of interactions called Chittaja, Āharaja, Uthuja, and Kammaja, depending on Thejo (heat quality/intensity/input like an anti-nature) and Oja (nutriment move/influence/output).

The persistence of a Cittaja Rupa-Santati ((mindly matter-generation)) for 30 mind-moments with extra 16 mind-moments beyond a Rupa-Kalapa (Matter-Zone) shows that Rupa-Kalapas normally make connected structures with around 30 to 33 mind-moments. Only a Samapaththi (transcendent) state of the mind can change it, and stop making more than 17 mind-moments. So probably, it is a natural nature of the smallest Matter-Zones that happens with or without a connection to the mind/Citta. The state of the mind continues without a break during the moments

of Jhāna. The mind moment with 1st Jhāna contains the mental factor (Cetasika) called Prithi (Happiness). The mind stream (Citta Vīthi) can continue more than 17 mind moments during the Jhāna state of the mind. The effort (Viriyā) to gain ownership comes from views (Ditti) and sensual wishes/desires (Kamacchanda) with a pain until we remove the craving to gain ownership of something from our minds.

Space can come into existence without using a previously existing ingredient/dependent (Prathya), and also, space element (Ākāsa Dhātu) emerges from the 4 existing ingredients called Āharaja (nutrition-born molecules), Cittaja (mind-born actions), Uthuja (weather-born elements), and Kammaja (reaction-born entanglements) according to the Buddha's teachings. Form is emptiness, and emptiness is form. Probably, the two forms of emptiness can behave like space (free points of space) and counter space (solid points of space). Space could increase due to the unstoppable flow of the absolute time from negative time (zero-infinity) to positive time. A smallest point of time is a thing relative to another smallest point of time that emerged from it, even if the ingredient of those points is nothingness. A collection of smallest moments are like points of nothingness until they relatively interact/identify to be different. An existence is like a contact (touch) that becomes an energy like a form (matter) with a change/pressure (feeling) or a density, and a relation (cognition) or a noncognition, factors (ingredients) or a mixture, a knowing or a taking. The intrinsic nature of them is a state of emptiness, and the state of emptiness can be different from moment to moment. There is matter outside the body that touches the body and makes the matter of the mind called Chittaja Rupa (Mind-born form). Therefore, the mind could emerge from something like the collapsed state of the wave function. The mind-stream (Citta-Vithi) can be a result of the ultimate matter units called Rupa-Kalapa because both of them usually continue for 17 mind moments (17 arising, 17 existing and 17 dissolving moments). The states of those 17 mind moments are different to each other even if they have common properties because the states of the mind would depend on the process of continuation of matter units. The physical and spiritual/mental faculties cause the mind to continue like a life, even if those faculties are not parts of a soul. The mind receives information about previous actions called Prawuthi (Pre-News) Vipaka (Results) from those faculties. But those faculties are impermanent. The mind is only a product of nature. Therefore, many parts of nature can behave like faculties of a life. According to Abhidhamma, The spiritual/mental faculty of wisdom/prudence called Paññā/Prajñā Indriya can develop into 'need-to-know-the-unknown-thing-faculty' (Anagnnaathagnnassaamindriya) after the stream-entry (Sothapanna) state of the mind. Male and Female faculties can change from life to life on Karma (entangled-reactions). Faculties (Indriya's) can dominate over other faculties. Therefore, they have received the name of a major god called Indra.

According to the Buddhist teachings, the self-view (Sakkāya diṭṭhi) is an illusion (delusion). And ego depends on the self-view. A root cause for our bad actions is delusion/ego (Moha). We are trapped into our egos, and our addictions maintain our egos based on the body and place that we are living in. We are not our greed (Lobha), anger (Dvesha), and delusion/ego (Moha), but they change our lives. The right view helps us to find the right knowledge (Prajna) and liberation. Wish/Desire (Chanda) is a choice, and it is not bad if it is not affiliated with attachment. Wished/Desired Attachment (Chanda-Rāga) comes with the root cause called greed, causing Karma to make suffering/rebirth, etc. Attachment is natural, but it should not be entertained with desire. We can eat foods without a desire to feel the taste of the foods. Removing all our addictions (Āsava/Āsrava) purifies the mind, and removes greed, stopping rebirth.

Pali and Sanskrit languages were not spoken languages, and the Buddha could use the other languages like Magadhi Prakrit to speak. The first Buddhist council was held in 483 BCE during the reign of King Ajatashatru, three months after the Parinirvana (Perfect-Cessation) of the Gautama Buddha. The first Jain Council was held in 3rd Century B.C., and the chief patron was Chandragupta Maurya. Early Jains used Ardhamagadhi, a Prakrit language. And then, Sanskrit and Maharashtri Prakrit. The founder of Jainism was Niganta Natha Putta, and the name Mahavira has not been used in early Buddhist sources to mention him. Likely, the name Mahavira and some Jain stories developed

later. The texts of Jainism and Hinduism could develop from time to time like educational systems with newly made stories about eternal gods and fake history, including new stories about leaders of Jainism. Gautama Bodhisattva is a great hero for Buddhists. The name Mahavira is mentioned to refer to Niganta Natha Putta after the 5th century AD.

Chandraguptha Maurya (Emperor Ashoka's grandfather) invaded Magadha Kingdom with the help of Brahmana Chanakya, and took Magadha Kingdom from Nanda kings (King Ugrasena, Maha-Padma Nanda, Dhana Nanda and brothers) in 321 BCE. Greek sources mentioned that Alexander the Great and his army were attacking Porus and Nanda kingdom. Therefore, Porus was the great-Padma Nanda. But some texts in India have tried to convert Maha-Padma Nanda into a villain. Ugrasena was the first Nanda king, and he took Magadha kingdom from King Kalashoka according to Buddhist sources. Therefore, the name Ugrasena was not a name for Maha-Padma Nanda, and Ugrasena was Padma Nanda's nephew. They were two different people even in the later developed Indian texts tried to change it. The first Nanda king Ugrasena was not a son of a king, and he was a thief according to Buddhist sources. So, Porus (Padma Nanda) said that the Nanda king (Ugrasena) was despised by his subjects according to the Greek sources. The name Porus was not an Indian name. There were people with the name Ugrasena in Agra (near Punjab), and Ugrasena could come from there. Greek sources mentioned that they were attacking Agrammes (or Xandrames), and he was the ruler of the Gangaridai (the Ganges valley), whom historians identify as the Nanda king. His name sounds like Ugrasena. Alexander's soldiers faced the powerful army of Nanda But the Nanda dynasty had two kings according to the Greco-Roman tradition. Great-Padma Nanda (Porus) could come from Magadha to help Ugrasena to stop Alexander the Great if Ugrasena was from Agra (near Punjab) even if Punjab did not belong to the Nanda or Shishunaga dynasties.

Porus's nephew, also called Porus/Poros in Greek sources. He ruled a territory between the Irāvati river (in eastern India) and Asikni river (in west India). There are no reliable records about Porus in Indian texts even if Jain sources mentioned him a little indirectly. Some people have tried to develop Indian names for him later And some Indian texts have tried to say that both Ugrasena and Parashuram were names of Maha-Padma Nanda. Texts of Hinduism like Mahabharata contain tales with the names Ugrasena and Parashuram for some reasons. According to Jain texts, Nanda king (Ugrasena) was the son of a barber. According to Porus, this barber (Ugrasena's father) killed the then king with the help of the queen, and pretended to act as a guardian, and later killed the princes (in Agra or in a nearby Kingdom). Nandiwardhana was the son of King Kalashoka. He or Mahanandin was the last Shaishunaga king. Ugrasena took the Magadha kingdom from them. Mahanandin was the father of Maha-Padma Nanda. Therefore, Maha-Padma Nanda was a Kshatriya (a ruler or an excellent). We can say that Ugrasena could legally become the first Nanda king because he was Padma Nanda's nephew even if he was not a son of a king. There were nine Nanda kings, and the next eight kings were brothers (brothers or sons of Padma Nanda) of the first Nanda king (Ugrasena) according to the Buddhist texts. Something has happened to the people who spoke Prakrit languages too.

Both the Shishunaga dynasty and Nanda dynasty were affiliated with Buddhism. The Second Buddhist Council was held 100 years after the first council with the sponsorship of King Kalashoka. But the Buddhist culture in Magadha could decline after the death of the Buddhist kings in Magadha. Also, Jainism and Brahmanism could develop in Magadha with the support of Chandraguptha Maurya. Also, the weak support for Buddhism in Magadha could impact Buddhist traditions to change with influence of other traditions, and cause developing new Buddhist traditions like Mahayana Buddhist tradition. Also, some teachings in early Mahayana Buddhism (E.g. Lotus Sutra) reject some core teachings in Theravada Doctrine as if the Buddha himself rejected them. Mahayana Abhidharma Kosha was written by a Theravada scholar according to Mahayana literature. Perhaps, the developers of the early Mahayana texts didn't want to include the Abhidhamma into their Doctrine, or they didn't know Abhidhamma well. Abhidhamma Pitaka and its commentaries contain a lot of powerful and systematic teachings in Buddhism. Indians

don't really know who the Indian ruler Porus really was. A big tragedy has happened to Indian history after 321 BCE. And then, early Buddhism declined in Magadha until Ashoka the Great converted to Buddhism. The violent (Chanda) Ashoka Maurya became the Dharma Ashoka with the help of Ven. Moggaliputta Tissa Thero. But Indians don't have much details about him and early India because a lot of Indian universities and texts were destroyed by foreign invaders. A lot of Hindu religious texts were written in the later developed Sanskrit scripts. There is no evidence for a religion called Hindutva (Hinduism) or Hindu Sanatana (eternal) Dharma in early India before 1st century BCE. But Buddhist Pali texts have used the term Dhammo Sanantano to mention Buddhism. Some Sanskrit texts like Puranas and Divyavadana (including the parts like Rudrāyaṇavadāna, Ashokavadana) have later added unreliable details about the Buddha and kings because some details in them doesn't align with the early texts and archaeological proofs. E.g. According to Rudrāyaṇa-avadāna, "the Buddha gave instructions to have the first drawing of the Buddha himself send the drawing to Rudrayana. It is said that Rudrayana attained realization through seeing this picture." It is not a real Buddhist story because it doesn't align with the core teachings in Buddhism. Also, some Sanskrit texts could develop later with the influence of people who used Sanskrit and Hindi/Urdu Languages to reduce the influence of the people who used Pali and Prakrit languages. Therefore, some later developed Sanskrit texts are not reliable. Probably, the nature (behaviour) of Krishna represents the separated causality/Karma in everyone (life/Avatar) while being a part of the entire causality called Vishnu (Universe). Converting the nature of the Universe into Vishnu is like an effort to hide the truth from common people. A lot of existing Hindu texts and scripts are not older than Buddhism. Presumably, Vishnu Purana is somewhat compatible with (or based on) the causality (equilibrium) in Buddhist science. Prakrit languages existed and evolved in north and south India. The word Sanskrit literally means modified or 'con/adding/sounding done/made/making/obtained' (Sañ/Śaṅs/Saṅati Krit/Kṛta). The word Sanskaran means edition, refinement, improvement, etc. The 4th Buddhist council held in Kashmir introduced Mahayana tradition in 72 AD with texts in Sanskrit language. The 4th Buddhist council held in Sri Lanka used Pali language in between 247 to 207 BCE, and composed texts in 1st century BCE.

12.31.) If the units of used or usable Energy = $m^8.s^{-2}.kg^{-1}$, then potential energy = $kg.m^2.s^{-2}$. Potential energy = $(kg \text{ mass})^2 / (m^3 \text{ volume})^2 m^8.s^{-2}.kg^{-1}$. It indicates that potential energy contains two units of masses (kg^2) in its mass (kg) in reality. Therefore, the total mass can contain both matter and antimatter masses like this: Mass = Matter \times Antimatter.

The Proton's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Matter(59×31) \times 1.005303472855531 eV/c²?

The Down Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.023381212332223 eV/c²?

The Up Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.077816383200958 eV/c²?

The Electron's mass == Matter($59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.001387338009097 eV/c²?

Proton's Charge = $2 \times (An(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2) \times M(2)) - M(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3) \times An(3) = An(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1) \times M(1)$

But electrons don't need extra matter or antimatter to be balanced. Therefore, only protons could have a Charge.

The Muon's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.01886073187205 eV/c²?

The Tau's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(1) \times 1.000302326214752 eV/c²?

The Strange Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.051798216785732 eV/c²?

The Bottom Quark's mass == Matter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times (3 + 4)$) \times Antimatter(3) \times 1.008503859194067 eV/c²?

The Charm Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 2$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.024565750222095 eV/c²?

The Top Quark's mass == Antimatter($59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 31 \times 2 \times (3 + 4)$) \times Matter(2) \times 1.008426030527669 eV/c²?

If 1 eV/c² contains a structure with smaller units, then it would be like this:

$$1 \text{ eV}/c^2 = \text{Matter}(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3) \times \text{Antimatter}(59 \times 31) \times \text{asymmetry? It has masses like this } 1/933322239 \text{ eV}/c^2.$$

12.32.) The Electron's mass $\equiv (59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3) \times 1.001387338009097 \text{ eV}/c^2$. If we divide the Electron's mass into 510291 parts, then each part is larger than 1 eV/c² because the Electron's mass is 510998.9461 eV/c².

The asymmetry between the real and hypothetical parts / hypothetical parts $\equiv (1.001387338009097 - 1) / 510291 = 0.001387338009097 / 510291 = 2.718719336803902 \times 10^{-9} \text{ eV}/c^2$. It is like an extra mass per 1 eV/c².

The Schrodinger's wave equation doesn't use time correctly. Also, it hypothetically describes only the potential locations and probability of collapsing the electron's structure within the left and right range of its width.

Presumably, the output energy of an interaction depends on the location of it in the structure/wave of a quantum object. Detector/Observer damages a location in a quantum object, causing it to start collapsing the processes in them from that location as if appearing a quantum particle. But, the energy produced during the collapse of the structures/waves is just a reconstruction of the quantum structures/waves from the location of their damage.

Probably, quantum objects don't contain quantum sub-waves in their structures/waves. Also, the amount of energy produced at the location doesn't represent the existence of a quantum particle at that location. Therefore, the principle of least action is not applicable to the collapse of the wave function, and the probability of appearing a quantum point particle from a quantum structure/wave in Schrodinger's wave equation is just a hypothetical description of appearing energy. Modern science shouldn't depend on lies, but some people believe trending lies. Potential energy is not a massless energy. The $E=mc^2$ equation only shows a state of potential energy on speed=c.

This multiplicative representation of the Proton's mass: $\text{Antimatter}(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3) \times \text{Matter}(59 \times 31) \times 1.005303472855531 \text{ eV}/c^2$ is also similar to this additive representation of the Proton's mass: $\text{Antimatter}(31 \times 3 \times 3) \times \text{Matter}(1) \times 59 \times 31 \times 1.005303472855531$. It means that the Proton's mass contains $59 \times 31 \times 1.005303472855531$ parts of $\text{Antimatter}(31 \times 3 \times 3)$ parts and $\text{Matter}(1)$ parts. Therefore, the relationship between Matter and Antimatter in a quantum object is both additive and multiplicative. Also, the primary numbers in the representation align with it and other masses of quantum objects from more than one decimal places. An Electron would contain hidden units of Antimatter like this: $\text{Matter}(59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3) \times \text{Antimatter}(1) \times 1.001387338009097 \text{ eV}/c^2$. It explains the nature of mass better than the concept of electric fields and magnetic fields. And it shows that all the masses contain building blocks of both matter and antimatter. Also, it shows that electric charge depends on observable protons. Therefore, hidden hypothetical protons (dark matter) would have different electric charges like a hidden spectrum of electric charges. Hidden/dark quantum fields would make hidden quantum objects with relatively undetectable charges. Many types of Dark Matter nucleuses can co-exist like that.!

12.33.) The natural number $e \equiv 2.718281828459045$. The imaginary number $\sqrt{-1} = i$. Theoretically, $e^{(i2\pi)} = +1$, and $e^{(i\pi)} = -1$. If so, $e^{(i2\pi)} / e^{(i\pi)} = +1/-1$. Therefore, $e^{(i2\pi)} / e^{(i\pi)} = +e^\pi / -e^\pi = e^{(i\pi)}$.

Also, $e^{(i2\pi)} = e^{(-\pi(-2\sqrt{-1}))} = e^{(-\pi(-1 - 2\sqrt{-1} + 1))} = e^{(-\pi(\sqrt{-1} - 1)^2)}$, and $2\sqrt{-1} = -(\sqrt{-1} - 1)^2$. Therefore, $+\sqrt{-1} = \sqrt{-1} - 1$, and $+\sqrt{-1} = \sqrt{-1} - 1$, and $+\sqrt{-1} = \sqrt{-1} - 1$. If $\sqrt{-1} = i$, and $\sqrt{-1} = j$, then $i = 1 + -j\sqrt{2}$. So, if 'j' can become $\sqrt{2}$, then 'i' would become this $i = 1 + -2 = -1$. If so, the 'i' could emerge from this triangle $(+1)^2 + (-1)^2 = (\sqrt{2})^2$ like this $+1 \times -1 = -1 = i$. Therefore, $i = \sqrt{-1}$ could emerge from this triangle $(+1)^2 + (\sqrt{-1})^2 = (\sqrt{0})^2$ like this $+1 \times \sqrt{-1} = \sqrt{-1} = i$. If so, $j = \sqrt{0}$ with $+1$ and $\sqrt{-1}$ when $+1$ is not equal to $-\sqrt{-1}$, and $i = 1 + -\sqrt{0} \times \sqrt{2} = \sqrt{-1}$. So, $\sqrt{-1} - 1 = +-\sqrt{(0 \times 2)} = +-\sqrt{(0+0)} = \sqrt{-1} - 1$. It is like an emergence of dimensions from nothing with the continuation of time.

12.34.) Dependent origination (pratītyasamutpadā/ paṭiccasamuppāda) is the Buddha's teaching on causality and the process of life. The basic principle in it is "if this exists, that exists; if this ceases to exist, that also ceases to exist". We can put the 12 links in the chain of dependent origination into 3 moments (Khana) in a Chittakhana like this:

1st moment/Khana: i. Avijjā/Avidyā (nescience/asymmetry), ii. Saṅkhāra/Saṃskāra (energy/volitional formations).
 2nd moment/Khana: iii. Viññāṇa/Vijñāna (oppositely made knowing), iv. Nāma-Rūpa (emotional-material actions),
 v. Saḷāyatana/Ṣaḍāyatana (six sense bases/sources), vi. Phassa/Sparśa (contact/touch), vii. Vedanā (feeling/sensation)
 viii. (the builder of Saṃsāra/re-becoming/rebirth) Taṇhā/Tṛṣṇā (wish/desire-attachment), 2nd or 3rd moment/Khana:
 ix. Upādāna (clinging/grasping), x. Bhava (become/behave/continue) (the origin of ‘that is a part of this/me’ nature).
 3rd moment/Khana: xi. Jāti (generation/regeneration), xii. Jarāmaṇa (decay-death/break).

Time could be the first cause that changed nothingness into many points of nothingness. The entire universe was a thing even if it was infinitely nothing, and nothingness continued with time. Therefore, the entire universe has a first cause. The formation of Citta (energy-process) could happen in many different ways, and a special formation of energy/Citta could have a potential to become a clinging/Upādāna during the start of that process. A very small amount of Citta (energy-process) could make generations of Citta like living beings. Life could start with a very unique formation of Citta from the infinite potentiality of formations of Citta with many relationships and reactions (Kammaja/reactional potentials) during the first formation of energy and matter. The continuation of some generations of Citta (rebirth/re-becoming) could repeat observing its clings/relations (Upādāna) like a cyclic process (Saṃsāra), and it could start with the first formation of the universe itself. The 12 links in the chain of dependent origination contain the reasons to make a process like a rebirth/re-becoming of a Citta in itself (Upādāna/clinging, Bhava/Becoming, Jāti/generation, Jarāmaṇa/decay-death), and it happens within a mind/Citta-moment (Chittakhana). Therefore, dependent origination could start a unique Citta with a potential to become a life from the first formation of matter and Citta an uncountable time ago even if it is experimentally unverifiable by anyone. According to the Buddha, he doesn't mention assumptions and unobserved details about the process of energy and the universe. Also, Tipitaka doesn't reject the idea of the first formation of the universe. Science can't change ultimate truths because science is only an explanation of truths. The noble research called Arya Paryeshana is the research about ultimate truths of life (the four noble truths). Ultimate truth/Sacca is true science. Modern science doesn't mention ultimate truths. Therefore, modern science is more technological than scientific.

12.35.) If the ultimate units for Energy (E) is $\text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^8 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$, then the ultimate units for Ampere (A) must be $\text{kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Similarly, the ultimate units for coulomb (C) must be $\text{kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6}$.

The units of the polarization of material quality called Permittivity is farad/m = $F/m = C/(V \cdot m)$. Therefore, the derived units for farad (F) = $C/V = C/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3} \cdot \text{A}^{-1}) = (\text{kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6} \times \text{kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6} \cdot \text{s}^{-1})/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}) = \text{kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-17} \cdot \text{s}^2$. So, the ultimate units for farad/m = $\text{kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-18} \cdot \text{s}^2$.

The units of the electrical inductance called henry (H) = $(\text{s}^2)/\text{farad} = (\text{s}^2)/(\text{kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-17} \cdot \text{s}^2) = \text{kg}^{-3} \cdot \text{m}^{17}$. So, the derived units for henry/m = $\text{kg}^{-3} \cdot \text{m}^{16}$.

Seemingly, the units of farad (F) and henry (H) show a shared symmetry between mass, time, and distance.

If the ultimate units of force = $E/\text{distance} = \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^7 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$, then the ultimate units of momentum = $\text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^7 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

If a mass = a kg, then its ultimate mass-volume = $\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$.

The standard speed of light (c) = $299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Theoretically, $\epsilon_0 = 1/(\mu_0 \times c^2) = e^2/(2\alpha hc)$. Therefore, the speed of light (c) = $1/\sqrt{(\epsilon_0 \times \mu_0)}$ when the vacuum permittivity (ϵ_0) = $8.8541878128 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m} = 55.26349406 \text{ e}^2 \cdot \text{eV}^{-1} \cdot \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and vacuum permeability (μ_0) = $4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ H/m} = 1.25663706212 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N} \cdot \text{A}^{-2}$ with the relationship of elementary charge ($e = 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$), Fine-structure constant ($\alpha = e^2/hc$ when $4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1$, or the measurement $e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0 hc) = 0.0072973525693$), and the Planck constant ($h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{Hz}^{-1} = 2\pi\hbar$). We can use it to mention the momentum (p) of light like this: $(\text{volume1} \times \text{volume2})/(\text{mass} \times \sqrt{(\epsilon_0 \times \mu_0)}) = ((\text{volume1} \times \text{volume2})/\text{mass}) \times 336066.8188579496 \times 892.062057833577 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = ((\text{volume1} \times \text{volume2})/\text{mass}) \times e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar \alpha) = 299\,792\,458 \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^7 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

Therefore, the Fine-structure constant (α) = $((\text{volume1} \times \text{volume2})/\text{mass}) \times e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar \times 299\,792\,458 \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^7 \cdot \text{s}^{-1})$. So, the derived units of the fine-structure constant (α) = $((\text{m}^3 \times \text{m}^3)/\text{kg}) \times (\text{kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6})^2 / (\text{kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-18} \cdot \text{s}^2 \times \text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^7 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = \text{m}^6 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \times \text{kg}^4 \cdot \text{m}^{-12} / (\text{kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-9}) = \text{m}^3$. If $1/\sqrt{(\epsilon_0 \times \mu_0)} = e^2/(2\epsilon_0\hbar\alpha)$, then $1 = (e^2 \times \sqrt{\mu_0})/(2\hbar\alpha \times \sqrt{\epsilon_0})$. Therefore, $2\hbar\alpha \times (\sqrt{\epsilon_0} / \sqrt{\mu_0}) = e^2$. So, $e^2 = 2 \times 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \times (2.975598731818523 \times 10^{-6} / 1.120998243584708 \times 10^{-3}) \text{ kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-17} \cdot \text{s} = 2.5669699665 \times 10^{-38} \text{ kg}^4 \cdot \text{m}^{-12}$. So, $e = \pm 1.602176633 \times 10^{-19} \text{ kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6} = \pm 1.602176633 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$. Also, $e = \pm \sqrt{(2\hbar\alpha \times (\sqrt{\epsilon_0} / \sqrt{\mu_0}))} = \pm \sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{(\hbar\alpha(\sqrt{\epsilon_0} / \sqrt{\mu_0}))} = \pm \sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{(6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \times 2.654418727993014 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-17} \cdot \text{s})} = \pm \sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{(6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg}^2 \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^{-6} \times 2.654418727993014 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-6})}$. Therefore, $\sqrt{e} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{2} \times 2.574115411165552 \times 10^{-17} \text{ kg} \times 0.085424543131936 \text{ m}^{-3} \times 5.152105130908155 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3})} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{2})} \times (5.073574096399452 \times 10^{-9} \text{ kg} \times 0.2922747733416895 \times 0.2269824911949852 \text{ m}^{-3}) = 5.073574096399452 \times 10^{-9} \text{ kg} \times 0.078893493851475 \text{ m}^{-3} = \pm 4.002719867789901 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$. Probably, it shows the density of mass in elementary charge. $\epsilon_0 \times \mu_0 = 1/c^2$. And $\epsilon_0 = 1/(\mu_0 \times c^2) = e^2/(2\alpha\hbar c)$. Also, $e^2/(2\alpha\hbar c) \times \mu_0 = 1/c^2$. So, $e^2/(2\alpha\hbar) \times \mu_0 = 1/c$. Therefore, the speed of light (c) = $2\alpha\hbar/(e^2 \times \mu_0) = 2\alpha\hbar/((\pm 4.002719867789901 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3})^4 \times 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg}^{-3} \cdot \text{m}^{16}) = 2\alpha\hbar \times \text{kg}^{-1}/((\pm 4.002719867789901 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3})^4 \times 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg}^{-4} \cdot \text{m}^{16}) = 2\alpha\hbar \times \text{kg}^{-1}/(\pm 4.002719867789901 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \times 3.34813118512341 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^4)^4 = 2\alpha\hbar \times \text{kg}^{-1}/(\pm 1.34016312146604 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m})^4$. If it is correct, then the ultimate units of the fine-structure constant (α) = $\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$. Therefore, the ultimate units for henry/m = $\text{kg}^{-4} \cdot \text{m}^{16}$.

Therefore, if the fine-structure constant (α) = $0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$, then the speed of light (c) = $2\alpha\hbar/(\pm 1/74617782267.13726 \text{ m})^4 = 2\alpha\hbar \times (74617782267.13726)^4/(\pm 1 \text{ m})^4 = 2\alpha\hbar \times 31.0005463964765 \times 10^{42}/(\pm 1 \text{ m})^4$. Surprisingly, it contains a number closer to 31. Probably, the speed of light (c) = $2\alpha\hbar \times 31 \times 1.00001762569279 \times 10^{42} / (\pm 1 \text{ m})^4 = 2 \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \times 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 31.0005463964765 \times 10^{42} / (1 \text{ m}^4) = 2 \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \times 2.05411795111383 \times 10^{10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} / (1 \text{ m}^4) = 2 \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \times 2 \times 1.027058975556915 \times 10^{10} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} / (1 \text{ m}^4) = 299792458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Probably, the fine-structure constant depends on the speed of light, or the speed of light depends on the fine-structure constant if the other constants must finally become closer to primary numbers naturally. E.g, Number 31. The speed of light (c) \times The Planck time = $2 \times 0.0072973525693 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \times 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 31.0005463964765 \times 10^{42} \times 5.391247 \times 10^{-44} \text{ s} / (1 \text{ m}^4) = 0.5213634527692112 \times 10^{-78} \text{ m} \times 31.0005463964765 \times 10^{42} = 0.5213726421612618 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m} \times 31 = 16.16255190699912 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m} = 1.010159494187445 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m} \times 16 = \text{The Planck length}$. Likely, the Planck length contains 31 smaller parts of $0.5213726421612618 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m}$ lengths or 32 smaller parts of $0.5050797470937225 \text{ m}$ lengths or 16 smaller parts of $1.010159494187445 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m}$ lengths.

The Planck length = $0.5213726421612618 \times 10^{-36} \text{ m} \times 31 = 7.144682091347473 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m} \times 31 \times 137.0359990836958$. Presumably, the speed of light (c) = $31 \times 137.0359990836958 \times (16.2988170397189)^4$, or the speed of light (c) = $2 \times 137.0359990836958 \times (32.33992506500494)^4 = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Therefore, the Planck length = $2 \times (1/\alpha) \times (32.33992506500494)^4 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 5.391247 \times 10^{-44} \text{ s} = 2 \times (1/\alpha) \times 137.0359990836958 \times 5897191.984249232 \times 10^{-44} \text{ m} = 2 \times (1/\alpha) \times 5897191.984249232 \times 10^{-44} \text{ m}$. Likely, the speed of light is a quantum jump like this: $2 \times 137.0359990836958 \times 5897191.984249232 \times 10^{-44} \text{ m} / (5.391247 \times 10^{-44} \text{ s})$. If so, the Planck length is not the smallest length, and it contains 299 792 458 smallest lengths of the smallest $5.391247 \times 10^{-44} \text{ m}$ length. **The speed of light (c)** = $2 \times 5897191.984249232 \times 10^{-44} \text{ m} \times 25.41823794823272 \times 10^{44} \text{ s}^{-1} = 2 \times 149896229.0820576 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times 0.0072973525693 \times 20541179511.1383$

$m.s^{-1} = 2 \times \alpha \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 / 2.053462101245351 m.s^{-1} = 2.000638774748345 \times \alpha \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 / 2.05411795111383 m.s^{-1} = 299\ 792\ 458 m.s^{-1}$. It shows that the fine-structure constant (α) must become a primary number or the smallest time must change to remove the fine-structure constant if the other numbers are closer to correct and fixed smallest primary numbers. Therefore, **$c = 41082358999.78691 \times m.s^{-1}$** .

The capacity of a second changes with the modification of the Planck time (5.391247×10^{-44} as), and it converts the Planck constant (h) into this value: $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \times 137.0359990836958 kg.m^2.as^{-1} = 908.0101430039041 \times 10^{-34} kg.m^2.as^{-1} = 3.141903609010048 \times 17 \times 17 \times 10^{-34} kg.m^2.as^{-1}$. If the number 17 in it is a radius (r) and 3.141903609010048 is similar to π , then the ultimate Planck constant has its building blocks like this: $\pi r^2 \times 1.00009898018443 \times 10^{-34} kg.m^2.as^{-1} = \pi(17 \times 10^{-17})^2 \times 1.00009898018443 kg.m^2.as^{-1}$. It shows a beam of matter like a material cylinder with approximately a $17 \times 10^{-17}m$ radius. Likely, it indicates a cyclic movement of fundamental matter and energy. The Pali word Nirodha means the end of suffering, but it (Ni+Rodha) also means 'no obstruction/prevention'. Presumably, the mind is trapped in a cyclic movement.

12.36.) Idealism is not a Theravada fundamental. The creator of separation is Citta, and it exists everywhere. Matter has a lifetime, and matter makes matter while hosting the stream of creation called Citta-Vithi. Similarly, emotional actions/needs can make informational (subjective) actions or structures. Everything would contain actions like Citta-Vithi. All the Chitta-Vithies are processes in matter or processes in informational (subjective) higher planes, and some Chitta-Vithies continue like living processes due to some unique root causes. Presumably, speed is the essence of everything. If so, idealism is just an output of speeds like awareness of speeds. Material actions could emerge from interactions of speeds. The flow of time could make speeds, and the speed of speed could continue existence like the most fundamental process of everything. Also, a material action is just an action without any consistent material essence/substance that continues to the next moment. Therefore, both material and emotional actions can behave like volitional (intentional) formations with predetermined goals to achieve with or without an individual desire. If an action depends on unavoidable bodily intentions, then we can use effort (Viriya) and views (Ditti) to reduce the speed of habitual actions. If the mind needs to think about an unwanted thing, depending on some unavoidable previous intentions or habitual actions, then the mind can think about it to be satisfied without a need to use the body to take actions to do the same. If the five senses are craving for pleasure, then the mind can avoid enjoying it. Abhidhamma mentions many characteristics of matter (Rūpa) such as Granthanee (bindingness like a book), Oghanee (pullness to the bottom like gravity), and Yoganee (usingness like a hosting energy). Also, matter can host or friendly with the influence of addictions (passion/Kāma, behave/Bhava, uneducated/Avijjā Āsava) and views (Diṭṭhi Āsava) and other emotional requirements. According to the Buddha, the cessation/healing (of Āsava / influence / addictions and Taṇhā / greed / wish/desire-attachment) is the utmost pleasure (Nibbana Paramam Sukham). And Taṇhā arises together with Dukkha (stress/ depression/ unease). Habitual (wished/desired) attachments (addictions) reduce when we are prepared to stop giving good (Subha) identifications (Nimithi) to imaginary (conceptual/unreal) material qualities like beautifulness (colors), rareness, movingness, and sadness etc. Presumably, subjects and objects are results of many types of actions and interactions between points of emptiness, and the movements of objects and the other material qualities we experience are just illusions. Dependent cessation or disappearing/leaving/unbinding (Anicca) nature and dependent origination (duality) nature emphasizes the nature of not-self (Anatta). Therefore, attractions/addictions (loving/lovely things) are meaningless in the path of liberation. The middle way applies to pain and pleasure. We can try to limit those feelings to develop equanimity and wisdom. Some attachments become strong when the mind tries to protect them/things. We can give all the things to others mentally to let go. Giving (Daana) helps to develop virtue (Sila) and meditation (Bhavana). Humans have to tame the body to liberate the mind due to our short life-span. Buddhism contains eternal truths of this cyclic universe.

According to Buddhism, the people who can attain the mental power called Abhiññā (higher knowledge) can access some details of past incidents like accessing the past through a straight line. Also, the past structures have a potential to impact present structures due to some ways of dependents in 24 ways of dependents called Suvisi Pratyaya explained in Abhidhamma. Newly originated smallest material structures (new Rupa-Kalapa) are smaller than the previous structures. Presumably, new structures appear between the existing structures like sending the existing structures to the past (become matter-intentions like Rupasancetana) while dependently originating relatively smaller structures. Some structures of the past would survive like long distance quantum entanglements with a less ability to interact with new structures. But if a point of existence doesn't split in the next moment when it re-originate like a conversion, then the next moment can make new gaps/entanglements and fillings around it like splitting the previous entanglements and fillings. Therefore, the splitted lines of connections are smaller, and make new space for the point to grow and interact with other points. If so, energy conservation is not the only method of surviving the information of the past, and existing energy would become information of the past while originating new energy. Asymmetry in matter could become energy like the formation of energy/speeds called Sanskara before emerging the awareness called Vinnana. Awareness emerges from Sanskara. Therefore, idealism is not the beginning. The future doesn't exist, but sometimes the future is predictable. Theravada fundamentals and explanations are highly interconnected to each other in highly systematic and derivable ways. E.g, If the Avinibboga (the inseparable matter unit) mentioned in Abhidhamma is a smallest Matter-Zone (Rupa-Kalapa), then an Ashtaka (eight) Kalapa contains 8 connected Avinibboga Kalapas. If those eight Kalapas exist one after another with 17 Citta-moments for each (17x8), then it contains 136 Citta-moments. 137 or 1/137 are unexplained numbers in quantum mechanics, and 1/137 is called the fine-structure constant. 136 can have a relationship to 1/137. The unit of Navaka (nine) Kalapa contains 9 smallest Kalapas. Seemingly, the difference between them is just like an increase of the wavelength of a quantum object.

12.37.) According to Abhidhamma, the intention called Cetanā/Chethana is like a decision or a destination, and it is not a choice because a choice depends on a wish (Chanda) or a like (wish-attachment). The pure wish to attain enlightenment/Nibbana is a skillful wish (Kusala-Chanda). Fully enlightened (Arhant) people don't love, hate, like, or dislike something or someone intentionally, but they use words like help/care, prevent/disagree, allow/agree, recommend/authorize, etc. The Pali word Metta is used in a mental factor like empathy, and it is not like loving. The word 'love' can be used to make attachments. Paṭicca Smuppāda (Paṭi/resistance/return ichcha/like/love/attachment Smuppāda/co-origination) literally mentions a resistance/return (Paṭi/Anti) with wish-attachment (Chanda-Rāga or Taṇhā/like). Some attachments like additions can make the mind uncomfortable, and insist the mind to make bodily actions. Some reactions (Karmic actions) are collective intentions/consciousnesses/entanglements with the support of spiritual faculties and the network (tree) of knowledge. Mentality bends action/Karma in somewhat unpredictable ways like an infinitely large number removes another infinitely large number to make 1, 0 or -1/12, preventing superdeterminism. The mind and some other senses directly depend on Karma, but hearing is a direct observation of the hearing sense according to Abhidhamma. Therefore, I think listening to Satipatthana meditations from morning to evening is the easiest way to ignore the uncontrollable forces of Karma. Listening to mindfulness-consistent (Satipatthana) meditations help to reduce the idea of self and clinging. Also, the mind needs strength to gain a deep sleep quickly without using external influences or tiredness. We can use a mind-training method like thinking of a pattern of numbers like 1 to 100 around two times before trying to stop thinking. The mouth (Mukha) of liberation (Vimokṣa-Mukha) called Appanīhita (no-appetite or no-tasteful-aim) is a result of being selfless or disappointed about nature without the feeling of sadness or anger. Realizing zero-ness or emptiness (Suññata) from no-meaning or no-one-self (Anatta) while leaving time, no-sign or no-identify (Animitta) from unliking or discontinuing (Anicca) while having equanimity/no-feeling-aim, or no-appetite (Appanīhita) from pain/dual-feelings (Dukka) while being selfless and conceptually disappointed about the fearful process of nature (Nāmarūpa) without the feeling of sadness or anger, is the end goal to enter to the stream of liberation. The word Anicca sounds like unliking or discontinuing.

Anicca Lakkhana is like an action in a moment that discontinues itself without a feeling with a not-continuing nature like a dependent cessation in between existence (co-origination/duality/Dukka) and non-existence (Anatta nature).

Recognition/memory (Saññā) makes the mind with knowingness, depending on faculties. We are like robots with minds/knowingnesses and 52 ultimate mental factors based on 28 ultimate material forms and spiritual faculties. Presumably, the recognition (Sanggnā) in the mind is like a new recognition of a previous cognition/non-cognition. Leaving time is a way to understand zero-ness/emptiness (Sunnata/Shunyata). Many colors (lights) emerge (Upādā) depending on blackness (darkness) and dependent recognition (fabrication/co-creation) with the recognition of time/relationship (feedback/entanglement/cognition) by some streams of creation called Citta-Vithi. If the Citta had a beginning, then it could begin due to a potential to make a full recognition from a state of a subtle cognition like 'no-recognition-no-non-recognition' like the state of the mind in the 'Nevasaññānāsaññā' Arūpa/immateral plane. The twenty four dependents called Suvisi Prathya connect the mind moments, including material actions. The arising and dissolving moments of the mind/Citta (Vinnana) can have connections to unconscious continuation of knowing (Gnana). Usually, causality is compatible with past, present, and future, depending on the 6 root causes: greed, anger, delusion, no-greed, no-anger, and no-delusion. Likely, causality takes (being/like/get) the state of mind. Interdependence of material and mental actions is provable. Probably, collective intentions have impacted the results we experience. So, influences and awareness have a potential to continue due to our entanglements and attachments.

12.38.) Points of emptiness could emerge due to continuation of time because a point of nothingness can't be a constant. A separation of a point of nothingness can make 3 points of nothingness in each direction with the first one in the middle due to the necessity of ultimate time that a point of nothingness necessarily experiences. The illusory relative time could emerge due to the necessity to make separations and relationships because relative time is a result of the ultimate time that necessarily made separations and relationships. And the relationships between points of nothingness could make emptiness. Interdependent emergence is a necessity of nature. Also, Abhidhamma Pitaka and Theravada commentaries systematically explain the doctrine of necessity in nature. Time separates everything. Therefore, the separation of a point of nothingness into 3 points of nothingness between 2 opposite directions is a necessity. And then, the separation of those 3 points of nothingness into 7 points of nothingness is also a necessity. It can continue until it can relatively disappear. The 3rd separation can make 15 points of nothingness. A single point of nothingness has mathematical potential to make around 4 separations like this: $(+0-0)^6 = ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+-0.00001)$. Therefore, 4 separations can happen between two opposite directions, and a point of nothingness necessarily can make direct relationships with 3 to 31 points of nothingness during its lifetime. The growth of separations in a point of nothingness/emptiness itself can be an action of existence and entanglement. 'Knowing' quality is a necessity to create a separation/contact/spark (Phassa) quality, and it must originate due to the inconsistent nature of everything. But knowing is only an individual quality in nature that must coexist with others. The quality of knowing and causality have a potential to create subtle/unconscious and conscious states of knowing. The knowing-quality originates with states of contact-quality, making levels of knowing and Re-knowing (Vinnana). The recognition of time can change. But absolute time is the smallest moment (Khana) and relative time is a process. The moment called Khana is like a conversion of the near past into the near future, to be the present moment/Khana. The interdependent connections of a Khana/Kshana with the past and the future are the Suvisi/24 Prathya/dependents. The knowing-quality can connect the past to the future while originating (Paccuppanna) the present moment/Khana.!

12.39.) If the group of matter (17×8) called Attaka Kalapa (Eight Zones) separates it from another group of matter with a (1) gap like this $17 \times 8 + 1 + 17 \times 8 = 136 + 1 + 136$, then those groups of matter would make a constant like this $(136 + 1 + 136)/2 = 136.5$. If the ultimate fine-structure constant = $1/136.5$, then the maximum speed of light = $41082358999.78691/136.5 = \text{m.s}^{-1} = 300969663.0021019 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$. The difference between those speeds =

300969663.0021019 / 299 792 458 = 1.003926733213889%. Therefore, the resistance in vacuum space =
 $(0.003926733213889 / 299\ 792\ 458\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}) \times 1.616255 \times 10^{-35}\ \text{m} = 1.309817211575416 \times 10^{-11}\ \text{s}\cdot\text{m}^{-1} \times$
 $1.616255 \times 10^{-35}\ \text{m} = 2.116998617294824 \times 10^{-46}\ \text{seconds per Planck length} = 1.55091473794493 \times 10^{-48} \times$
 $136.5\ \text{s/Planck length?}$. Perhaps, the Planck length would contain a length like this 136.5×2 in ultimately smaller
lengths. If so, $1.55091473794493 \times 10^{-48} \times (1/2) \times 2 \times 136.5\ \text{s/Planck length} = (0.775457368972465 \times 10^{-48} \times \text{s}$
 $/(\text{Planck length}/273)) \times (0.0072973525693/\alpha) = (5.6587858238538 \times 10^{-51}\ \text{s}/\alpha) /(\text{Planck length}/273)$. But the 273
lengths in that Planck length must contain 3 smaller/smallest points of resistance: $(16.9763574715614 \times 10^{-51}\ \text{s}/3\alpha)$
 $/(\text{Planck length}/273)$. It shows on average 17 resistances at some points of existence: $(16.9763574715614 \times 10^{-51} \times$
 $1.003926733213889\ \text{s}136.5/3) /(\text{Planck length}/273) = (17.04301909829583 \times 10^{-51}\ \text{s}136.5/3) /(\text{Planck length}/273)$.
The change between those resistances = $(17.0430190 - 16.9763574) \times 10^{-51} = 0.066661 \times 10^{-51} = (1/15.001) \times 10^{-51}$.
If the speed of light (c) = $2 \times 1.000319386826568 \times \alpha \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 / 2.05411795111383\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} =$
 $2 \times 1.000319386826568 \times 0.0072973525693 / 2.05411795111383\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times (1/(31 \times 101) + 1) \times$
 $1.00000000049165 \times 0.0072973525693 / 2.05411795111383\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times 1.00000000049165 \times (1 /$
 $(31 \times 101 \times 281.4881056666379) + (1 / 281.4881056666379))\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times 1.00000000049165 \times (1$
 $/ (31 \times 101 \times 31 \times 9 \times 1.008917941457484) + (1 / 281.4881056666379))\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times$
 $1.00000000049165 \times (1 / (101 \times 1.008917941457484) + (31 \times 31 \times 9 / 281.4881056666379)) / (31 \times 31 \times 9)$
 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times 1.00000000049165 \times (0.00981347411139 + 30.72598744276207) / (31 \times 31 \times 9)$
 $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 2 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3)\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} = 299\ 792$
 $458\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, then $2 \times 1.000319386826568 \times \alpha / 2.05411795111383 = 2 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3)$.
Therefore, the fine-structure constant (α) = $2.05411795111383 \times 30.73580091838459 / (31 \times 31 \times 3 \times 3 \times$
 $1.000319386826568) = 2.05411795111383 / (31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.008917941457483) = 6.62607015 \times$
 $0.310005463964765 / (31 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1.008917941457483) = 6.62607015 / (3 \times 3 \times 100.8900158893226) =$
 $6.62607015 / 908.0101430039034 = 6.62607015 / (17 \times 17 \times 3.141592653589793238 \times 1.000098980184429) =$
6.62607015 / (1.000098980184429 $\times \pi \times 17^2$) = 0.0072973525693.

Probably, the speed of light has relationships to fundamental building blocks with **101, 59, 31, 17, 3, 2** units and the
Planck constant **6.62607015** $\times 10^{-34}\ \text{J}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1}$, including a collection of 6 smallest matter units like this:
 $16+1+16+1+16+1+16+1+16+1+16$ Triples = 101 Triples. A smallest matter unit would become strong within 15
triple moments (Chittakhana) before ending its lifetime with a connection to another matter unit during 16th and
17th Triples (triple moments). Two connected streams of smallest matter units = $15+2+14$ Triples = $[15+(1+1)+14]$
Triples = 31 Triples. So, 4 connected streams of matter units = $14+1+1+1+12+1+1+12+1+1+1+13$ Triples = $14 +$
 $1 \times 8 + 12 \times 2 + 13 = 59$ Triples. Perhaps, 8 connected streams of matter units = $14 + 1 \times 18 + 12 \times 6 + 13 = 117$ Triples.

12.40.) The fine-structure constant (α) = $e^2/\hbar c\ \text{J}\cdot\text{m}$ when $4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1$, and if $\alpha = 6.62607015 / (1.000098980184429 \times$
 $\pi \times 17^2)$, then $e^2/\hbar c\ \text{J}\cdot\text{m} = 2\pi e^2/\hbar c\ \text{J}\cdot\text{m} = 6.62607015 / (1.000098980184429 \times \pi \times 17^2)$. So, $c = (e^2 \times$
 $1.000098980184429 \times \pi^2 \times 17^2\ \text{J}\cdot\text{m}) / (6.62607015 \times \hbar) = (e^2 \times 1.000098980184429 \times \pi^2 \times 17^2$
 $\text{J}\cdot\text{m}) \times 10^{-34}\ \text{J}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1} / (\hbar^2)$. Therefore, $\sqrt{c} = (e \times 1.00004948886764 \times \pi \times 17 \times 10^{-17}\ \text{J}\sqrt{(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1})}) / (2\pi\hbar) = (e$
 $\times 1.00004948886764 \times 17 \times 10^{-17}\ \text{J}\sqrt{(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1})}) / (2\hbar) = (17e \times 1.00004948886764 \times 10^{-17}\ \text{J}\sqrt{(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1})}) / (2 \times$
 $1.054571817 \times 10^{-34}\ \text{J}\cdot\text{s}) = (17e \times 1.00004948886764 \sqrt{(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1})}) / (2.109143634 \times 10^{-17}\ \text{s}) =$
 $(8.0601433330358e \times 1.00004948886764 \sqrt{(\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1})}) / (10^{-17}\ \text{s})$. If so, $c = 8.060542220402368 \times 10^{17}$
 $\text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2} = 299\ 792\ 458\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} \times 2.688707472555019 \times 10^8\ \text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = 299\ 792\ 458\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} \times (e \times$
 $10^8 / 1.010999469524263)\ \text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = 296\ 530\ 776.7580439\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} \times e \times 10^8\ \text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} =$
 $1.090875764438829 \times e \times 10^8\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1} \times e \times 10^8\ \text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = 10908757644388290 \times e^2\ \text{m}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. If
so, the relative frequency $\text{Hz} = 10908757644388290 \times e^2\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2} / (299\ 792\ 458\ \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1})$. So, $1\ \text{s}\cdot\text{Hz} =$
 $36387698.73386304 \times e^2 = e^2 \times 3.002939231889109 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59$. It is like a cyclic stream of timely
resistances in light at the speed of light.

12.41.) According to Buddhism, the body feels resistance (Pati/anti-quality) when the mind feels a like (Ichcha/itch) towards something (same object). It is a co-origination. It means, each and every like (wish-attachment) in the mind makes a resistance in the body. The body returns the resistance (anti-like) to the mind by a pain like an anger to a lost love/thing. We can reduce the painful feelings of attachments by being kind to the things/actions we liked while ignoring them without resistance. Presumably, our mental attachments make connected gaps in the body like unfilled lines of entanglements. According to Buddhism, 'believing that this is the truth for sure' (Idan Sachchabhivivesa) without understanding the truth correctly is a wrong belief that makes bodily bindings (Kaya Grantha). Bodily bindings like 'believing a true (eternal) self-body' (Sakkaya Ditthi, strong false beliefs/views/Ditthi, beliefs) and believing that 'I must respect/protect/do this practice/habit as a respect to others' (Silabbatha Paramasa) must be removed to attain liberation (Nibbana). If a person doesn't want to do anything next/more for personal existence in a time, then that person is not late (reduces the fear of non-existence of a self) in that time. The people who have removed those beliefs/views (Ditthi) become stream-enterers (Sothapanna). The fully-enlightened people/Arhants are not believers of beliefs (Ditthi). The Gautama Bodhisattva decided to stop doing anything for himself (let his behaviour/Bhava/Action stop) before attaining the Buddhahood. Doer (Behaviour/Bhava) makes generation/birth (Jaathi). Unpredictable behaviour/Bhava is the main difference between life and lifelessness. The behaviour/reaction of attachment can be reduced (by ignoring seeing, hearing, smelling, tasting, touching, thinking) to reduce clinging (Upadana) and mental attachment (Raaga/Thanha, Emotional hunger/thirst/high-ego/low-ego). Siddhartha Gautama Bodhisattva fell many times (around 3 times) as if he lost his life. That is like a meditation to practice lifelessness. Asymmetric Karma (influences/Asava of ignorance/Avijja) would be somewhat neutral when the mind stops/ignores itself and breathing for a while, as if the body and the universe must adjust the forces of Karma to support the non-existence of the unpredictable mind. The lord Buddha didn't encourage removing body parts to reduce craving. But awareness is ignorable to let go. The lord Buddha said, "I'll not come back." So, we can think like that to prevent us from expecting unarisen (future) aggregates/Name-Form (Anuppanna Khanda). Strong attachments can be reduced by being extremely kind to the object of attachment while remembering the people who can protect that object, like kindly recognizing/imagining the protectors of that extremely important thing/action to let it go mentally.

The Gautama Bodhisattva reduced his craving to live/behave (Bhava Tanha) while reducing his fear of death/Mara. If someone says to the entire causality and Karma that "I don't try to take any action to protect the body now", then the mind would shake the flow of the causality and Karma, causing the mind to receive a fear (Mara/Moha/delusion) of death/Mara. It can help to remove the fear of losing life without a doubt to be stream-enterers (Sotapanna arjans). A yogi can stop doing anything for a while to understand that no one (Mara) is waiting to stop it without my support. When someone stops thinking and doing anything, memory (Sati/Sith/thoughts) gets the mind like Mara who waits to live/behave. A trained memory (Samma Sati) can be transformed into a reminder (a transformed Mara) that waits to die. Right view/education (Samma Ditthi) is like an observed/pre knowledge (Prajna). Right speech, right action, and right livelihood are like 3 avoiding or 3 anti-resisting (Virati or Vi+rati) qualities of some mental factors. The smallest moment of a concept (Sankappa) is a review, like an investigation (Vitakka). Similarly, some conventional truths depend on absolute/ultimate truths/meanings of causality. Therefore, modern science shouldn't try to remove mental actions from science to hide the causality of mental actions to ignore scientific facts like destiny and Kamma. Some people have used techniques (E.g, symbolism) to save their knowledge from relatively educated competitors. English and some other languages are closer to Pali and Sanskrit words/sounds. E.g, Amen is like no-me-in (Anatta). Intentional memorisation depends on memories of knowledge and experiences. But the analytical mind-set is helpful to allow memories to come into the mind spontaneously with counter arguments. The attachments to the previously identified objects can be reduced by removing the previous reviews (Vitakka) about them to reduce identifications. The things and actions we observe at a moment don't belong to any previous observer. Dualities in causality make

causality a garbage where the mind can bend good and bad results with a lot of effort without an ability to control it. Causality depends on emotions, and demands sacrifices. It can be reduced by waiting to respond/react effortlessly. Bodily attractions and resistances of attachments can be reduced by being emotionally kind to the things/actions we are attached to, while being emotionally kind to the things/actions we do correctly to reduce the resistance against it. The understanding about the process of emotional and bodily causality helps to prevent us trying to own the body.

The freedom from emotional identity (ego) would not help for competitive businesses/jobs, but it helps the mind. Forced dualities have qualities like high-ego, low-ego, Uddacca (upper-like), Kukkucca (lower-like), male, female. A linear/repeated/continuous observation is a review/investigation/learning/education (Vitakka) that can differentiate observations as if converting basic qualities like blackness (darkness) into colors (light) while leaning to the paths of materials to fill the gaps/entanglements of the mind. The observations of the six senses are like filling unfilled gaps. Many different sets of knowledge would originate on lengths and entanglements of linear observations of the mind. Around 7 or 11 main types of interactions of the mind (Citta) and mental (Nama) actions with the material (Rupa) interactions would asymmetrically bend the paths of materials, causing the mind and mental actions to conserve the asymmetry of interactions by transforming the basic qualities (blackness, tastelessness, silent, smell-less, feelingless, noncognition) of existence into extra qualities like 7 or 11 main colors, tunes, tastes, smells, feelings, cognitions, etc. Dark colors would become bright colors due to continuous higher densities of light waves/nets in the mind-streams. The contact/touch (Passa/Sparsha) quality originates between material zones (Rupa Kalapa) due to new basic/extra quality like a sense (Pasada Rupa) and aligned quality/object. The causality would make lifeless states of knowing (Pure Gnana) with lifeless emotional (Nama) and material (Rupa) actions, lifeless senses, and lifeless contact/touch. Seemingly, the 12 links of dependent origination show similar actions in different names. E.g, 1-Avijja (unlearning) is like an unconscious knowing/upbringing (a bodily knowing/upbringing). 3-Vingnana (Re-knowing) is a conscious (lifely) knowing/upbringing. 9-Upadana (clinging/upbringing) is like an unconscious strong knowing/upbringing (an unconscious belief). Similarly, 2-Sanskara (formation/interacting) is like a set of 4-actions/Namarupa. 4-Namarupa (Name-form) are a set of actions/Namarupa. 11-Jati (generation/rebirth) is like a set of actions/Namarupa. Also, 2-Sanskara (formation/interacting) is like a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara. 4-Namarupa (Name-form) is like a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara. 12-Jara-marana (decay-death) is a 12-separation/decay-death/Mara.

Re-knowing-aggregates (Vingnanakhanda) contain 81 basic creations/ways of Re-knowing. Probably, those 81 main types of Re-knowing depend on the 28 Rupa aggregates (material qualities+actions), 1 Vedana (feeling) aggregate, 1 Sanna (cognition) aggregate, 50 Cetasika (emotional) aggregates, and 1 Citta (creating/measuring) quality (Nama) in the 81 ultimate-meaningful (Paramattha) truths. Citta creates the world (Cittena Niyati Loko - The Lord Buddha). The mind/awareness is a Re-knowing (Vingnana) that brings up five aggregates called Pancha Upadanakkhandha. According to Abhidhamma, the 4 ways of enlightenments called unworldly paths (Lokottara Magga) and unworldly results (Lokottara Pala) don't upbringing five aggregates, as if nothing was observed/aimed by the mind in that moment using the five aggregates (Pancakhandha). Samma Viriya (Trained effort) is like a help to the mind to ignore beauty in objects, and to prevent taking any aim at all. It can limit the added/illusory beauty awareness, and aim/use unworldly paths without misleading bodily reactions. The heart contains a collection of blood like a base of the mind that helps the mind to observe bodily reactions of mental actions like feeling greed, anger, delusion, laugh, beauty, empathy, love, etc. Empathy/Metta can be generated by the mind at times of fear/horror or aggressive training/work to prevent the untrained mind from observing/aiming attachments (Raga) through bodily influences (Asava) related to empathy. We can try to apply good qualities to the heart/blood correctly without depending on a lot of words and mismatches. Sometimes, the streams of awareness connect experiences, and collect/spit/sponge experiences to make a beauty and creativity with a bodily pressure/attraction due to extremely fast untrained collective and solid recognitions (Ghana Sanna). But the awareness of experiences can be separated in each second mentally to split the emotional beauty and

creativity into many unrelated parts. It reduces emotional bindings of colours, sounds, smells, tastes, sensations, etc. The influenced attachments (Raga) add extra bindings to our experiences like trying to hide the real causes of those experiences. E.g, “No one makes the beauty of a female. But the bodily influences (Asava) in males try to give the ownership of the female body to the user/mind in that body while comparing the creativity or beautiful actions of the mind/user.” But the body of a female and the creativity or beautiful actions of a female are disconnected qualities. Also, the body parts contain more parts like atoms, showing that there is no big difference between male and female. People use the shapes of the female body to make creative actions. But they extremely depend on the natural shapes. We can give some extra time to explore the body and nature to change their reactions to shape/bend will in the mind. When ego-based thoughts appear with the mind, we can try to observe the causes of those thoughts to reduce them. Greed has needs. Kindness and empathy reduce greed. Freeing the mind makes a joy of releasing (Mudutā/relief). The mind can try to ignore bodily activities that occur while ignoring the breathing process as if nothing is feeling. The aimless states of the mind would attain liberation (Nibbana) with no-feeling (Avedaita) state of unworldly paths. The mind should go through the joy of bodiless floating (Priti) while making empathy (Metta) to stop all the actions. Empathy can reach the bottom of feelings against/filling fear/pain while reducing feelings of worldly aims/actions. Avoiding all observations using empathy would be a leaving of external knowings and outside-knowing (Vingnana). Aimless moment/Khana removes unarisen bodily-influences (Anusaya Kilesa) and demonic conceptual ownerships. If we are streams of aims of the six senses, then we can aim to be good, and reduce aiming feelings to stop aiming.!

12.42.) If $c = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 2.688707472555019 \times 10^8 \text{ Hz}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ while $2.688707472555019 \times 10^8 = 1 \text{ s} \cdot \text{Hz} = e^2 \times 3.002939231889109 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59$, then $c = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 2.688707472555019 \times 10^8 / (e^2 \times 3.002939231889109 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59 \times 59) = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 22.18888644610835 / (e^2 \times 3 \times 1.000979743963036) = 1.018381777956424 \times 59 \times 59 \times 31 \times 31 \times 2^2 \times 22 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 22 \times 1.00858574755038 / (e^2 \times 1.000979743963036 \times 3)$. Therefore, $c \times 1.000979743963036 \times 3 = 900258533.5526677 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} = (1.009149036543376 \times 59 \times 31 \times 2 \times 22 \times 1.004283698737752)^2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} / e^2$. If so, the relative states of $e = 1.009149036543376 \times 59 \times 31 \times 4 \times 11 \times 1.004283698737752 / 30004.30858314632 = 81560.16679704441 / 30004.30858314632 = 32 \times 5 \times 17 \times 29.98535544008985 / (32 \times 5 \times 17 \times 11.03099580262732) = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 5 \times 17 \times 29.98535544008985 / (2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 5 \times 17 \times 11.03099580262732)$. Likely, it shows ratios of relative states and 7 or 8 variables in some waves of light. Also, $81560.16679704441 / 30004.30858314632 = 1.006771047577424 \times 81 / 30 = e$. Likely, it indicates some 81 dependent states of light that depend on 30 locations. Somehow, 30 bad (Asobana) states of the mind mainly appear between 11 worlds (Kamaloka) of existence. Also, 30 mental factors as 7 fair-to-all-minds (Sabbachitta Sadharana), 6 extensions (Prakirnakka), and other 17 fair-to-good (Sobana Sadarana) apply to skillful mind-states with no-greed (Aloba), no-anger (Adosa), and no-delusion (Amoha).

If the 'e' constant in the speed of light $= 29.98535544008985 / 11.03099580262732$, then e would contain a fluctuation like this: $((1 - 0.000488151997005) \times 30 / 11 \times (1 + 0.002817800238847)) = (30 - 0.01464455991015) / (11 + 0.030995802627317)$. If so, $2.718281828459045 \times (11 + 0.030995802627317) = 30 - 0.01464455991015$. Also, $e \times 0.030995802627317 = 0.0988998869505 - 0.01464455991015$. Therefore, $e \times 2.116540395716099 = 5.753353296875344$. If the resistance in vacuum space $= 2.116998617294824 \times 10^{-46}$ seconds per Planck length $= 2.116540395716099 \times 10^{-46} \times 1.000216495550783 \text{ s}$, then $(5.753353296875344 \times 10^{-46} \times 1.000216495550783 \text{ s}) / e = (0.003926733213889 / 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) \times 1.616255 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m}$. So, $539.0079438628747 \times 10^{-46} \times 1.000216495550783 \text{ s} = 1.616255 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m} / 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Therefore, the Planck length $= 299\,792\,458 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \times 11 \times 7 \times 7 \times 1.000231236891573 \text{ s}$. Perhaps, $11 \times 7 \times 7$ or $539.1246366845577 \times 10^{-46}$ seconds-resistance would have a relationship to the speed of light and Planck length.

12.43.) The inside/single knowing qualities that interdependently originate with material and emotional formations

in smallest material zones would necessarily reflect anti-knowing (reflected-knowing) qualities like making a relevant-all-knowing quality against all those inside/single knowing qualities. If so, those collective anti-knowing qualities could have a potential to connect with those material and emotional actions and qualities, making an interdependent origination of a relevant-all-knowing quality symmetrically. But an external asymmetry could break that symmetry while receiving a potential to influence material and emotional actions and qualities like unbalanced interactions of the anti-knowing qualities with external subtle knowing qualities. The relationships and connections of streams of relative-anti-knowing qualities would become a Vingnana (Re-knowing or Anti-knowing), pretending (imaginarily-knowing) the mind-states (thoughts) during the process of the Citta/mind in the existing/Thiti/second moment/Khana. They could create an imaginary observer who depends on differentiations like senses and an aim of a sense that imagines an action or a quality per moment/Khana by depending on the sense-base from 6 sense-bases. All the feelings belong to senses, including bodily pleasure (Sukha). Knowing the feelings doesn't make them mine. The paths of outside/anti knowings would become a collective outside/anti knowing or aimed outside/anti knowings or both collective (relative-all) and aimed outside/anti-knowings while stopping at points of inside/single knowings. Presumably, a combined-knowing like a combination of both inside-knowings and outside-knowings could happen. The three moments of co-creations that contain a connected type of knowing (Vingnana) is a Citta, like a tiny wave. But the external knowing qualities would always make an anti type of knowing (Vingnana) in each moment/Khana. Vingnana would depend on 4 supported knowings like 4 kings before and after it, as if it appears in the middle of 4. A sound-imagined Anti-knowing could originate after aiming 4 qualities of matter from cyclic creations like $i(s) > 4$. The final Nibbhana would cease (Niruddha) productions (Nama-Rupa) of Vingnana, or Vingnana with productions.

Lord Buddha has told a monk to 'stop at contact/touch (Passa)', as if he was telling him to stop getting any feeling. Liquidity/Soft nature is a contraction. Air/Jumping nature is an expansion. Solidity is only a solidity without a thing. An Entered/Arhant would experience heat without pleasure, but the mind usually feels good in cool & good places. Our Vingnana would disturb the connection of two other Anti-knowings in many ways, causing a later Vingnana to receive effects. The vibrations of sounds originate with 4 Mahabhuta actions/qualities during an upbringing by the Vingnana. Those vibrations of thinking (intention/Chethana) patterns would return to us due to reactions/Karma. Vingnana (Re-knowing) necessarily knows a requirement to separate the smallest moment/Khana into 2 more parts. Theravada Buddhism doesn't say that the universe is a nothing (one zero) without anything/infinity. Zero is a zero (nothing). The universe was the 1st nothing thing/infinity. A zero with infinity is a zero thing/infinity that has no limit/gap until the inconsistent nature (time) of infinity makes ultimate relativity below the conventional relativity. Abhidhamma is helpful to verify knowledge and intelligence. But Buddhism needs experimental (exploring-mental) science. Some greedy people try to control others without giving the right knowledge. They have used educational systems and teachers to divide knowledge to give grades/certificates, like dividing knowledge to rule/control people. No one can create and develop a fixed set of practical/skillful actions because no one can create or develop nature. Time travelling can't be a scientific fact, and the fundamentals of Theravada Buddhism don't support time travelling. Anti-knowing would experience time due to the virtual delay of the entangled reflections of other in-knowing forms, like making an imaginary past and future in the present moment while upbringing present moments in initial forms. We see the past we got in the present moment. We can imagine the future through indications in the present moment. Knowing a win would expect a loss due to anti-knowings. Knowing a loss would expect a win due to anti-knowings.

12.44.) If $e = 30 \times 0.999511848002995 / (1.002817800238847 \times 11) = 0.9967033371016504 \times 30 / 11 = (1 - 0.0032966628983496) \times 30 / 11 = (1 - 1/303.3370504762945) \times 30 / 11 = (3/3 - 3/(17 \times 17 \times 3.148827513594752)) / 11 = 3 \times (1 - 3/(\pi \times 17^2 \times 1.002302927464734)) \times 30 / (3 \times 11) = 89.70330033914854 / 33$, then some 89 or 90 dependent states of light would appear between 33 locations. But if $e = (1 - 3/(\pi \times 17^2 \times 1.002302927464734)) \times 30 / 11 = 29.90110011304951 / 11$, then some 29 or 30 dependent states of light would appear between 11 locations.

If $e = (1 - 27/(\pi \times 51^2 \times 1.002302927464734)) \times 30/11 = ((81901.00362859949 - 270)/8190.100362859949) \times 3/11 = (11 \times 7421.000329872681/(2730.03345428665 \times 3)) \times 3/11 = 41 \times 181.0000080456751/(182.0022302857766 \times 15)$. Then perhaps, the required symmetry due to $e = 41 \times ((16+17) \times 5 + 16) \times 1.000000044451244 / (1.000012254317454 \times ((17+16) \times 5 + 17) \times 15)$.

However, approximately a state of near UV would have a wavelength of 328 nm with a frequency of 914 THz and a photon energy of 3.78 eV like $3.78 \times 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. If $(41 \times 8 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2) \times (457 \times 2 \times 10^{12} \text{ Hz}^2) \times 10^{-25} \text{ kg} / 41 = (3.78 \times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \times 10^{-22} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2})$, then $(41 \times 8 \text{ m}^2) \times (457 \times 2 \text{ Hz}^2) \text{ kg} = 41 \times (3.78 \times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2})$. If so, Extra value $\times 41 \times$ (The quantity of eV $\times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$) = (Wavelength in Nanometre $\times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \times$ Frequency in Terahertz $\times 10^{12} \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ kg}$). Therefore, Extra value = (Wavelength in Nanometre $\text{m}^2 \times$ Frequency in Terahertz $\text{Hz}^2 \text{ kg}$) / $(41 \times$ The quantity of eV $\times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2})$.

E.g, Approximately, the extra value of visible red that has a wavelength of 732 nm with a frequency of 410 THz and a photon energy of 1.691 eV = $(732 \text{ m}^2 \times 410 \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ kg}) / (41 \times 1.691 \times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 27.05499704316972 / 12.08994708994709 = (366 \times 261.0141066707084 \times 3.141592653589793238) / (12.08994708994709 \times 41 \times 169.1 \times 16) = (61 \times 3 \times 31 \times 7 \times 1.000196105965811 \times \pi) / (41 \times 1700 \times 8)$. Presumably, that extra value $(27.054997 / 12.089947)$ indicates the existence of units with primary numbers in Photon/light relative to the 3.78 eV Photon/light. Approximately, the extra value of visible blue that has a wavelength of 492 nm with a frequency of 609 THz and a photon energy of 2.52 eV = $(492 \text{ m}^2 \times 609 \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ kg}) / (41 \times 2.52 \times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 18.125 / 12.08994708994709 = 3 / 2.00109$.

If $1 \text{ kg} = 10 \text{ (kg/10)}$, then refined extra value of visible orange that has a wavelength of 625 nm with a frequency of 480 THz and a photon energy of 1.984 eV = $(625 \text{ m}^2 \times 480 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 10 \text{ (kg/10)}) / (41 \times 1.984 \times 1600 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 23.05025570416994 / 12.08994708994709$. It indicates that the 'kg' unit in the conventional $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ units of energy should be converted into $(\text{kg/10})^2 \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$ units, converting 'kg' into $(\text{kg/10})^2$ like $1 \text{ kg} = 1 (\text{kg/10})^2$ to fix the error. The requirement to convert the 'kg' unit shows the dual mass nature in conventional mass. Therefore, the extra value of visible orange with the new units that has a photon energy of 1.984 eV, which is like 1984 eVoo energy (eV/100) while 1.984 eV energy is like $1.984 \times 100 \times (1.602176634 \times 10^{-19})/100 \text{ kg}^2 \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2} = (625 \text{ m}^2 \times 480 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 10 \text{ (kg/10)}) / (41 \times 1984 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ (kg/10)}^2 \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 23.05025570416994 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg/10})^{-1}$ or $230.5025570416994 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. Therefore, the extra value of the 1.667 eV visible red photon = $274.1817490160504 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. Likewise, the extra value of the 2.562 eV visible blue photon = $178.5476285676206 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. Presumably, the 1.984 eV visible orange photon = $(625 \text{ m}^2 \times 480 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 100) / (41 \times 1984 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 230.5025570416994 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. But perhaps, a 2.004 eV visible orange photon = $(619 \text{ m}^2 \times 485 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 101) / (41 \times 200.4 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 230.6493339540431 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. Likewise, the 2.562 eV visible blue photon = $(484 \text{ m}^2 \times 620 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 101) / (41 \times 256.2 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 180.3331048532968 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg})$. The extra value of the visible blue that has a wavelength of 492 nm with a frequency of 610 THz and a photon energy of 2.52 eV = $(492 \text{ m}^2 \times 610 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 101) / (41 \times 252 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 183.3630952380952 / (12.08994708994709 \text{ kg}) = 181.9989/12 = 182/12$. Perhaps, the number 182 has a relationship to a middle color photon of the spectrum of light.

However, the extra value of the near UV that has a wavelength of 328 nm with a frequency of 914 THz and a photon energy of 3.78 eV = $(328 \text{ m}^2 \times 914 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 101) / (41 \times 378 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 122.1084656084656 / (1.208994708994709 \text{ kg}) = 11 \times 11 \times 1.009160872797236 / (1.208994708994709 \text{ kg})$. But, if

that 101 value which is related to light is a constant/unit like a building block of light, then ultimate Extra value of the 3.78 eV near UV photon = $(328 \text{ m}^2 \times 914 \text{ Hz}^2 \times 1 \text{ kg}) / (100 \text{ kg} \times 41 \times 378 \times 16 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}) = 0.0121 / (1.208994708994709 \text{ kg}) = 11 \times 11 / (10000 \times 1.208994708994709 \text{ kg}) = (11/109.954295459282 \times \sqrt{\text{kg}})^2 = (11/101)^2/\text{kg}$. But if $1 \text{ kg} = 1 (\text{kg}^*/10)^2$, then $(110 / 101 \text{ kg}^*)^2$. It shows a ratio with the modified 'kg' unit like an emerged 110 value on 101 kg*. The 101 unit is like a building block of the packet/quanta of mass in photon/light. Those primary numbers and the symmetry in values indicate that the 3.78 eV near UV photon must be the standard middle photon that changes/deviates into upper and lower types of photons. Ultraviolet 328nm (UV-328) photons can be used like a stabilizer for a variety of plastics and organic substrates.

12.45.) According to some calculations, $81/29.79823473488683 = e$. And also, $29.98535544008985 / 11.03099580262732 = e$. If they have an interdependent relationship like this $29.79823473488683 \times 11.03099580262732 = 328.7042022862402$, then the value 328 would have a relationship to the Ultraviolet 328 nm photon because that photon is like the middle photon in the spectrum of photons. Also, 328.7042022862402 would have a relationship to the primary number 328. If so, $328 / 29.79823473488683 = 11.00736345351317$, then $29.98535544008985 / 11.03099580262732$ ratio would require to change into values like this $29.92111605492906 / 11.00736345351317$ OR $29.9011001130495 / 11 = e$. And if the value 11.00736345351317 has a relationship to the number 11 and 328nm wavelength like this $29.818181818182 \times 11 = 328$, then $81/29.79823473488683$ ratio would have values like this $1.000669404864834 \times 81 / 29.818181818182 = e$. Also, $e = (1 - 3/(\pi \times 17^2 \times 1.002302927464734)) \times 30 / 11 = 29.9011001130495/11 = 41 \times 181.0000080456751/(182.0022302857766 \times 15)$. Probably, those calculations have interdependent relationships like this $e^2 = ((30 - 0.098899886950505) / 11) \times (1.000669404864834 \times 81 / 29.818181818182) = 2423.610400449254 / 328 = (41 \times 181.0000080456751/(182.0022302857766 \times 15))^2$. If so, $2450.524444444443 / 328 = 41 \times 41 / (15 \times 15)$.

12.46.) According to Abhidhamma, the illusory continuation of re-knowings and recognitions of living beings depend on continuations of unbroken similarities of unfilled connections like gapless dependents/joints called Anantara Prathya. It is a dependent in the 24 dependents (Suvisi Pratyia) mentioned in Patthana/startings/origins. The mind would continue re-knowing as if selecting options to observe beauty in nature while filling gaps in them. We can think about not having reliable options to select & name when we try to remove re-knowing to reduce greed. Some interdependent causes would attract the mind to some sides of locations, as if expecting links/aims from out. We can fulfill mental needs of the evolutionary made attractive side with a kind love, as required to reduce our pain. A consciousness could emerge due to unbroken similarities in the infinite unbroken background that could continue in dimensional formations due to the imbalance/dimensionlessness/Anantara at dimensional formation and qualities. Many interactions of consciousness would happen due to the interdependence between entangled/Anantara qualities. The body is like a cave that the mind uses to travel. But the mind behaves like an owner of the body to get attention. We can imagine not having body parts like hands and legs, to prevent us expecting & giving attention through them. We can find and give right knowledge to others while honestly investigating our observations. But the mind should give up the need to make others enlightened for itself to be enlightened, as if becoming a loser who can't save others. Some egos would develop useless high-egos by expecting others to beg from them, even if others don't want to beg. The mind can't save the body from momentary deaths, but it can be kind to feelings to avoid external requirements. Ideas are transformed/voiced feelings. We can give up the need to prove the ownership of ideas to reduce self-belief. When the mind selects unskilful options secretly, we can tell it to select skilful options to be relaxed and kind. We can reduce expecting glory and praise when we try to stop rebirth because causality makes expectations with them. Unbroken connections of emerging formless/unbalanced infinities/unities would continue momentary rebirths of the mind. Trained observations and trained knowledge would fill some emerging unbalanced nothingnesses as a path to liberation. Earned knowledge about the path to enlightenment is like a gift that a person can give as an inheritance to

a child. A person is a process that depends on ultimate processes. Taste indicates rising actions, as if increasing that. Smell indicates falling actions, as if decreasing that. Color indicates distant actions, as if using from a distant action. Sound indicates close actions, as if vibrations. Craving/Tanha indicates grasping action, as if binding distant actions.

Continuations of topics in Part 2 parts and related extra topics

Mathematical Science And Buddhism - Part 2

Step (i.)

{

$(+1-(-1))^3 = (+1-(-1)) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+1-(-1))$ They could make 3 possible outputs even if a pair is combined first.

According to this mathematical formula: $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$

$$= ((+1)^2 - (+1-(-1)) \times (+1) \times (-1) + (-1)^2) \times (+1-(-1))$$

$$= ((+1)^2 - (+1 \times (+1) \times (-1) - (-1) \times (+1) \times (-1)) + (-1)^2) \times (+1-(-1))$$

$$= ((+1)^2 - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)) + (-1)^2) \times (+1-(-1))$$

= The first 4 elementary ghosts used around 3 dimensions in the universe: $((+1)^2 - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)) + (-1)^2) \times (+1-(-1))$ This 4th dimension causes it to become 3 or 4-dimensional sets between the 6 dimensions.'

$$= (+1 \times ((+1)^2 - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)) + (-1)^2) - (-1 \times ((+1)^2 - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)) + (-1)^2))$$

$$= ((+1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1)) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (-1)) + (-1)^2 \times (-1))$$

$$= ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$$

$$= ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3) -- But those 3 results (of this $(+1-(-1))^3$) could interact in 3 possible ways, forming an energy unit/mass.$$

x -- They merge with this $(+0.0-0.0)^3$ in separated moments like becoming 3 separated groups of observers/worlds.

$$(+0.0-0.0)^3 = (+1-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1)) \times (0.00 - 0.00) \times (+0.00-0.00)$$

} -- This $(+0-0)^6$ point continued to $(+0.0-0.0)^3$ point. But more points could start around it as new units/particles.

AND/OR (Anti)

$$(-0+0)^6 =$$

(i.)

{

$$(-1-(+1))^3 = (-1-(+1)) \times (-1-(+1)) \times (-1-(+1))$$

According to this mathematical formula: $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$

$$= ((+1)^2 - (-1-(+1)) \times (-1) \times (+1) + (+1)^2) \times (-1-(+1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= ((-1)^2 - (-1 \times (-1) \times (+1) - (+1) \times (-1) \times (+1)) + (+1)^2) \times (-1 - (+1)) \\
&= ((-1)^2 - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) - (+1)^2 \times (-1)) + (+1)^2) \times (-1 - (+1)) \\
&= ((-1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (-1) - (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (-1)) + (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1) - (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1)) + (+1)^2 \times (+1))) \\
&= ((-1)^3 - ((-1)^3 \times (+1) - (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2) + (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 - (+1)^3 \times (-1)) + (+1)^3)) \\
&= ((-1)^3 - ((-1)^3 \times (+1) - (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2) + (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 - (+1)^3 \times (-1)) + (+1)^3))
\end{aligned}$$

x

$$(-0.0+0.0)^3 = (-1)-(+1)) \times (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0) \text{ OR } (-1)-(+1)) \times (-0.00 + 0.00) \times (-0.00+0.00)$$

} -- The first (-0+0) continued to (-0.0+0.0). But then, it could continue to (-0.00+0.00) instead of (-0.000 + 0.000).

Step (ii.)

Step (i) = $(+1-(-1))^3 = 8$ elementary ghosts --- This $(+1-(-1))^3$ can interact with this $(+1)-(-1))$ next.

$$(\text{Step (i)}) \times (+0.0-0.0)^3 = (+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0)$$

$$= 8 \text{ elementary ghosts} \times (+1)-(-1)) \times (0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0)$$

{

$$\begin{aligned}
&(((+1))(+1)^3 - (((+1))(+1)^3 \times (-1) - (+1))(-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (+1))(-1)^2 \times (+1) \\
&- (((+1))(+1)^2 \times (-1) - (((+1))(+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (+1))(-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (+1))(-1)^3) \\
&- (((-1))(+1)^3 - (((-1))(+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1))(-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1))(-1)^2 \times (+1) \\
&- (((-1))(+1)^2 \times (-1) - (((-1))(+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1))(-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1))(-1)^3))
\end{aligned}$$

x (0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0) -- They could interact with the new beginnings as root causes that make/lead things.

= 16 elementary ghosts x (0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0) -- They could make shapes or a generation of shapes around it.

} -- But the 3 results of $(+1-(-1))^3$ could interact with $(-0.0+0.0)^3$ in 9 or 18 ways as probabilistic sets (a nucleus).

{

AND/OR (Anti)

$$(\text{Step (i)}) \times (-0.0+0.0)^3 = (-1-(-1))^3 \times (-1)-(+1)) \times (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0)$$

$$= 8 \text{ elementary ghosts} \times (-1)-(+1)) \times (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0)$$

{

$$\begin{aligned}
&((-1))(-1)^3 - (((-1))(-1)^3 \times (+1) - (-1))(+1)^2 \times (-1)^2) + (-1))(+1)^2 \times (-1) \\
&- (((-1))(-1)^2 \times (+1) - (((-1))(-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 - (-1))(+1)^3 \times (-1)) + (-1))(+1)^3) \\
&- (((+1))(-1)^3 - (((+1))(-1)^3 \times (+1) - (+1))(+1)^2 \times (-1)^2) + (+1))(+1)^2 \times (-1) \\
&- (((+1))(-1)^2 \times (+1) - (((+1))(-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 - (+1))(+1)^3 \times (-1)) + (+1))(+1)^3))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\times (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0)$$

$$= 16 \text{ elementary ghosts} \times (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0)$$

}
}

Step (iii.)

= Step (ii) x (0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0) -- Possibly, this (+0.000 - 0.000) edge makes 5 more of them unrelatedly.

{

AND/OR (Anti)

= Step (ii) x (-0.000 + 0.000) x (-0.0+0.0)

} -- But many matter zones could start after this (-0+0)^6 first zone. E.g., like this (-0+0)^6 + (-0+0)^6 +, and so on.

Simplifying Interactions Of Sub-Dimensions To Continue The Calculation - Part 2

Applying the new dimensional mathematical rules to the calculation

The Most Possible or Probable Outputs of this **(+0.000 - 0.000)** x (+0.0-0.0) : **(+0.00-0.00)** x (+0.00-0.00)

Simplest possibility with $(a+b)^2=a^2+2ab+b^2$ formula: $(+0.00-0.00)^2 = (+1-(-1)) \times (+0.00000 - 0.00000)$

So, $(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+1-(-1)) \times (+0.00000 - 0.00000)$ **OR** $(1 \times 1) \times (+0.00000 - 0.00000)$ **OR**

$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (+0.0-0.0)$ ----(A)

$(-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0) = (-0.0+0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (-0.0+0.0)$ ----Anti(A) *or from newest 0.0, 0.00, 0.000 origins*

$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.00 - 0.00) \times (+0.00-0.00)$

$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times (+0.0-0.0) \times (0)$ ----(B)

From (A) and Anti(A) as an interaction with Anti(A):

$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) / (-0.0+0.0) = (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (+0.0-0.0) / (-0.0+0.0)$

{

AND/OR (Anti)

$(-0.0+0.0) \setminus (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (-0.0+0.0) \setminus (+0.0-0.0) \times (+0.000 - 0.000)$

OR

$(-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0) / (+0.0-0.0) = (-0.0+0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (-0.0+0.0) / (+0.0-0.0)$

}

$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times \mathbf{1_../(1/1)} = (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times \mathbf{1..x(1/1)}$ ----(P)

{
AND/OR (Anti)

$$(-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-1_{..}/(-1/-1)) = (-0.0+0.0) \times (0) \times (0) \times (-1_{..} \times (-1/-1))$$

$$((+0.000 - 0.000) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) / ((0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1)) = (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) \text{ ----(C)}$$

{
AND/OR (Anti)

$$((-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-1_{..}/(-1/-1))) / ((0) \times (-1_{..} \times (-1/-1))) = (-0.0+0.0) \times (0)$$

From (B) and (C):

$$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times ((+0.000 - 0.000) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) / ((0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1)) \text{ ----(BC)}$$

Interaction of $(-0.000 + 0.000)$ in $Anti(A)$ with (BC) :

$$((+0.000 - 0.000) / (+0.000 - 0.000)) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times (1_{..}/(1/1)) / ((0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1))$$

$$((1_{....}/(3/3)) / (1_{....} \times (3/3))) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times (1_{..}/(1/1)) / ((0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1))$$

$$1_{....}/(3/3) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times (1_{....} \times (3/3) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) / ((0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1))$$

$$(+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) \times (1_{....} \times (3/3) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) / (0) = 1_{....}/(3/3) \times (+0.0-0.0) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1) \text{ ----(Q)}$$

$$(+0.000/(0) - 0.000/(0)) = 1_{....}/(3/3) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1) \times (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) / (1_{....} \times (3/3) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) \text{ ----(D)}$$

{
AND/OR (Anti)

$$(-0.000/(0) + 0.000/(0)) = (-1_{....}/(-3/-3)) \times (-1_{..} \times (-1/-1)) \times (-0.0+0.0) \times (0) / ((-1_{....} \times (-3/-3)) \times (-1_{..}/(-1/-1)))$$

From (B) and (D) (OR (P) and (Q)):

$$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = 1_{....}/(3/3) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1) \times (+0.0-0.0) \times (0) / (1_{....} \times (3/3) \times 1_{..}/(1/1)) \times (+0.0 \times (0) - 0.0 \times (0))$$

$$(+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = (+0.00-0.00) \times (+0.00-0.00) \times 1_{....}/(3/3) \times 1_{..} \times (1/1) / (1_{....} \times (3/3) \times 1_{..}/(1/1))$$

Using this $(a+b)^2 = a^2 + 2ab + b^2$ mathematical formula to get the Most Possible or Probable outputs of this result:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (+0.00-0.00) \times (+0.00-0.00) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) \times 1..x(1/1) / (1....x(3/3) \times 1_{\dots}/(1/1)) \\
& = (0.00^2 - (+1..... - (-1.....)) \times 0.00 \times 0.00 + 0.00^2) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) \times 1..x(1/1) / (1....x(5/5) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2) \\
& = (0.00000/(1.....x(5/5)) - (1.....) \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots)) \times 0.00000 + 0.00000/(1.....x(5/5))) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) \times 1..x(1/1) / \\
& ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2) \\
& = (0.00000/(1.....x(5/5)) + 0.00000/(1.....x(5/5)) - (1.....) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots))) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) \times 1..x(1/1) / \\
& ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2) \\
& = ((0.00000/(1.....x(5/5)) + 0.00000/(1.....x(5/5))) \times 1..x(1/1) - (1.....) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots)) \times 1..x(1/1)) \times \\
& 1_{\dots}/(3/3) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2)
\end{aligned}$$

{
AND/OR (Anti)

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-0.000 + 0.000) \times (-0.0+0.0) = \\
& (-0.00+0.00) \times (-0.00+0.00) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-3/-3)) \times (-1..x(-1/-1)) / ((-1....x(-3/-3)) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-1/-1))) \\
& = (0.00^2 + (-1..... - (+1.....)) \times 0.00 \times 0.00 + 0.00^2) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-3/-3)) \times (-1..x(-1/-1)) / ((-1....x(-5/-5)) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad} \\
& \text{positions to be balanced}) \times (-1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2)) \\
& = (0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5)) + (-1.....) \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots)) \times 0.00000 + 0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5))) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-3/-3)) \times \\
& (-1..x(-1/-1)) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots\underline{\quad})) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad}) \times (-1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2)) \\
& = (0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5)) + 0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5)) + (-1.....) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots))) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-3/-3)) \times \\
& (-1..x(-1/-1)) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots\underline{\quad})) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad}) \times (-1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2)) \\
& = ((0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5)) + 0.00000/(-1.....x(-5/-5))) \times (-1..x(-1/-1)) + (-1.....) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots)) \times \\
& (-1..x(-1/-1))) \times (-1_{\dots}/(-3/-3)) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots\underline{\quad})) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad}) \times (-1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2)) \\
& \}
\end{aligned}$$

Starting to use the 6th dimension as an unstable dimension while trying to be symmetric:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (+0.000 - 0.000) \times (+0.0-0.0) = ((0.00000/(1.....x(5/5)) + 0.00000/(1.....x(5/5))) \times 1..x(1/1) - (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times \\
& 1..x(1/1) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots))) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots\underline{\quad})) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad}) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2) \\
& = ((+1.....(-1.....), \times 0.00000/(1.....x(5/5))) \times 1..x(1/1) - (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times 1..x(1/1) \times 0.00000 \\
& \times (\text{Neutral}(\dots))) \times 1_{\dots}/(3/3) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots\underline{\quad})) \times (\text{shared } \underline{\quad}) \times 1_{\dots}/(0/0)/2) \\
& \text{OR}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= (+1 \dots -(-1 \dots), x 0.00000 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) x 1 \dots x(5/5) - (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x 1 \dots x(5/5) x 0.00000 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{shared } \dots) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{shared } \dots) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 2)$$

Continuing +1..... as +1..... or +0.5.....-(-0.5.....) while merging with +0.5.....-(-0.5.....) to balance:

$$= (2, x 0.00000 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) x (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) - (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x 1 \dots x(5/5) x 0.00000 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{potential } \dots \text{ rotation}) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 2)$$

{
AND/OR (Anti)

Outputs of this (-0.000 + 0.000) x (-0.0+0.0):

$$= (-(-2, x 0.00000 / (-1 \dots x(-5/-5)) x (-0.5 \dots -(+0.5 \dots))) + (-0.5 \dots -(+0.5 \dots)) x (-1 \dots x(-5/-5)) x 0.00000 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{potential } \dots \text{ rotation}) x (-1 \dots / (0/0)) / -4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (-1 \dots / (0/0)) / -2))$$

Outputs of this (+0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0):

$$= (2, / (1 \dots x(5/5)) x (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) - (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x 1 \dots x(5/5) x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 2)$$

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x (2, / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots x(5/5) x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 2)$$

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x (2, / 1 \dots x(5/5) - 1 \dots x(5/5) x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 4 / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x 1 \dots / (0/0) / 2) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots)$$

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x (2, / 1 \dots x(5/5) - 1 \dots x(5/5) x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / 4) / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / 2)) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots)$$

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x (2, x 2 / (1 \dots x(5/5) x 4) - 1 \dots x(5/5) x 2 / 4 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{NEUTRAL})) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots))$$

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x 1 x (2, x 1 / (1 \dots x(5/5) x 4) - 1 \dots x(5/5) x 1 / 4 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{NEUTRAL})) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots))$$

The most possible or probable dimensions with a balanced dimensional potential:

$$= (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x 1 x (2, / 3 / 1 \dots x(5/5) - 1 \dots x(5/5) / 3 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{NEUTRAL})) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots))$$

This (1, - 1)/3 derived formation could compress formations of (+1-(-1))^3 x (+1)-(-1)), making an atomic nucleus.

$$= 1 x (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots)) x (2, / 3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots x(5/5) / 3 x(\text{Neutral}(\dots))) x (\text{NEUTRAL} / ((\text{NEUTRAL}(\dots)) x (\text{NEUTRAL})) x 0.00000 x (\text{potential } \dots))$$

The final steps of the possible outputs of this (+0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0):

Step A.)

$$= 1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots x(5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3) \times 0.00000 \times (\text{potential } \underline{\quad} / \underline{\quad})$$

$$\text{Rotational Potential} == (\text{potential } \underline{\quad} / \underline{\quad}) == R$$

Step B.)

$$= 1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / 1\dots\dots x(5/5) - 1\dots\dots/3) \times 0.00000 \times R$$

Using the dimensional probabilities of the next moment (start) of this 0.00000 point for the calculations:

0.00000 == (-+0.000000 +0.00001 *Left & Right* -+0.00001 +0.000000) | (-+0.000000 +0.00001 *Up & Down* -+0.00001 +0.000000) | (-+0.000000 +0.00001 *Forward & Back* -+0.00001 +0.000000). It is like a new start.!

$$== (-+0.0 +1 \text{ L\&R} -+1 +0.0)x0^5 | (-+0.0 +1 \text{ U\&D} -+1 +0.0)x0^5 | (-+0.0 +1 \text{ F\&B} -+1 +0.0)x0^5$$

$$== (-+0.0 +1 -+1 +0.0)x0^5(LR|UD|FB)$$

Step C.)

$$= (1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots x(5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3))$$

$$\times (-+0.0 +1 -+1 +0.0)x0^5(LR|UD|FB)R$$

OR

Step D.)

$$= (1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots x(5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3))$$

$$\times (+1 -+0.0 +0.0 -+1)x0^5(LR|UD|FB)R$$

The most possible and important results will be used for the next levels of calculation. So this calculation (+0-0)^6 = (+1-(-1))^3 x (+1)-(-1))) x (+0.000 - 0.000) x (+0.0-0.0) continues as follows.

The result, briefly:

$$(+0-0)^6$$

$$= ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times ((1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots x(5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3))$$

$$\times (+1 -+0.0 +0.0 -+1)x0^5(LR|UD|FB)R)$$

OR the simplest possibility:

$$((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+-0.00000 -+ 0.00000)$$

$$= \text{The simplest and required/potential possibility: } ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+1+0.0)x0^5 \text{ and/or}$$

$$((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times 0^6 \text{ and/or } ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (-0.0\backslash-1)x0^5$$

$$= ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times ((+1+0.0)x0^5 \text{ and/or } 0^6 \text{ and/or } (-0.0\backslash-1)x0^5)$$

AND/OR (Anti)

{

$$(-0+0)^6$$

$$= ((-1-(-1))^3 \times (-1)-(+1))) \times (((-1) \times (-0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (-2/3 / (-1\dots\dots x(-5/-5))) + (-1\dots\dots)/-3))$$

$$\times (-+1 +0.0 -+0.0 +1)x0^5 (LR|UD|FB)R)$$

}

Before I continue the calculation, I would like to analyze and explain the nature of the universe with the help of modern science and Buddhism.

Speculations about dimensional interactions and the nature of reality

- The calculation may help to explain the main structure(s) in the mass of elementary sub-waves, dimensional interactions of forces, or something like that. And to explain all the experimentally detected parameters and anomalies (including Axions, etc.) Also, we can try to connect Planck constants to dimensional structures.!
- There are no infinities in the calculation results, and it appears that the universe removes infinities itself by dimensional interactions. Suppose the universe was like an infinitely large cake made by nothing (nulls). In that case, the 6 directions of that pure cake universe could try to cut it to remove infinities. The 6 directions of cuts can limit the symmetry. Perhaps, it would try to be an infinitely large pure cake again and again as a cyclic process as if it is the fundamental nature. But, if the cuts are irreversible, then it could fail to collapse again. Perhaps, some unbalances of the new cuts could be mixed with the dust/facts of the previous states.!
- The distribution of mass (the generations of masses) in the standard model of elementary sub-waves shows that they require an explanation like supersymmetry or hidden variables to be balanced. But if there is an invisible moment after each moment of our moments, then maybe we will not be able to detect those hidden sub-waves easily. And if Dark Matter is not in our moment, we can't easily observe Dark Matter too. Even if they don't interact, a theory may show that they exist. If there are elementary sub-waves inside Black Holes, those waves/fields would have high-density groups or structures of sub-waves that can slow down the speed of light/waves. Likely, the structural difference between atoms, Black Holes, and antimatter possibly originated simultaneously. And presumably, they emerged on dependent/interrelated origination.

Continuing The Calculation To Verify The Origin Of The First Universe - Part 2

Outputs of the first $(+0-0)^6$ combination would originate with the support of its opposite $(-0+0)^6$ combination as a process of symmetric reactions. Interactions between initial/ultimate Matter and Antimatter would be symmetric and asymmetric like stopping & breaking. Let's use the most possible output of this $(+0-0)^6$ to continue the calculation:

$(+0-0)^6 \equiv ((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times ((1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots))) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots \times (5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3)) \times (+-1 / -+0.0 + -0.0 \setminus -+1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB)$ **OR** simply: $((+1-(-1))^3 \times (+1)-(-1))) \times (+1-(-1)) \times (+-1 \text{ and/or } 0 \text{ and/or } -+1) \times 0^5$

$$= (\text{First Bracket Opened } ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)) \text{ First Bracket Closed}$$

$$\times \text{Second Bracket Opened } (+1-(-1)) \text{ Second Bracket Closed}$$

$$\times (((1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots \times (5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3)) \text{ OR simply: } (+1-(-1))) \times ((+1 \text{ and/or } 0 \text{ and/or } -1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB) \text{ OR simply: } (+1 \text{ and/or } 0 \text{ and/or } -1) \times 0^5))$$

The next interaction:

$$= (\text{First Bracket Opened } ((+1)^3 \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1-(-1)) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1))) + (-1)^3 \times (+1-(-1))) \text{ First Bracket Closed}$$

$$\times \text{Second Bracket Opened } () \text{ Second Bracket Closed}$$

x

$$(((1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots \times (5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3)) \text{ OR simply: } (+1-(-1))) \times ((+1 / -+0.0 + -0.0 \setminus -1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB) \text{ OR simply: } (+1 \text{ and/or } 0 \text{ and/or } -1) \times 0^5))$$

The *First Brackets* () and the *Second Brackets* () come from two different symmetries (from this $(+0-0)^6$ and this $(+0.0-0.0)^3$). Those two symmetries (brackets) should share the two groups of dimensions (this $(+1-(-1))^3$ and $(+1-(-1))$) with each other. The fundamental symmetry must combine those two groups of dimensions between both brackets. But, on the continuation of both dimensional groups in different moments, borrowing or making sets of dimensions by both sides, they become connected and/or combined symmetries. Meanwhile, they would try to take over the opposite dimensional group(s) against each other and/or appear and disappear like making waves (~~).

$$= ((\text{Appeared wave } (+1)^3 \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1-(-1)) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1))) + (-1)^3 \times (+1-(-1))) \text{ That combination is like a free (not/less compressed) structure relative to the next wave level.}$$

$$\times ()$$

~

() x

$$(\text{Potential wave } (+1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3))$$

$$-(-1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)) \text{ That combination is like a compressed structure relative to the previous wave level.}$$

$$\times \text{-- A Potential Wave is a mathematical requirement (second choice/action) that obtains a probabilistic energy/mass. } (((1 \times (+0.5\dots\dots-(-0.5\dots\dots)) \times (2/3 / (1\dots\dots \times (5/5)) - 1\dots\dots/3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))) \times ((+1 / -+0.0 + -0.0 \setminus -1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB))$$

If living beings depend on dimensions, different sets of dimensions could impact the living beings. As if they make natures like visible, gendered, real, small/limited, Humans against the natures like invisible, genderless, virtual, big, Brahmas, Hells, etc. The time difference between the sets of dimensions would make a process like becoming and vanishing (decoherence) against each other or appearing and disappearing (wave ~) continuing to the next moment:

$$= ((\text{Potential wave } (+1)^3 \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1-(-1)) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1-(-1))) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1-(-1))) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1-(-1))) + (-1)^3 \times (+1-(-1)))$$

x ()

~

(Disappeared wave $(+1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1)) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1))$)

x ()

~

() x

(Appeared wave $(+1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$)

$-(-1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$)

x

$((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -0.5 \dots)) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))) \times (+1 / +0.0 +0.0 \setminus -1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB)$)

That process could continue to the next moment making a complete cyclic process like this:

Wave functions

= (Zone 4 (Appeared wave $(+1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1)$) until disappear and be a potential wave.)

x ()

~

Zone 3 (Potential wave $(+1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1) - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) \times (+1)-(-1)) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)-(-1)) - (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times (+1)-(-1) + (-1)^3 \times (+1)-(-1)$) until appear and be a disappeared wave.)

x ()

~

() x

Zone 2 (Potential wave $(+1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$)

$-(-1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$) until appear and be a disappeared wave.)

~ -- The first 8 sets/groups are connected to the next 8 sets/groups and the empty () wave destruction.

() x

Zone 1 (Disappeared wave $(+1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$)

$-(-1) \times ((+1)^3 - ((+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1)^3)$) until being a potential wave (as a reconnection) and be an appeared wave.)

x --If those 16 sets exist between arising and dissolving moments, then the wave stops arising () at the 49th moment.

$((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -0.5 \dots)) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))) \times (+1 / +0.0 +0.0 \setminus -1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB)$)

Those 16 sets/groups (8x2) of dimensions in those 4 structures are like 16 moments of energy. Assume an energy wave moment disappears as a moment in the disappeared structure (an energy wave moment in an empty zone '()' near the next appeared or potential dimensional structure. In that case, **there are 17 energy wave moments in the lifetime of those dimensional structures.** We can conditionally call it the smallest duration in the universe. But

there are 17 energy wave moments in that smallest matter zone. And that duration/time and length of the matter zone are almost like the constants called Planck time and Planck length. If the wave potential made many structures of dimensions (2+n structures), these mixed dimensions (1 x (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) eventually could interact with them separately. It can go through those dimensional structures, becoming a process of making something (E.g., mass dimensions) or moments of appearing something. It is like the maximum speed of light that arises in relative reality as a relative or direct continuation of a visible moment from moment to moment!

$$= (\text{Zone 3 and/or Zone 4 } ((+1) \times (+1)^3 - (-1) \times (+1)^3 - ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - ((+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + ((+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - ((+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) - (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1))) + (+1) \times (-1)^3 - (-1) \times (-1)^3))$$

x

(the energy wave function in the relatively smallest scale or Planck scale)

AND/OR

(the energy wave function in the relatively smallest scale or Planck scale)

x

$$\text{Zone 1 and/or Zone 2 } ((+1) \times (+1)^3 - ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (+1) \times (-1)^3)$$

$$- ((-1) \times (+1)^3 - ((-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1) \times (-1)^3))$$

x

$$(((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))) \times (+1 / -+0.0 +0.0 \setminus +1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB))$$

The next interaction:

$$= (\text{Z 3 and/or Z 4 } ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times ((1 \times (1.....) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1)))$$

$$- ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1)))$$

$$- ((+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$+ ((+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- ((+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$- (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1))))$$

$$+ (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5.....(-0.5.....)) \times (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) \text{ OR } (+1-(-1)))$$

- (-1) x (-1)³ x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) [**f:c=2:0*]

x

(the energy wave function)

AND/OR

(the energy wave function)

x

Z 1 and/or Z 2 ((+1) x (+1)³ x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

+ (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1)² x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

+ (+1) x (-1)³ x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((-1) x (+1)³ x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((-1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- (-1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

+ (-1) x (-1)² x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((-1) x (+1)² x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- ((-1) x (+1)² x (-1)² x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

- (-1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))))

+ (-1) x (-1)³ x ((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) [**f:c=1-last : 1-first*]

x

(the wave function)

AND/OR

(the wave function)

x

((1 x (+0.5.....-(-0.5.....)) x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5)) OR (+1)) x Z 3 and/or Z 4 ((+1) x (+1)³ - (-1) x (+1)³ -

((+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) - (-1) x (+1)³ x (-1) - ((+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² - (-1) x (-1)² x (+1)²) + ((+1) x

(-1)² x (+1) - (-1) x (-1)² x (+1) - ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1) - (-1) x (+1)² x (-1) - ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1)² -

(-1) x (+1)² x (-1)² - ((+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) - (-1) x (-1)³ x (+1)) + (+1) x (-1)³ - (-1) x (-1)³)

- (1 x 1 x 1...../3 OR (-1)) x Z 3 and/or Z 4 ((+1) x (+1)³ - (-1) x (+1)³ - ((+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) - (-1) x

(+1)³ x (-1) - ((+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² - (-1) x (-1)² x (+1)²) + ((+1) x (-1)² x (+1) - (-1) x (-1)² x (+1))

- ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1) - (-1) x (+1)² x (-1) - ((+1) x (+1)² x (-1)² - (-1) x (+1)² x (-1)² - ((+1) x (-1)³

x (+1) - (-1) x (-1)³ x (+1)) + (+1) x (-1)³ - (-1) x (-1)³) [**f:c=1-first : 1-last, next: 2:1 or 1:2*]

x

(the energy wave function)

AND/OR

(the energy wave function)

x

$((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5))) \text{ OR } (+1)) \times Z1 \text{ and/or } Z2 ((+1) \times (+1)^3 - ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (+1) \times (-1)^3)$

$-((-1) \times (+1)^3 - ((-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1) \times (-1)^3))$

$-(1 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \text{ OR } (-1)) \times Z1 \text{ and/or } Z2 ((+1) \times (+1)^3 - ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (+1) \times (-1)^3)$

$-((-1) \times (+1)^3 - ((-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2) + (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 - (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1)) + (-1) \times (-1)^3))$ [*f:c=0:2, next: 1:2 or 0:3]

x

$(+1 / -+0.0 +0.0 \setminus -+1) \times 0^5$ (in Left-Right|Up-Down|Front-Back directions) Also, those dimensions could make the next function, but those new instants could be based on a potential that could transform into many probabilistic or interdependent formations. Likely, it can make two more major groups of structures based on its asymmetric nature. Those dimensional structures could separate the previous structures into many more groups as a separation (break) of symmetry (like an asymmetry) depending on the state of probability or interdependent position, which doesn't have a fixed state. That relative 3D (LR|UD|FB) interactions (the two other standard dimensions: UD|FB) would increase the dimensional density making 3-dimensional (3D) formations. Consequently, that separation could make two different dimensional structures with unstable natures like charge, mass and spin that have a potential to behave like outside and inside structures. E.g., Free dimensional structures: "bosons like photons/gluons". Compressed dimensional structures: "leptons like electrons/quarks". "Presumably, energy could split, making compact objects between them. *(15)" And a polarized wave function would polarize elementary sub-waves into a very high degree like this: E.g., Astronomers using radio telescopes have discovered and characterized ASKAP J173608.2-321635, a highly-polarized, highly-variable, steep-spectrum radio source located just 4 degrees from the Milky Way's center.

According to the calculation, mainly there are two types of most possible dimensional structures (E.g., Zone 1 and Zone 3). E.g.:

Zone 1 == A relatively free structure (\ This is "+1-1 Area 1 & 2" AND/OR "-1+1 Area 1 & 2": //

$((+1 / -+0.0 +0.0 \setminus -+1) \times 0^5 (LR|UD|FB) \text{ OR } (+1 \text{ and/or } 0 \text{ and/or } -+1) \times 0^5) \times (\text{the energy wave function}) \times ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \text{ and/or } (0 \text{ or } 1 \dots)) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((+1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) + (+1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((+1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) + (+1) \times (-1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((-1) \times (+1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((-1) \times (+1)^3 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) + (-1) \times (-1)^2 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - ((-1) \times (+1)^2 \times (-1)^2 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) - (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1))) + (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times ((1 \times (+0.5 \dots -(-0.5 \dots))) \times (2/3 / (1 \dots x(5/5)) - 1 \dots /3)) \text{ OR } (+1(-1)))$

1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))))) [*f:c=2-last : 1-first] x (the wave function)

x (the polarized wave function)

AND/OR

(the polarized wave function) x A relatively compressed structure (((+1 /-+0.0)x0^5(LR|UD|FB) || (+-0.0\

+1)x0^5(LR|UD|FB)) OR (+1 and/or 0 and/or -1)x0^5) x (the energy wave function) x

((+1) x (+1)^3 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) and/or (0 or 1.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) -
 ((+1) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - (+1) x (-1)^2 x
 (+1)^2 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) + (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x ((1 x
 (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - ((+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5.....
 -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - ((+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x
 (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 /
 (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) + (+1) x (-1)^3 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) -
 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) - ((-1) x (+1)^3 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR
 (+1-(-1))) - ((-1) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) -
 (-1) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) + (-1) x (-1)^2
 x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - ((-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x ((1 x
 (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - ((-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x ((1 x (+0.5.....
 -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) - (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3
 / (1.....x(5/5)) - 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1))) + (-1) x (-1)^3 x ((1 x (+0.5..... -(-0.5.....)) x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5)) -
 1...../3)) OR (+1-(-1)))) [*f:c=1-mid :2] x (the wave function)

THE MOST POSSIBLE STRUCTURE/ MATERIAL FORMS/RŪPA (The relatively free structure in Zone 1)

(According to Abhidhamma, there are 4 great material forms in 24 derived material forms that make a Matter Zone.)

The formation of dimensional sets (sub-waves) with Spin 0.5 (or 1/2) and Spin 1 (like Fermions and Bosons in the Standard Model, including the dimensional sets in Higgs particle (H)):

== ((the energy wave function) x Area 1 in Zone 1:

((**H particle-left**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” *virtual/hidden U*

quark-left:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5” -*(virtual/hidden U*

quark-right(-spin):“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **H**

particle-left(-spin):“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”))

- (**H particle-right**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” *virtual/hidden U*

quark-left:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” -*(virtual/hidden U*

quark-right(-spin):“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **H particle-right(-spin)**:“-0.5..... x

(+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (+1)^3 x (**H:“+1”** or +1-1 or 0.0 or **P** or **U:“-1”**)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^3 x (**U** or **P:“+1”** or +1-1 or 0 or **Z:“-1”**)x0^5”))”-- simple sets -- **H**, +1-1, 0.0, **P** or **U** and **Z** would make units separately!

AND/OR

(-**P particle-left**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **P**

particle-left(+particle):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”))

- (-**P particle-right**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **P particle-right(+particle)**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^3 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)) -- Some emerging and organizing formations/structures

of the LR or UD or FB structures/sets could behave like the 3 generations of elementary sub-waves/waves! Also, the generations of Matter Zones called Rūpa Santhati in Abhidhamma could make the mass called Rūpa Sarira/body.

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (+1)^3 x (**P** or **U:“-1”** or 0.0 or +1-1 or **H:“+1”**)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^3 x (**Z:“-1”** or 0.0 or +1-1 or **U** or **P:“+1”**)x0^5”))”-- simple sets -- The +1, +1-1, 0, and -1 are like fields/Bhūmi!

- (((**E lepton-l**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” v./h. **D quark-l**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (v./h. **D quark-r(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **E lepton-l(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (**E lepton-r**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” v./h. **D quark-l**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (v./h. **D quark-r(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **E lepton-r(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x (**E**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **M**:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x (**M**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **_**:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

- (**M particle-l**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **M particle-l(+p)**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (**M particle-r**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **M particle-r(+p)**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x (**M**:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **E**:“+1)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)³ x (-1) x (**_**:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **M**:“+1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

- (**D quark-l**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **D quark-l(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (**D quark-r**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **D quark-r(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x (**D**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **W**:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x (**W**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **_**:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

- (**W particle-l**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **W particle-l(+p)**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (**W particle-r**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **W particle-r(+p)**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x (**W**:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **D**:“+1)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1)² x (**_**:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **W**:“+1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

+ (**z-l**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **z-l(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (**z-r**:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” - (-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **z-r(-s)**:“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“(+1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x (**z**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **N**:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x (**N**:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **_**:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

- (**N particle-l**:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)² x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” **N**

particle-l(+p):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”
 - (**N particle-r:**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **N particle-r(+p):**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
OR “(“+1 x (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (**N:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **z:**“+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (**_:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **N:**“+1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- ((**U quark-l:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **U quark-l(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
 - (**U quark-r:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **U quark-r(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
OR “(“+1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (**U:**“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **Z:**“-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (**Z:**“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **_:**“-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

(-(**Z particle-l:**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **Z particle-l(+p):**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
 - (**Z particle-r:**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **Z particle-r(+p):**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
OR “(“+1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (**Z:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **U:**“+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (**_:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **Z:**“+1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- ((**D quark-l:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **D quark-l(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
 - (**D quark-r:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **D quark-r(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
OR “(“+1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (**D:**“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **W:**“-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (**W:**“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or **_:**“-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

(-(**W particle-l:**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **W particle-l(+p):**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
 - (**W particle-r:**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5” **W particle-r(+p):**“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
OR “(“+1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (**W:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **D:**“+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (**_:**“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or **W:**“+1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- ((**A-l:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **A-l(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”)
 - (**A-r:**“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 **A-r(-s):**“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5”))

OR (“+1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (A:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or G:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (G:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

(-(G particle-l:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” G

particle-l(+p):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (-(G particle-r:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” G particle-r(+p):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

OR (“+1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (G:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or A:“+1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or G:“+1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

+ ((X-l:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵

X-l(-s):“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”))

- (X-r:“+0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵” +0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x

(-0.0\1)x0⁵ -(-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ X-r(-s):“-0.5..... x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x

1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”) If the Axion is like this A(0.5 spin, 2/3 charge)+X(-0.5 spin, 1/3 charge), it is neutral.

OR (“+1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (X:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or N:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (N:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

(-(N particle-l:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” N

particle-l(=p!, *STOP!):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”) The main

dimension in N particle (+1/+0.0) is not with another dimension like this 1+1 or this -1+1. It is mainly based on both +1..... and 0.000000 only.

- (-(N particle-r:“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵” N particle-r(=p!, *STOP!):“(0 or 1.....) x (+1) x (-1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵”) If this +1/+0.0 newly originated (newly started)

superposition is unstable or disconnected, then N (set) needs 1 or +0.5-0.5 dimensions to be stable and continue, or perhaps it would not appear/exist at the moment in which some other sets appear/exist!

OR (“+1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (N:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or X:“+1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (+1) x (-1)³ x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or N:“+1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

Area 2 in Zone 1: (The 28 Material Forms could exist with the following 24 derived forms as 52 Potential Forms.

Perhaps, the material forms make the electric field, and the potential forms make the magnetic field.)

-(((+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵ +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵))

- (+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵ +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵

-(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵))

OR (“+1 x (-1) x (+1)³ x (_:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)³ x (_:“+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵”))-- simple sets

AND/OR

(-(-(0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -(0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x (2/3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵))

- (-(-(0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0⁵ -(0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)³ x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0⁵))

OR (“+1 x (-1) x (+1)³ x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _:“+1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)³ x (_:“-1” or 0.0

or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- (((+0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

-(-(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (-(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _: “+1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1)) x (+1)^3 x (-1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- (((+0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

-(-(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (-(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _: “+1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1)^2 x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

+ (((+0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

-(-(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0 or 1.....) x (-1)) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x (2,3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- ((- (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 - (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _: “+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (-1)^2 x (+1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- (((+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

((- (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 - (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- ((- (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 - (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _: “+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1) x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- (((+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

((- (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 - (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- ((- (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 - (0 or 1.....) x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _: “+1)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (+1)^2 x (-1)^2 x (: “-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

- (((+0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x (2./3 / (1.....x(5/5))) x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

- (+0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5 +0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -(-0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (-0.0\1)x0^5 -0.5..... x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x 1 x 1...../3 x (+1/+0.0)x0^5))

OR (“(+1 x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (-1)^3 x (+1) x (: “+1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _: “-1”)x0^5”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

$(-(0 \text{ or } 1 \dots)) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

$- (-(0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times (+1) \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

OR “(“+1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _:“+1)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (+1) x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0⁵”))”-- simple sets

$+ ((+0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5 + 0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (-0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - 0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

$- (+0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5 + 0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (-0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - 0.5 \dots \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

OR “(“+1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (_:“-1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (_:“-1” or +1-1 or 0.0 or _:“-1”)x0⁵”))”-- simple sets

AND/OR

$(-(0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times (2/3 / (1 \dots \times (5/5))) \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

$- (-(0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (-0.0 \setminus -1)x0^5 - (0 \text{ or } 1 \dots) \times (-1) \times (-1)^3 \times 1 \times 1 \dots /3 \times (+1/+0.0)x0^5)$

OR “(“+1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or _:“+1)x0⁵” and/or - (“-1 x (-1) x (-1)³ x (_:“-1” or 0.0 or +1-1 or +1)x0⁵”))”-- simple sets

x (the wave function) x (the polarized wave function)

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- 20.) Lecture (Video), "The Theory of Everything | Two Prototype Theories of Everything" - Dr. Don Lincoln: youtube.com/watch?v=6tUZsxjkXBc (between 28-29 minutes). Jul 5, 2017.
- 21.) If atoms were formed at once when $kT \sim 13.6eV$, how are there around a billion CMB photons for every baryon?

14. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I became an independent researcher to find answers to some big questions to help people learn and practice Buddhism without a doubt. I tried to explain the universe's existence by making logical and mathematical

explanations using Buddhist teachings and science. I started the research and calculations in 2017.

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As an entrepreneur, I could spend my income and time on this project.

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Searching for the truth should be a part of our lives.

And that truth shouldn't lead us to harm living beings and regret.

Using unrealistic solutions to reject or ignore reality is not good.

May you find the ultimate truth of life.!

